

Appendix A

Additional Notes on Radiant Floor Modeling

This appendix gathers supplementary material related to the modeling of radiant floor cooling systems. It includes specific focuses and detailed discussions that were originally part of the comprehensive literature review developed for the paper “*Radiant Floor Cooling Systems: A Critical Review of Modeling Methods*”, but were excluded from the main text to maintain narrative continuity. These contents are provided to complement the main thesis discussion, offering additional depth and context in the subject of radiant systems modeling.

A.1. Convection Coefficient for Floor Cooling Applications

Convective exchange with air also needs proper treatment. While a great amount of literature is present for radiant floor heating applications, studies on cooling operation (i.e., a cooled plate facing upward) are comparatively scarce and often lack consistency.

In cooling, analytical analysis suggests negligible convection due to air stratification, but in real environments, non-uniformities such as temperature gradients, sun patches, or pipe spacing initiate air movement. Therefore in this case, analytical results are not considered sufficiently reliable.

Due to variability in actual conditions, modeling convection remains challenging. However, because of its minor contribution in most cases, especially in cooling, simplified models are often acceptable. Above all, Camci et al. [1] provide a detailed review of convective heat transfer in radiant heating and cooling systems, emphasizing experimental findings, modeling strategies, and correlations for predicting convective heat transfer coefficients. A major contribution of the review is the collection and comparison of various empirical correlations that express the convective heat transfer coefficient in terms of dimensionless numbers. They highlight that convective heat transfer is strongly affected by room dimensions, surface orientation (horizontal, vertical, inclined), and the thermal interaction between surfaces. It emphasizes that upward-facing cooled surfaces (e.g., radiant floors in cooling mode) exhibit significantly different convective behavior from downward-facing heated ones due to air stratification and reduced buoyancy-driven motion.

The authors note discrepancies between experimental findings and theoretical models, especially under real-room conditions. This reinforces the need for case-specific validation when applying convective coefficients in simulations.

Table A.1 summarizes the values or correlation proposed in the previously mentioned studies to characterize the convective heat transfer coefficient h_{conv} between the radiant floor surface and the room air node, in cooling applications. To easily allow the comparison among different values, all the references are reported in terms of Nusselt number Nu , and a general correlation to the Rayleigh number Ra can be observed: $Nu = c Ra^n$. It seems evident that there is no neat agreement on the subject, as the proposed coefficient can differ significantly. This could be seen as an additional demonstration of the fact that convection in floor cooling applications is heavily dependent on site-specific conditions, and therefore it is difficult to propose a general approach with broad validity.

Table A.1. Correlations and values of air Nusselt coefficient usable for the cooled floor surface (stratified conditions). Where not stated, the reference temperature is the bulk temperature.

Reference	Nusselt coefficient [-]	Notes
Fishenden and Saunders [2]	$Nu = 0.25 Ra^{1/4}$	$3 \times 10^5 \leq Ra \leq 3 \times 10^{10}$
Min et al. [3]	$Nu = 0.071 Ra^{0.255}$	Ra range not specified
Restrepo & Glicksman [4]	$Nu = 0.587 Ra^{1/4}$	Horizontal heated place facing downwards with cooled sides, $1.66 \cdot 10^6 \leq Ra \leq 3.19 \cdot 10^6$
Alamdari and Hammond [5]	$Nu = 0.586 Ra^{1/5}$	$Ra < 10^{11}$
Awbi and Hatton [6]	$Nu = 2.353 Ra^{0.133}$	$1.02 \cdot 10^{10} \leq Ra \leq 7.12 \cdot 10^{10}$

Olesen et al. [7]	$Nu = 0.654 Ra^{1/4*}$	Reference height for air temperature: $h_{ref} = 0.6 m$	$2.4 \cdot 10^{10} \leq Ra \leq 5.2 \cdot 10^{10}$
	$Nu = 0.499 Ra^{1/4*}$	Reference height for air temperature: $h_{ref} = 1.1 m$	
	$Nu = 184.6^*$	General suggestion, $L_c = 4.8 m$	
Glent [8]	$Nu = 0.265 Ra^{1/4*}$	Ra range not specified	
ASHRAE [9]	$Nu = 0.230 Ra^{1/4*}$	Ra range not specified	
McAdams [10]	$Nu = 0.27 Ra^{1/4}$	$3 \cdot 10^5 \leq Ra \leq 3 \cdot 10^{10}$	
Cholewa et al. [11]	$Nu = 6^*$	$4.6 \cdot 10^8 \leq Ra \leq 1.8 \cdot 10^9, L_c = 1.56 m$	
Karakoyun et al. [12]	$Nu = 161.8 Ra^{-0.1*}$	$h_{ref} = 1.1 m$, heated walls, $1.1 \cdot 10^9 \leq Ra \leq 8.6 \cdot 10^9, L_c = 1.8 m$	
EN 1264-5 [13]	$Nu = 194.7$	$3.8 \cdot 10^9 \leq Ra \leq 5.1 \cdot 10^{10}, L_c = 3 m$ (taken as a typical value)	

* In order to represent all correlations in terms of Nu , the values of g, β, ν and α are calculated for air at $25^\circ C$ ($Ra = 9.5 \cdot 10^7 L_c^3 \Delta T$), and, where needed, the characteristic length is retrieved from references by considering $L_c = 4 \frac{Area}{Perimeter}$.

The different correlations are also visually presented in Figure A.1. Despite some of them bring similar results, probably because of similar conditions employed in the studies, a wide range of Nusselt values is actually covered.

Figure A.1. Graphical representation of the correlations available for the Nusselt number in stratified natural convection over a horizontal plate, which is the case of floor cooling applications.

A.2. Models Used in Software

Energy performance simulation tools like TRNSYS and EnergyPlus are widely used in both research and industry to evaluate and optimize building systems. Both programs support dynamic modeling of radiant floor systems with thermal coupling to the building environment, aligning with the comprehensive coupled methods already discussed.

EnergyPlus modeling is based on the transfer function method [14], [15], and includes both 1D and 2D models for RFs. The 1D method was validated in a successive study by Chantrasrisalai et al. [16]. However, a more recent paper by Brideau et al. [17] questioned the EnergyPlus correct estimation of the conductive heat transfer within the floor, comparing the output of its simulations with reference finite elements analysis. Only the 2D code was found to be coherent with the benchmark solution, but after a manual tuning of the parameters.

On the other end, the TRNSYS simulation software provides three distinct modeling methods for active surfaces such as TABS and ESS, which were validated and compared in a study by Rey et al. [18]. The first approach is the active layer method that is integrated into “Type 56”, which is the TRNSYS model for a general built environment with multiple thermal zones. The model was developed following Glück’s method [19], which establishes a conduction network using a correction similar to the conduction shape factor approach. This resistive approach is employed for steady-state calculations but is also regarded as valid for transient conditions. “Type 653”, the so called “Simple Floor Heating System” model, treats the floor as a lumped capacitance and accounts for the heat transfer between the tube and the floor with a heat exchanger approach. Instead, “Type 933”, is a more detailed modeling method that operates a 3D analysis of the conduction within the slab; therefore, it requires a relevantly larger computational effort. “Type 993” was reported to be the least accurate method, whereas the two lumped approaches were able to predict more correctly the temperature within the pipes and the surface temperature. However, the outputs of the models are particularly dependent on several input parameters which are hard to know exactly; therefore, the correct estimation with the last two methods was obtained after a tuning process on those parameters.

The techniques used in such simulation software suffer from the same limitations already observed: either the description is too simplistic and struggles to provide accurate results, or it is too detailed, making it impractical for real-world case studies where users may not know the full configuration details. In addition, even though these software tools account for many of the important phenomena, they still have the same problems as other modeling methods in terms of convective exchange and accounting for furniture.

A.3. Considerations on Modeling Accuracy

Besides the rather clear distinction between the two main model classes, within each category there is no clear distinction in terms of the convenience of different types of heat transfer resolution methods. Numerical, analytical, and semi-analytical methods can indeed achieve similar levels of accuracy, as demonstrated by experimental validations where average errors of a few tenths of a degree Celsius are often obtained. However, the use of one method or another may be more or less appropriate in specific cases, depending on the application for which the modeling is required, the computational capabilities available, and the creative effort one wishes to invest in the modeling phase of the specific system.

Simplified methods, such as those that employ a 1D or 2D approach to investigate a section of the floor, or even 0D models that provide a lumped representation of the problem, typically possess general applicability. Indeed, their output is not dependent on specific room dimensions or pipework configurations, such as serpentine or spiral layouts. And consequently, as evident in Figure 5, they are the main source for design and control purposes, thanks to their generality. Meanwhile, the detailed 3D methods, as well as the coupled floor-building models, require more thoughtful tailoring to the specific dimensions and configuration of the room being considered.

Remarkably, it might be useful to further investigate the accuracy actually needed in the use of the RFCS models. As highlighted in previous sections, two of the most common applications are the design and the control of the cooling systems. In both cases, accuracy of a few tenths of a degree might be significantly superior to what is actually required. Indeed, the design calculations aim to develop a system configuration that can fulfill the comfort and energy requirements during its operation. However, for obvious reasons, a conservative approach is generally taken at this stage, whereby the capacity of the system tends to be over-dimensioned in order to ensure good robustness even under rare but extreme conditions. In this context, a model that provides accuracies to tenths of a degree would be over-qualified for real needs. And frequently, steady-state considerations are enough in these situations.

On the other hand, for control applications, dynamic and more accurate modeling could be useful to optimize the operation of the system. However, in these cases, the problem lies instead in the ability to correctly assess the actual state of the building and the system during its operation. For instance, these systems controllers are typically based on the measurement of the ambient temperature using a room thermostat; this applies to current installations as well as many methods still in the R&D phase. The problem is then the actual reliability of the temperature measurement made by the thermostat, since its placement in the room or building often does not reflect the actual internal conditions (Shehadi, 2019): errors up to 2°C have been reported in some scenarios. Therefore, using a system model within a control methodology that aims for much higher accuracy could prove useless in this case as well.

Consequently, selecting the appropriate model for the specific application and context in which it will be used is crucial. For example, in situations where very precise control is desired and where special emphasis is placed on correctly estimating the system state variables, a modeling approach capable of achieving high accuracy would be required. Similar considerations apply to all the features previously listed for each model: there is no need to complicate the treatment by introducing a detailed 3D or 2D description if the target uses do not require it, nor is there a need to treat the problem as time-varying if equally significant results can be obtained with a steady-state analysis. This same principle underlies the use of simplified methods to account for the effect of solar radiation, radiative exchange with walls, convective heat transfer, and presence of furniture.

The analysis just conducted reveals indeed the necessity to tailor the complexity and the accuracy of the modeling method to the specific context for which it is needed. However, as in practical and typically faced contexts great accuracy is not expected, in these situations a deeply detailed model, which may also require the need for more detailed simulations to be characterized as some of the reviewed methods do, risks being worthless.

Therefore, in our view, future research trends should aim at the development of modeling methods that are oriented toward practical and widespread applications. New models should be easy to

characterize, depending on a limited number of parameters that could be easily obtained from building construction projects or on-site surveys. That is, they should be simply employable without the need for too detailed knowledge of the geometrical and constructive configuration of the system. Moreover, the approach to follow should be the integrated one, considering the coupling between the floor and the rest of the building. Although such a target for wider application would probably involve a lowering of accuracy expectations even in coupled models, overall energy benefits could still be achieved, especially if models are used to improve the control methodologies for both existing and new buildings. A valuable tool to address this need for easily characterizable modeling methods could come from a large-scale monitoring campaign involving actual buildings. The collection of operational data from a wide variety of practical applications could facilitate the development of novel gray-box techniques for modeling buildings equipped with radiant floor cooling systems, by integrating these data with the existing knowledge of the physical phenomena governing their operation.

Additionally, a significant gap in the available literature on RFCS modeling methods is the absence of some schematization of the furniture and other obstacles to heat transfer, which might deeply interfere with the heat transfer mechanism previously described, as highlighted by preliminary research investigations on the topic. Even the presence of people and additional internal gains are never fully evaluated since, besides being other terms to take into account in the sensible and latent energy balances, they have a significant influence on the floor heat transfer itself due to the thermal plumes they produce, which increase the convective exchange. As a general suggestion for further research, an effective way to address these modeling gaps would be to conduct several dedicated experimental campaigns on the topics, which may provide the most appropriate means to capture physical behaviors and establish correlations or correction coefficients to be integrated into models. Not considering these effects can severely undermine model accuracy in real-world scenarios. Therefore, further work on the reliable schematization of these effects is needed, and it should be widely applicable as well.

A.4. References

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Appendix B

Illustrative Application of a Prediction-Based HVAC Control for Hybrid Heat Pumps

This appendix summarizes the published study entitled “*Improving energy efficiency through forecast-driven control in hybrid heat pumps*”. The purpose of this preliminary study was to evaluate whether simple, data-driven forecasting methods could improve the supervisory operation of hybrid heat pumps (HHPs) and deliver tangible benefits compared to standard weather-compensation control.

B.1. Introduction

A promising generation device for space heating in buildings is the so-called hybrid heat pump. This technology generally integrates a gas boiler and an air-source heat pump (ASHP), with the two units working jointly to meet the thermal demand. Indeed, one of the main problems with ASHPs is that they face the worst operating conditions – i.e. reduced heating capacity and low efficiency – in the most severe outdoor conditions, when the building heating load is at its maximum. With the use of HHPs, these conditions might be effectively covered by the activation of the boiler to support the heat pump. These systems experienced remarkable growth in the domestic heating market in recent years, largely due to the increasing trend towards the electrification of thermal energy services. Their penetration is particularly significant in Italy, which was reported to be the leading country in Europe for HHP installations [1].

As seen, along with the installation of new, high-performance HVAC systems, energy efficiency in buildings can be further enhanced by improving control strategies for their use. Non-optimal control can lead to highly inefficient operation, even with the latest-generation equipment. Traditional control strategies for commercial products are generally straightforward. The water supply temperature is typically controlled with a fixed set-point or using a weather compensation strategy. Even if some procedures are available for the determination of the optimal weather compensation curve [2], in practical applications the relationship between outdoor conditions and water supply temperatures is generally set to the device's default configuration or to a trial-and-error calibration of installers and/or owners. Given the arbitrariness of the process, a large share of residential buildings is likely to have a non-optimal control of heating and cooling systems operation [3], [4]. As a result, a clear need for more advanced HHP control strategies emerged to realize their true energy-saving potential. Among other possible strategies, the integration of data-driven modeling techniques (e.g., black-box or gray-box methods) directly into the controller could improve control efficiency while effectively reducing the complexity associated with detailed physical modeling requirements [5], [6], [7].

In this part of the research, propaedeutically to the further analysis at the core of the thesis, we present the development of an HHP control procedure based on a black-box modeling procedure. Using the prediction, heaters' performance can be forecasted and the optimal operating configuration in terms of generator activation and water supply temperature can be targeted. The system scheme is presented in Figure B.1.

Figure B.1. Summary diagram of an AR-based predictive controller for hybrid heat pumps.

This study evaluates the effectiveness of this control and compares it to other reference control strategies. The seasonal performance of the HHP is evaluated in 21 different scenarios, 3 of which are based on real monitored data, while the other 18 are simulated case studies. The latter dataset is selected to represent the Italian housing stock, enabling a generalizable analysis at the country level.

B.1.1. Literature and General Remarks on Hybrid Heat Pumps

The use of hybrid heat pumps has increased considerably in recent years. Beccali et al. [8] provided a comprehensive review of the state of the art in scientific research on these systems, highlighting the variety of perspectives and analyses. Several studies highlighted the potential of these systems. Initial works aimed to estimate the benefits of the use of HHPs in monetary or primary energy terms, while others discussed and compared the influence of the control methodology on the hybrid systems.

In their publication [9], Hackel and Pertzborn simulated the potential savings achievable by integrating a ground-source heat pump (GSHP) with a gas boiler in a residential scenario. They found that the hybrid alternative performed better than a conventional GSHP in terms of operational costs and CO₂ emissions. Similarly, in the research by Li et al [10] a reduction in operational expenses was observed when using a sewage-source hybrid HP instead of a conventional coal-fired heating system. However, ground and sewage-source HPs do not suffer from critical external conditions as much as air-source heat pumps, so the benefits mainly arise from the possibility of HP size reduction rather than from operational savings.

Other studies focused on the potential of ASHP hybrid systems. Klein et al. [11] conducted simulations in West German buildings, studying an HHP series-connected, with the HP pre-heating the boiler inlet water. Although the HP alone was the best alternative in terms of energy consumption, they found significant primary energy savings with HHPs compared to gas boilers. On the other hand, HP alone was the most expensive option in terms of total cost, and HHP also failed to offer any cost savings over a boiler. The need for dedicated incentives on such systems was therefore emphasized, especially in scenarios where the electricity-gas price ratio is high. Similarly, Park and colleagues [12] found substantial energy savings in a Korean scenario, but these did not

translate into economic savings. Di Perna et al. drew similar conclusions in their study of a hybrid generator in a residential building in Milan, Italy [13].

Despite the variability of their economic feasibility depending on the specific scenario, HHPs have been found capable of significantly reducing the energy-related emissions of the building sector, thanks to the achievable primary energy savings. Other studies evaluated the large-scale implications, at the level of urban agglomerations, that the widespread adoption of hybrid heat pumps in existing buildings could bring. Asaee et al. [14] found that ASHP retrofit, if coupled with boiler integration, is feasible in almost 3/4 of the Canadian housing stock. Such a widespread measure would allow a 36% reduction in national energy usage. Vuillecard and his team [15] tested several heat generation systems on a modest sample of 40 dwellings on the French territory. They found that the HHP installation would significantly limit the impact of the total load on the electric grid, which is a major limitation for the diffusion of heat pumps. Regarding the Italian scenario, Schito et al. [16] addressed the energy saving possibilities resulting from a comprehensive substitution of heat generators within the residential stock. The hybrid heat pump emerged as the most cost-effective generator in almost all scenarios, being also robust to changes in energy prices and control strategies. Similarly, Bennet et al. analyzed the possible benefits of a widespread adoption of HHPs in the English residential stock [17]. They concluded that with current prices, hybrid systems are not economically viable for the UK market yet. However, their implementation could significantly relieve the energy grid compared to HPs only.

Bennet's research also highlighted the importance of selecting the right operating logic for HHPs. The switch criterion plays a crucial role in placing the performance of the hybrid system between that of the HP and the boiler. To achieve significant savings, it is thus necessary to pursue the optimal choice of system configuration and switching logic. An extensive study on system configurations and switch temperatures was carried out by Bagarella et al. in [18]. They simulated various combinations $T_{cut-off}$ and $T_{bivalent}$, which respectively represent the external temperature value below which only the boiler is used – also referred as switch temperature – and the temperature at which the HP can fully satisfy the heat load without modulation. The value of $T_{bivalent}$ is dependent on the HP dimensioning for the specific case study, whereas the value of $T_{cut-off}$ is an arbitrary variable to be selected by users or installers. In a cold-humid climate, it was found that optimal performance with a well-sized heat pump – i.e., low bivalent temperature – could be achieved with a purely alternative system, where $T_{cut-off} = T_{bivalent}$. On the other hand, with a smaller HP, greater energy savings were achieved by adopting an integrative configuration. In mild-dry climates, the integrative configuration was found to be more convenient, even with a large HP size, but not significantly better than the alternative. Dongellini et al. [19] also studied the impact of HHP sizing and control strategies. Examining a case study with low-temperature emitters, they concluded that both integrative and alternative operation modalities provide improvements in the seasonal efficiency of the HHP system with respect to monovalent heaters, if cut-off and bivalent temperatures are properly selected. The study by Wullhorst et al. [20] addressed the HHP topic with a focus on the back-up unit. They found a clear interaction between the type, placement, and control of the back-up heater, which could significantly affect the overall performance of the HHP. Another paper by Roccatello et al. [21] analyzed parallel and series configurations, as well as alternative and integrative logics. In terms of primary energy consumption, the integrative logic with the series

configuration was found to be the best strategy, but the parallel alternative, if the correct switching temperature was chosen, gave similar results.

Based on the above discussion, it is easy to see that hybrid heating systems could lead to significant energy and economic savings in several climatic conditions, if properly configured. The best configuration, whether alternative or integrative, depends on the size of the heat pump and the climate. It is widely acknowledged that control of these systems is a crucial aspect that can significantly influence their feasibility. Given that, many studies specifically addressed the issue of HHP control.

B.2. Description of the HHP Control

The developed supervisory control logic is based on two sequential steps: forecasting and optimization. First, the AR predictive methodology is used to forecast the next hourly building heat demand. The forecast is then used to evaluate the expected performance of the two heat generators for the next hour. Based on this evaluation, the most cost-effective heating unit is scheduled for the next hour.

This procedure is intended to be implemented as a supervisory control layer for standard HHP systems, aimed at the supply temperature set-point selection for HHP operation (see the control architecture in Figure B.2). Cascaded with this supervisory structure, a standard low-level controller (e.g., PID) is integrated into the HHP system to realize the supply temperature set-point and correlated thermal power output. Additionally, a standard zone controller is employed to maintain the thermal zone's internal temperature within the accepted band gap. This is accomplished by using internal thermostat/s placed within the thermal zone to help compensate for potential errors in predicting heat generation output.

Figure B.2. Control box diagram of a hybrid heat pump system with the AR-based integrated control logic implemented.

The scheme shown in Figure B.2 provides a complete representation of the control logic of an HHP system with forecast-based strategy. The AR block is the one where forecasts are made based on previous observations, then the optimization block calculates the Boolean to turn on the most advantageous heat generator. The information coming from the supervisory control is fed to the HHP block, where the selected generator is activated and its internal control (e.g. PID) works to reach the given set-point. The actual supply temperature is fed to the heating terminals, and a thermal load is given to the building. Finally, the internal temperature is measured and a deadband controller is used to maintain the desired internal set-point even in the presence of prediction errors. If the predicted variables are not sufficient to maintain the internal temperature (i.e. a deficit forecast), the

AR correction switch forces the boiler to operate at a fixed supply temperature.

The switch criterion between the two heat generation units is based on a cost-driven logic. The objective function to minimize is the forecasted cost for the next hour, specifically:

$$cost^{(i)} = \frac{Q_{forecast}^{(i)}}{COP_{forecast}^{(i)}} \cdot c_{el} \cdot (HP_{ON}^{(i)}) + \frac{Q_{forecast}^{(i)}}{\eta_{forecast}^{(i)}} \cdot c_{gas} \cdot (1 - HP_{ON}^{(i)}), \quad (B.1)$$

where $cost^{(i)}$ is the energy expense for the next hour (i), and it is a function of the load forecast ($Q_{forecast}^{(i)}$), the estimated performance parameters ($COP_{forecast}^{(i)}$ and $\eta_{forecast}^{(i)}$) and the energy costs in €/kWh (c_{el} and c_{gas}). The control variable to be defined is the value of the Boolean $HP_{ON}^{(i)}$, representing the activation of the heat pump at the next timestep.

The optimization problem employed is trivial, as it is only used to determine whether to activate the HP or the boiler. Due to the lack of thermal energy storage, a short forecasting horizon of 1 hour (only 1 timestep ahead) is used in this case. The other operational parameters necessary to satisfy the heat demand (i.e., supply temperature and heating load) are selected by the forecasting algorithm and they do not take part in the optimization, as they are imposed to maintain comfort conditions in the heated space, which is a constraint of the problem. Consequently, the COP and the efficiency of the HP and the boiler, respectively, are uniquely known by their performance models. Energy costs are taken as constant over time.

The heat generators performance estimation is based on specific models. The accuracy of the load and supply temperature forecasts influences the consistency of the hourly cost function evaluation. Consequently, more accurate forecasts should result in more optimal control.

B.2.1. Predictive Model

The first step of the procedure concerns the prediction of the building thermal load. This is achieved using data-driven techniques, which estimate the heating requirements of the building and the corresponding supply temperature.

Selection of the Forecasting Method

A straightforward forecasting method is selected: the AR model, a linear approach that belongs to the ARMA (Autoregressive Moving Average) class of methods. Although the AR methodology has limitations in terms of predictive ability – it is primarily suitable for approximating linear trends – it offers significant advantages in terms of simplicity and computational efficiency compared to more advanced deep learning techniques.

A key reason for selecting the AR model was the goal of developing efficient control techniques without requiring additional software and hardware resources for the HHP control. The AR implementation cost is low, as its training (both pre-training and in-operation updating) involves only basic linear operations: when the least squares estimation technique is used, the problem reduces to matrix inversion [22], which can be easily handled by an on-board processor. Additionally, since heat transfer in a building exhibits a sufficiently smooth dynamics, the AR can effectively capture its evolution, especially for a one-hour-ahead forecasting horizon.

Indeed, as reported by literature [23], the AR model offers a good trade-off for widespread

applications. Specifically, in residential scenarios where the feasibility and cost-effectiveness of a method are critical for adoption, AR-based control strategies are particularly well-suited and are worth further analysis.

Autoregressive Predictive Model

AR only requires the historical data of the variable under investigation to establish a linear relationship between past values and the forecast. The linear combination of previous observed values is defined by the autoregressive coefficients, which weigh each contribution. In our specific case, the algorithm uses the heat demand data in n previous timesteps (hours) and provides a forecast for the next hour's load. The mathematical representation is:

$$Q_{forecast}^{(t+1)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \phi_Q^{(i)} \cdot Q^{(t-n+i)}, \quad (B.2)$$

where $Q_{forecast}^{(t+1)}$ is the predicted hourly thermal load and $\phi_Q^{(i)}$ represent the autoregressive coefficients, namely the weight of previous hourly loads $Q^{(t-n+i)}$. These coefficients should be identified to completely characterize the operational context of the generator, as they are somewhat representative of the heat load pattern. An initial period is therefore used for model training: a large database of j values is collected and used to calculate the $\phi_Q^{(i)}$ coefficients with an identification technique based on the least-square approximation of the recorded heating load values. During the training phase, the AR control is not yet operational, therefore the default control of the building heating system would be employed. Once the training phase is complete, the optimized forecast-based control is enabled. Furthermore, additional periodic updates of the coefficients are planned on a regular basis to account for potential variations in the behavior of the building or the climate. The update is repeated every m timesteps. During these subsequent updates, the AR-based control can continue to operate, as the training is performed over a moving window of j values, some of which may also be used, hour by hour, for prediction.

Since the internal thermostat ensures that the internal temperature set-point is maintained, the hourly thermal energy demand can be considered satisfied in any situation, correcting possible prediction errors generated by the AR algorithm. Errors are thus prevented from accumulating, and the heat load terms on the right side of Eq. 2 represent the actual values of energy demand.

The methodology is intuitively illustrated in Figure B.3.

Figure B.3. Simplified scheme of the autoregressive forecasting procedure used for heating load and supply temperature prediction.

The AR prediction procedure is also used for the generator supply temperature. In addition, the same forecasting technique is used to estimate the outdoor temperature, as it also affects the performance of the heating equipment (i.e., the heat pump unit).

The same values of j , n , and m are used for both heat and temperature. The identification of the best combination of j , n , and m that provides the best forecast in each application depends on the specific case. However, in this work, we analyze and propose a nearly-optimal triplet that can effectively applied in all the considered buildings of the Italian scenario. Possible values, expressed as days, are:

$$j = [14, 21, 28, 35, 42] \quad n = [2, 4, 7, 8] \quad m = [4, 7, 14]$$

The accuracy of the forecasting algorithm is evaluated using the average hourly error between the actual and predicted values of heating load and supply temperature. The mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) might be used to evaluate the accuracy of the supply temperature prediction, considering the error on the internal set-point and the supply temperature delta.

$$MAPE_T = \frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{T_{s,forecast}^{(i)} - T_s^{(i)}}{T_s^{(i)} - T_{int,SP}} \right|. \quad (B.4)$$

However, MAPE is found to be unreliable for heating load predictions, as large percentage errors could occur when the actual demand is very low. In such instances, even though the errors may be insignificant from an energy perspective, the MAPE value could still rise significantly (e.g., up to 100% when an incorrect switch-off is predicted). To address this, we calculate a modified version of MAPE (wMAPE), weighted by thermal load values. This weighted approach assigns greater significance to errors occurring during periods of higher energy demand, thus providing a more accurate assessment of their energetic impact:

$$wMAPE_Q = \frac{1}{\sum_i Q^{(i)}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} \left[\left| \frac{(Q_{forecast}^{(i)} - Q^{(i)})}{Q^{(i)}} \right| Q^{(i)} \right]. \quad (B.5)$$

The performance metric is only calculated in timesteps (i) when the hourly heat load is non-zero ($Q^{(i)} > 0$) since, in practice, low-level controls such as the room thermostat would prevent the activation of the HHP in the event of a false activation forecast.

Finally, for ease of interpretation, an absolute error in the water supply temperature was also provided.

$$MAE_T = \frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} |T_{s,forecast}^{(i)} - T_s^{(i)}| \quad (B.6)$$

B.2.2. Hybrid Heat Pump Performance Assessment

The load and supply temperature forecasts are used to estimate the one-hour-ahead behavior of the heat generation unit and control it as efficiently as possible. To achieve this, HHP performance estimation and control criteria need to be addressed. The HHP systems implemented in the study's analyzed scenarios are constituted by a classic-sized condensing boiler and a well-sized HP.

Considering previous literature findings [18], [19], with such configuration the alternative operating mode is believed to be an effective logic for the system operation.

Specific modeling methods available by manufacturers should be used in this phase, in order to accurately represent the operation of each generator. Partial load conditions should be considered, given their high impact on results. For this study, a customized model, based on preceding studies, is used for the HP. For the boiler, a standardized procedure is used to interpolate manufacturer's data and correct it based on actual operating conditions.

B.3. Benchmark Building Datasets

For testing the predictive model and assessing its related advantages, an extensive building load dataset was generated using TRNSYS-simulated benchmark buildings. This approach allowed for the testing of our methodology across various climatic and building scenarios, helping to identify the strengths and limitations specific to each context. Additionally, three field-monitored buildings were utilized to further assess the forecasting accuracy in real cases and the whole control logic.

The datasets are used twice: first, to carry out the training and testing of the AR predictive method, then to evaluate the energy consumption resulting from the application of the proposed control.

B.3.1. Simulative Dataset

Due to the important influence of climatic conditions and building insulation levels on HHP performance [11], several climates and building types were simulated in the TRNSYS environment. Concerning the climate, three Italian major cities are considered, corresponding to the most inhabited climatic zones: Parma (HDD=2502), Florence (HDD=1821), and Bari (HDD=1185). These locations can be qualitatively classified as having a cold, mild, and warm climate, respectively. In simulations, for each location the hourly climatic data was taken from the Italian typical meteorological year (TMY) database.

Within each climatic scenario, three typical dwellings were considered: an apartment in a multi-family house built in the 1980s with radiators (80 m²), a detached single-family house built in the 1990s with radiators (140 m²), and a newer detached house built in the 2000s (130 m²) with a higher level of thermal insulation and radiant floor as heating terminal.

Coupled with each building typology, specific occupational patterns for domestic use were considered. Both regular (extremely repetitive) and more randomized.

Overall, the simulated dataset derived from 18 distinct case studies, as summarized in Table B.1. These case studies also vary in terms of building design load factor and heat pump size. Conventional sizing was adopted for the boilers: 24.1 kW for each case study. In contrast, the heat pumps were sized slightly smaller, yet close to the building design load [24], with the aim of achieving a balance between efficiency and performance.

Table B.1. Summary of the key features of the 18 simulated case studies, including building characteristics and thermal system sizing, used for the AR control strategy application.

Name	Location	Building typology	Occupancy pattern	Design heating load [kW]	Transmittance value [W/m ² K]	HP nominal heating output [kW]
Cold 1	Parma	1980s flat	Regular	5.5	1.0	6.0

Cold 1R	Parma	1980s flat	Randomized	5.5	1.0	6.0
Cold 2	Parma	1990s villa	Regular	8.9	0.7	8.0
Cold 2R	Parma	1990s villa	Randomized	8.9	0.7	8.0
Cold 3	Parma	2000s villa	Regular	4.4	0.2	6.0
Cold 3R	Parma	2000s villa	Randomized	4.4	0.2	6.0
Mild 1	Florence	1980s flat	Regular	4.4	1.0	6.0
Mild 1R	Florence	1980s flat	Randomized	4.4	1.0	6.0
Mild 2	Florence	1990s villa	Regular	8.7	0.9	8.0
Mild 2R	Florence	1990s villa	Randomized	8.7	0.9	8.0
Mild 3	Florence	2000s villa	Regular	3.9	0.3	6.0
Mild 3R	Florence	2000s villa	Randomized	3.9	0.3	6.0
Warm 1	Bari	1980s flat	Regular	4.4	1.0	6.0
Warm 1R	Bari	1980s flat	Randomized	4.4	1.0	6.0
Warm 2	Bari	1990s villa	Regular	8.6	0.8	8.0
Warm 2R	Bari	1990s villa	Randomized	8.6	0.8	8.0
Warm 3	Bari	2000s villa	Regular	4.2	0.3	6.0
Warm 3R	Bari	2000s villa	Randomized	4.2	0.3	6.0

The annual building heating demand was calculated using a 1-hour simulation timestep. In addition to the actual thermal energy demand, it was necessary to determine the ideal water supply temperature from the heat generator to deliver that amount of heat. To achieve this, we also modeled the two types of heating terminals used in the system: radiators and radiant floor panels.

Radiators were analytically modelled considering the radiative and convective heat transfer processes. The device was schematized as an array of vertical cylinders and required dimensionless numbers for natural convection assessment were calculated accordingly [25]. Internal convection and conduction through the metal tube were neglected, due to their low contribution to overall thermal resistance.

An extremely simple modeling was used to characterize radiant floors, provided by the standard EN 1264-2:2008 [26], which evaluates the thermal resistance between tubes and the operative temperature of the thermal zone. No thermal capacity of the slab is considered.

B.3.2. Field-Monitored Dataset

The hypotheses and simplifications adopted in simulations inevitably lead to differences from actual conditions encountered in real-world applications. Real data is significantly influenced by unpredictable events, such as the various behaviors that might occur in a real house and the non-ideal operation and control of the heat generator.

Therefore a test of the forecasting technique on real data was also performed, starting from measurements recorded during the actual operation of real residential heating systems. The field-monitored dataset here employed was acquired during the operation of 3 residential buildings placed on the Italian territory, in the winter season December 2021 - March 2022. No information about the building was known except for the geographical location. The data “Exp1”, “Exp2”, and “Exp3” were respectively gathered from buildings in Genoa (HDD=1435), Como (HDD=2228), and Pavia (HDD=2623).

An example of these heating load profiles is shown in Figure B.4, which showcases the typical dynamics of thermal output along with the frequent on/off cycling of the heat generator. These dynamics cannot be ascribed to the building's thermal load; rather, they are influenced by the particular control system and the heat capacity of the water-based equipment. It is evident that a 10-

minute timescale is insufficient for accurately depicting the building load, which requires at least averaging over a longer duration. Therefore, a pre-processing phase was necessary to apply the forecasting algorithm to the real-world dataset. This phase involved cleaning and transformation of the recorded time series to produce a version suitable for AR model training and validation.

Figure B.4. 10-minute thermal power data recorded from on-field operation of a domestic boiler located in Como, Italy.

An example of the final monitored datasets, after preprocessing, is presented in Figure B.5.

Figure B.5. Original and pre-processed datasets obtained from the monitoring of the case study EXP3 in terms of hourly heating load and supply temperature to the heating terminals.

B.4. Simulation of the Proposed HHP Control

The forecasting algorithm and energy performance assessment were simulated in a MATLAB environment to evaluate the performance of the proposed control. On an hourly basis, AR predictions were performed, HHP performance was estimated, and energy consumption and cost were calculated. Additionally, the effect of thermostatic zone control was incorporated into our code by triggering an early system shutdown when a surplus was predicted and activating the boiler at a

high supply temperature when a deficit was predicted. This behavior is modeled with a simplified post-strategy, which does not consider the actual coupling between building operation and control. The performance of the heat generators is then evaluated, in accordance with the thermal demand of the building (coming from the original dataset).

B.4.1. Benchmark Control Configurations and Energy Performance Metrics

The proposed control system, referred to as the “Predictive”, is based on AR forecasts of the thermal load and supply temperature. To evaluate its performance, for each dataset, it was compared to three other configurations from an energy and cost saving perspective. The additional control scenarios analyzed are:

- “Baseline”: condensing boiler alone, with weather compensation control.
- “Current”: a typical control logic of commercial HHP, i.e., weather compensation to control supply water temperature and switch between boiler and HP at fixed temperature (i.e., -15°C).
- “Ideal”: optimal predictive control of the HHP, based on the ideal thermal load and supply temperature prediction.

The weather compensation control underlying the first two comparison scenarios is based on a linear correlation between external air and supply water temperatures. This correlation was tailored for each case study by extrapolating it from the supply and external temperature available data. In addition, the “Current” control, given the extremely low switch temperature, can be considered an HP priority mode.

The comparison with the “Current” methodology should be considered particularly significant, as it represents the standard scenario encountered in practical situations that the AR-based control developed in this study seeks to improve. The difference between the benchmarks and the AR-based control is only due to the use of different supervisory-level actions, while the low-level controls are assumed to be the same in all scenarios.

Several indicators were analyzed to evaluate the validity of the proposed control strategy and consequently compare it with the reference control scenarios just introduced. Six indicators were selected.

- Cost savings: it represents the economic percentage savings with respect to the baseline configuration. It reads:

$$C_s = \frac{C_{seasonal,ref} - C_{seasonal,x}}{C_{seasonal,ref}} \cdot 100\% \quad (B.9)$$

- Primary energy savings: analogous to the cost saving index but referred to seasonal non-renewable primary energy consumption.

$$PE_s = \frac{PE_{seasonal,ref} - PE_{seasonal,x}}{PE_{seasonal,ref}} \cdot 100\% \quad (B.10)$$

- GHG emission savings: similar evaluation to the preceding ones, but in terms of $kg_{CO_2,eq}$ savings.

$$GHG_s = \frac{GHG_{seasonal,ref} - GHG_{seasonal,x}}{GHG_{seasonal,ref}} \cdot 100\% \quad (B.11)$$

- HP energy usage: it represents the share of seasonal energy demand satisfied with the heat pump. The remaining share is supplied by the boiler.

$$E_{HP,\%} = \frac{\sum_i Q_{HP}^{(i)}}{\sum_i Q^{(i)}} \cdot 100\% \quad (\text{B.12})$$

- HP Seasonal Coefficient of Performance (SCOP): it represents the seasonal efficiency of the heat pump, calculated considering overall thermal energy output and electric consumption.

$$SCOP_{HP} = \frac{\sum_i Q_{HP}^{(i)}}{\sum_i E_{el}^{(i)}} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

- Boiler average efficiency: it represents the average seasonal efficiency of the condensing boiler.

$$\eta_{boiler,avg} = \frac{\sum_i Q^{(i)} - \sum_i Q_{HP}^{(i)}}{\sum_i E_{gas}^{(i)}} \quad (\text{B.14})$$

Energy vector costs, non-renewable primary energy factors (PEFs), and emission factors employed for calculation are summarized in Table B.2.

Table B.2. Simulation parameters for energy prices, non-renewable primary energy factors, and carbon dioxide emission factors of energy vectors utilized by the hybrid heat pump system.

	Natural gas	Electricity
Energy cost [€/kWh]	0.11 [27]	0.29 [27]
PEF [kWh _p /kWh]	1.05 [28]	1.95 [28]
CO ₂ emission factor [kg _{CO_{2,eq}} /kWh]	0.211 [29]	0.268 [30]

Italian energy, cost, and environmental scenarios highlight the importance of optimized operation in hybrid heat pumps, since choosing the less suitable heat generation unit can significantly reduce overall performance. For example, the threshold COP for cost-effective heat pump operation is around 2.6, whereas actual heat pump performance may often deviate substantially from this value, either positively or negatively, underscoring the need for accurate performance assessment and control strategies.

B.4.2. Results

In the following sections, simulation results from both the simulated and on-field monitored datasets are presented and discussed.

Simulative Dataset Results

Prediction

The AR predictive algorithm is characterized by three indexes: j , n , and m , representing the training, autoregressive, and re-update timesteps, respectively. A sensitivity analysis has been performed for these indexes in order to find the optimal choice. The optimal combination of j , n , and m varies for each specific case study. However, standard values may be used as a good and generalizable trade-off for all case studies: 28 days of training (j), 2 days of autoregression (n), and 7 days before re-updating (m). This combination was found to provide a good balance between prediction accuracy and minimizing the waiting time before the first prediction. Therefore, the results presented in the

text refer only to this standard triplet.

For both thermal load and supply temperature, the predictive ability was evaluated for the standard heating period for each location: from January 1st to April 15th for Parma and Florence, and from January 1st to March 31st for Bari. Results are presented in Table B.3.

Table B.3. Accuracy errors derived from the application of the AR forecasting algorithm to heating load and supply temperature time series in TRNSYS simulated case studies.

	$wMAPE_Q$	$MAPE_T$	MAE_T [K]
Cold 1	4.7%	2.9%	1.1
Cold 1R	12.3%	5.7%	2.4
Cold 2	7.3%	3.6%	1.3
Cold 2R	17.9%	7.8%	2.9
Cold 3	13.7%	9.4%	2.3
Cold 3R	24.7%	14.0%	3.5
Mild 1	7.3%	4.4%	1.8
Mild 1R	13.7%	6.7%	3.0
Mild 2	9.7%	4.5%	1.6
Mild 2R	18.7%	7.7%	2.9
Mild 3	19.3%	13.0%	3.2
Mild 3R	27.0%	16.9%	4.2
Warm 1	8.3%	4.5%	1.8
Warm 1R	20.9%	9.5%	4.1
Warm 2	9.4%	4.3%	1.6
Warm 2R	24.2%	9.7%	3.9
Warm 3	18.5%	11.3%	2.7
Warm 3R	32.2%	16.5%	4.2

The $wMAPE_Q$ errors reveal high accuracy in cold climates with older building typologies (e.g., cases “Cold 1” and “Cold 2”). In contrast, predictive accuracy clearly declines in newer buildings with low-temperature radiant heating systems, particularly in warmer climates (e.g., “Mild 3” and “Warm 3”). As expected, the presence of more variable occupation profiles significantly increases accuracy errors compared to scenarios with regular internal occupation profiles, causing $wMAPE_Q$ errors to at least double.

Concerning the supply temperature prediction, using the specific $MAPE_T$ error evaluation presented in Eq. 4, the errors appear more limited. However, there is a notable variation between well-predicted and worst-case scenarios. In terms of absolute errors, i.e., MAE_T , the variation is minimal, ranging from 1°C to 4°C. Nonetheless, in buildings with low-temperature heating systems, a variation of 4°C is quite substantial, as the supply temperature was generally lower than 30°C. In these cases, proper control may be more adversely affected by non-ideal predictions.

The errors obtained with the AR forecast on heat demand and supply temperature are visually presented in Figure B.6.

Figure B.6. Representation of actual and forecasted heating load (a, c) and supply temperature (b, d) over one week using simulative datasets. The case studies presented include COLD 1 (a, b) and WARM 3R (c, d).

However, in this study, the accuracy assessment is secondary to the evaluation of the energy and economic benefits provided by the AR-based control method, even in cases of non-perfect predictions.

Energy Assessment

Next, the energy, emission, and cost implications of the proposed control methodology were examined. By comparing the AR-based control with an ideal control, the impact of imperfect prediction on HHP seasonal energy consumption was evaluated.

Integral results for the seasonal operation are shown in Table B.4, which summarizes the main indicators resulting by simulations in the different building typologies and climatic contexts. All the energy metrics were calculated for each case study within the time window from January 1st to March 31st, to ensure a comparable period during which the HHP operates in all case studies

Table B.4. Seasonal integral indicators resulted from the application of the different control scenarios for the 18 simulative case studies.

Case study	Control scenario	C_s	PE_s	GHG_s	$E_{HP,\%}$	$SCOP_{HP}$	$\eta_{boiler,avg}$
Cold 1	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	83.8%
	Current	2.2%	48.1%	50.2%	18.5%	2.45	83.8%
	Predictive	19.1%	59.5%	63.0%	44.0%	3.39	89.2%
	Ideal	22.8%	61.8%	65.5%	46.5%	3.43	94.3%
Cold 1R	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	83.6%
	Current	2.1%	47.6%	49.4%	16.1%	2.48	83.6%
	Predictive	17.8%	58.6%	62.1%	42.9%	3.38	87.6%
	Ideal	22.9%	61.9%	65.7%	47.1%	3.41	94.4%
Cold 2	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	87.3%
	Current	1.4%	48.0%	50.0%	17.3%	2.39	87.6%
	Predictive	21.3%	62.0%	66.2%	54.5%	3.64	89.1%
	Ideal	26.1%	64.9%	69.3%	57.5%	3.67	97.1%
Cold 2R	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	86.5%
	Current	1.1%	46.3%	47.1%	7.7%	2.48	86.6%

<i>Case study</i>	<i>Control scenario</i>	<i>Cs</i>	<i>PEs</i>	<i>GHGs</i>	<i>E_{HP,%}</i>	<i>SCOP_{HP}</i>	<i>η_{boiler,avg}</i>
<i>Cold 3</i>	Predictive	20.4%	61.1%	65.1%	51.8%	3.62	88.0%
	Ideal	26.4%	65.0%	69.3%	56.9%	3.65	97.1%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	95.6%
	Current	22.9%	64.8%	70.6%	68.3%	3.67	100.5%
	Predictive	22.0%	62.2%	66.4%	56.9%	4.23	93.6%
<i>Cold 3R</i>	Ideal	30.1%	67.6%	72.5%	68.3%	4.34	100.5%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	95.3%
	Current	23.3%	64.9%	70.7%	68.8%	3.68	100.3%
	Predictive	19.5%	60.0%	63.8%	51.7%	4.25	92.2%
<i>Mild 1</i>	Ideal	30.6%	67.7%	72.6%	68.7%	4.37	100.1%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	79.6%
	Current	2.6%	43.9%	45.0%	11.1%	2.77	79.4%
	Predictive	20.6%	58.8%	63.1%	50.9%	3.27	83.6%
<i>Mild 1R</i>	Ideal	26.0%	62.5%	67.2%	55.7%	3.28	91.9%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	79.2%
	Current	2.1%	43.3%	44.1%	8.2%	2.76	79.3%
	Predictive	20.1%	58.5%	62.7%	50.6%	3.29	82.1%
<i>Mild 2</i>	Ideal	26.5%	62.9%	67.6%	56.2%	3.28	92.1%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	86.6%
	Current	2.9%	45.6%	48.0%	21.5%	2.65	86.3%
	Predictive	23.9%	61.8%	66.9%	64.7%	3.76	83.0%
<i>Mild 2R</i>	Ideal	30.9%	66.2%	71.6%	68.6%	3.81	96.6%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	86.1%
	Current	2.0%	43.0%	43.9%	8.5%	2.96	86.3%
	Predictive	22.8%	60.8%	65.8%	62.2%	3.75	82.5%
<i>Mild 3</i>	Ideal	30.5%	65.9%	71.2%	67.5%	3.79	96.7%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	94.7%
	Current	38.4%	70.9%	77.1%	84.1%	4.52	100.4%
	Predictive	30.2%	63.6%	68.1%	66.2%	4.92	88.8%
<i>Mild 3R</i>	Ideal	44.0%	73.2%	78.8%	84.1%	5.13	100.4%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	94.7%
	Current	37.8%	71.0%	77.7%	86.4%	4.39	100.1%
	Predictive	24.0%	58.7%	62.5%	54.0%	4.86	90.6%
<i>Warm 1</i>	Ideal	43.9%	73.6%	79.4%	86.3%	5.01	100.0%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	79.2%
	Current	7.9%	49.3%	53.4%	38.1%	2.58	79.2%
	Predictive	25.6%	61.8%	67.3%	68.2%	3.53	73.1%
<i>Warm 1R</i>	Ideal	35.0%	68.2%	74.2%	75.5%	3.56	91.4%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	77.7%
	Current	3.8%	43.1%	44.4%	12.5%	2.66	78.1%
	Predictive	23.6%	59.9%	64.8%	62.1%	3.52	72.6%
<i>Warm 2</i>	Ideal	35.0%	67.3%	72.5%	68.5%	3.63	92.1%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	85.9%
	Current	4.2%	46.2%	49.0%	25.2%	2.69	85.7%
	Predictive	26.1%	62.6%	67.8%	67.8%	3.91	79.6%
<i>Warm 2R</i>	Ideal	34.3%	68.2%	73.9%	74.6%	3.91	95.8%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	85.2%
	Current	2.6%	42.8%	43.8%	10.4%	2.93	85.2%
	Predictive	23.8%	60.6%	65.5%	63.1%	3.86	79.3%
<i>Warm 2R</i>	Ideal	33.5%	67.3%	72.8%	71.5%	3.89	95.8%
	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	95.8%
	Current	2.6%	42.8%	43.8%	10.4%	2.93	85.2%
	Predictive	23.8%	60.6%	65.5%	63.1%	3.86	79.3%

<i>Case study</i>	<i>Control scenario</i>	<i>Cs</i>	<i>PEs</i>	<i>GHGs</i>	<i>E_{HHP},%</i>	<i>SCOP_{HHP}</i>	<i>η_{boiler,avg}</i>
<i>Warm 3</i>	Current	45.6%	75.7%	82.0%	92.4%	4.94	100.6%
	Predictive	37.4%	68.6%	73.1%	74.3%	5.49	86.8%
	Ideal	51.5%	78.2%	83.7%	92.4%	5.65	100.6%
<i>Warm 3R</i>	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00	95.9%
	Current	43.6%	74.5%	80.9%	91.2%	4.81	100.6%
	Predictive	29.5%	62.3%	65.9%	58.7%	5.48	91.3%
	Ideal	50.2%	77.3%	82.9%	91.2%	5.58	100.4%

From the analysis, HHP systems generally emerge as a convenient alternative to condensing boilers alone in terms of operative costs, primary energy use, and equivalent CO₂ emissions. However, under the Italian price scenario, the “current control” results in only minimal savings in case studies where radiators are used as heating units. Conversely, in these situations, the optimal potential of the HHP – which would lead to 22% – 35% seasonal cost savings – is nearly achieved with the AR predictive control, which allows cost savings in the range of 18% – 26% with respect to the baseline case. Different results are observed in 2000s buildings, where the current control of the HHP already achieves significant cost savings of up to 46%, which is very close to the ideal savings potential of up to 52%. For these low-temperature heating case studies, AR predictive control of the HHP is generally less convenient than the currently implemented strategy, due to prediction errors.

When comparing the AR-based control expenses with the ideal scenario, the percentage increase in operational costs generally ranges from 5% to 15% for high-temperature case studies. However, for low-temperature case studies, the gap between our control and the ideal scenario increases significantly.

Climate also appears to have an impact on potential savings. With the predictive controls, the seasonal cost savings increase from colder to warmer climates. Randomization of internal occupancy profiles also has an effect, leading to a slight reduction in the economic savings achievable with the AR control. Nevertheless, these discrepancies are considerably more reduced than those observed in terms of forecasting accuracy. This implies that there is no strict correlation between prediction accuracy and actual energy savings.

One of the key factors that appears to significantly influence cost savings is the share of thermal demand met by the heat pump. In high-temperature heating scenarios, the current control setup rarely permits the use of the HP. Despite the controller prioritizing the HP, the elevated supply temperatures resulting from weather compensation control often push the HP beyond its operating limits, preventing its utilization. Under ideal conditions, HP usage would be considerably higher, and AR predictive control generally approaches this maximum potential. Conversely, in the case of radiant heating systems, there is an ample opportunity for extensive HP usage even with the current control strategy. In contrast, AR predictive control results in an increase in boiler usage due to relevant forecasting errors, with a consequential increase in operational costs.

Seasonal COP also varies with different controls: ideally, the SCOP of the HHP would be very high (3.3 – 5.6), and the AR predictive control closely approaches it. The current control does not optimize the performance of the HHP and thus generally results in a lower SCOP for the HP. This remains true also in newer buildings. Concerning the boiler, while its average efficiency may vary, values generally remain very high in all control scenarios.

Alongside the cost savings, replacing a condensing boiler alone with an HHP also results in notable savings in terms of primary energy consumption and associated CO₂ emissions. Non-renewable primary energy benefits are also substantial, greater than 43%, when HHP is used with the current control strategy. With the AR predictive control strategy, even though the optimization is only based on cost optimization, primary energy savings exceed 58%. Similar, but larger, percentage benefits are achieved in terms of emissions as well.

Field-Monitored Dataset Results

Prediction

The same AR algorithm is also applied to the real-world dataset to test and validate the model with more realistic conditions. Accuracy errors evaluated in the period January 1st – March 31st are reported in Table B.5.

Table B.5. Accuracy errors derived from the application of the AR forecasting algorithm to heating load and supply temperature time series in on-field monitored simulated case studies.

	$wMAPE_Q$	$MAPE_T$	MAE_T [K]
Exp 1	30.9%	15.3%	4.6
Exp 2	31.1%	16.7%	4.1
Exp 3	20.3%	9.3%	2.1

The application of the prediction algorithm to such dataset results in low accuracies, especially for the heating load prediction, due to the higher variability of the hourly profiles. However, the errors are generally within or close to the maximum values obtained from the simulations.

Energy Assessment

Concerning the comprehensive implementation of the control, Table B.6 summarizes the results obtained with a real-world dataset, providing integral indicators derived from the seasonal operation.

Table B.6. Seasonal integral indicators resulted from the application of the different control scenarios for the 3 on-field monitored case studies.

Case study	Control scenario	C_s	PE_s	GHG_s	$E_{HP,\%}$	$SCOP_{HP}$	$\eta_{boiler,avg}$
Exp 1	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0	92.3%
	Current	0.4%	24.9%	25.2%	2.0%	3.0	92.8%
	Predictive	6.7%	33.7%	36.9%	26.1%	3.3	92.5%
	Ideal	8.9%	34.9%	37.8%	22.8%	3.2	97.0%
Exp 2	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0	95.5%
	Current	0.0%	33.0%	33.5%	2.7%	2.4	95.6%
	Predictive	6.1%	39.2%	41.2%	18.7%	3.5	96.2%
	Ideal	7.5%	40.0%	41.8%	17.0%	3.5	98.7%
Exp 3	Baseline	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0	95.6%
	Current	0.6%	29.1%	30.2%	7.3%	2.7	96.4%
	Predictive	3.7%	31.8%	33.2%	12.0%	3.4	96.8%
	Ideal	4.8%	32.4%	33.8%	11.2%	3.4	98.2%

The AR predictive control method achieves savings of approximately 4–7%, which is very close to the 5–9% savings that could be obtained with an ideal control system. A direct comparison between the AR control and the ideal scenario shows indeed an increase in operational expenses of less than 3%. In contrast, the use of an HHP with traditional weather compensation control does not result in

meaningful economic savings even with respect to the boiler alone, due to the very limited possibility of HP use. However, from a primary energy and environmental perspective, HHP offers more benefits than the baseline case across all the control strategies analyzed.

While SCOP values are still high, the share of heating demand satisfaction with the HP is low, especially if the HHP is used with traditional control. No significant differences appear in the average values of boiler efficiency.

B.5. Discussion and Comparison

The results of the AR forecasting algorithm show great variability depending on the specific case study analyzed. In older building contexts, such as 1980s and 1990s houses, average hourly prediction errors are generally low, though accuracy declined from colder to warmer climates. The randomization of occupancy has a significant effect, nearly doubling the errors compared to a regular occupancy schedule. Higher forecasting errors are observed in more recent houses, i.e., 2000s villas. In these cases, the increased relative weight of loads due to quasi-random phenomena – such as solar radiation and internal loads – causes greater hourly variation in heating demand and worsens the AR predictive ability.

AR prediction errors inevitably affect the application of the control, leading to deviations from optimal behavior. Hourly errors in heating load forecasting may result in suboptimal decisions regarding generators activation and the supply temperature set-point. Additionally, such errors may lead to the activation of the boiler to compensate for a deficit in the hourly forecast. This is identified as the main cause of increased costs and primary energy consumption with the non-ideal AR-based predictive controller.

Cost savings results presented in Table B.4 and Table B.6 are summarized in the bar chart shown in Figure B.7, illustrating the economic savings compared to using the boiler alone. For the simulation datasets, only randomized configurations are shown, as they are considered more representative.

Figure B.7. Bar chart comparing the percentage cost savings (Cs) relative to the use of a condensation boiler alone. Results are presented for simulated case studies with randomized occupancy profiles as well as for on-field monitored case studies.

While the comparison to the boiler-only case is significant for evaluating the benefits of implementing the HHP, the comparison to a typical control strategy (the current control) is crucial for assessing the savings potential of our forecast-based control strategy. For each case study analyzed, both simulated and field-monitored, Figure B.8 summarizes the obtained cost savings respect to the current control logic.

Figure B.8: Spider plots illustrating seasonal costs for the 'Current', 'Predictive', and 'Ideal' HHP control scenarios in each case study, normalized to the seasonal energy cost of the 'Current' control scenario. Results are shown for both simulated (a) and monitored (b) datasets.

As previously noted, AR-based predictive control is generally beneficial. In the 1980s and 1990s simulated case studies, as well as in the three real-world scenarios, AR control not only ensures savings comparable to the ideal ones but is also significantly more cost-effective than the current control. Savings are around 20% in the 1980s and 1990s simulations, and around 7% with the real-world data. However, in the simulated case studies of 2000s detached houses equipped with high insulation and a low-temperature heating system, the current control already achieves near-optimal results due to the heat pump's ability to cover a significant portion of the seasonal energy needs, facilitated by the low supply temperature. In these cases, the AR-based control hinders overall performance because prediction errors led to extensive use of the gas boiler, causing a general increase in operational costs by up to 25%. The effect of climate variation is not significant, and the variation in savings due to randomized internal occupancy schedules are practically negligible. This indicates that, up to a certain level, the control is robust to variations in AR forecasting capabilities: despite significant degradation in the ability to predict load and temperature from regular to random profiles and from colder to warmer climates, there is no corresponding degradation in potential energy and cost savings.

On the other hand, the differences between the results obtained from the simulated and field-monitored datasets are more pronounced. The field-monitored data show a general decline in energy savings. Specifically, the HP's energy share is significantly lower compared to the simulated case studies, primarily due to higher thermal power peaks and the use of elevated supply temperatures by the system. This also leads to lower COPs.

The real-world monitored dataset should be considered more representative of the expectable behavior in the practical application of AR-based predictive control on an HHP system. In fact, the

variables constituting that dataset, which are recorded on board the heating unit, would indeed be those available in practice to be used as input for AR training and forecasting, as well as for system modeling. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the data monitored in this case was collected from the operation of gas-fired boilers, not HHPs. If data were recorded from an HHP, different parameters of operation would have been obtained. Therefore, to better evaluate the practical potentialities of this control, dedicated experimental campaigns should be conducted to test the procedure on HHPs.

B.6. Conclusions and Main Limitations

In the present appendix a data-driven model-based control strategy for hybrid heat pumps was developed and applied to heating operation in several residential scenarios. The proposed procedure is based on the autoregressive prediction of the hourly building heat demand and corresponding water temperature to be supplied to the heat emitters. Given that, the next-hour energy performances of the two heat generation units are estimated to choose which one is more convenient to activate, considering an alternative operating mode. The AR forecast method was proposed as it was found to be a valuable trade-off between computational effort, required input data, and expected results.

The data-driven model-based control strategy was dynamically simulated into several reference buildings, representative of the Italian residential scenario. Seasonal implementation of the control strategy demonstrated significant savings when compared to traditional control methods and approached the performance of the ideal forecast-based controls. In non-renovated buildings, the AR-based predictive control achieved 15–20% reductions in both costs and $CO_{2,eq}$ emissions compared to standard controls, primarily by increasing and improving heat pump utilization through better supply temperature regulation. Importantly, the results closely aligned with those achievable using an ideal predictive control, underscoring the efficacy of the AR-based method. The application to the high-efficiency villas with low-temperature emitters revealed narrower performance gaps between standard and advanced controls. Therefore, forecast-based control appears to be not so important for this particular type of building.

Application of the control strategy to a small field-monitored dataset revealed a limited savings potential for AR control, due to generally higher water supply temperatures compared to simulations, which reduced the operational potential of the HP. Even so, the AR control performance deviated by less than 3% in cost compared to ideal control, confirming its robustness and adaptability.

This research highlights the potential for meaningful energy, environmental, and economic benefits through improved HHP control strategies. The proposed AR-based control method provides a practical and highly efficient solution, offering near-ideal performance with minimal computational demands. The ability to easily self-learn from operational data makes it broadly applicable across multiple building types, without the need for advanced hardware resources. Its simple calculations can be efficiently processed by the standard on-board processors included in HHPs.

However, a number of limitations emerged from this preliminary work, which directly motivated the developments pursued in the thesis work.

The analysis used few case studies, too narrow to cover the variability of climates, buildings, and occupancy. Radiant floors were modeled in oversimplified form, ignoring thermal capacity and dynamic effects. Predictive control was only tested with a simplified post-strategy, without closed-

loop interaction with the rest of the building and the heating system.

The study showed that forecast-based supervisory control can achieve near-ideal benefits at low computational cost and modeling effort, while revealing specific challenges with radiant floors. As these efficient systems are likely to grow in use, this thesis builds on that foundation to advance their modeling and control.

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Appendix C

Assessment of Experimental, Analytical, and Numerical Methods for Predicting Surface Temperature Distribution in Radiant Floor Applications

This appendix summarizes a published study entitled “*Evaluation by Liquid Crystal Thermography of Transient Surface Temperature Distribution in Radiant Floor Cooling Applications and Assessment of Analytical and Numerical Models*”. The work focused on the superficial temperature distribution of radiant floor systems, with a special focus for cooling operation.

C.1. Introduction

Conventional modeling approaches for radiant floor systems often assume a uniform floor surface temperature, typically by representing the entire surface with a single node. However, to verify the actual validity of this assumption in real applications, a thorough study of the topic was deemed necessary. Several studies have already employed experimental assessments to characterize radiant heating/cooling applications. Some were mainly interested in analyzing the comfort conditions in a space conditioned by radiant panels [19 – 21], but without studying the surface temperature distribution on the radiative emitter. Typically, the surface temperature was specifically analyzed in studies in which unconventional radiant systems are described [22 – 25], along with the characterization of the heat transfer phenomena involved. In [23 – 25], the authors also presented and discussed the temperature distribution on the panel surface; they reported relevant spatial temperature non-uniformities, in some cases higher than 4°C, but employing ceilings or lightweight floors that do not present a significant massive layer over the pipes as in classical radiant floor applications. Furthermore, the temperature uniformity on a radiant ceiling was analyzed as it has been proposed as a new method to improve cooling capacity without causing condensation [26 – 27]. However, no tailored experimental analysis has been conducted to assess the surface temperature distribution in typical radiant floor applications. In addition, liquid crystal thermography has never been applied to the study of a radiant heating/cooling terminal.

To fill this gap, the present study describes and discusses the results of an experimental campaign conducted in two test rooms, representative of typical residential applications, equipped with radiant floor systems in cooling operation. Therefore, the primary objective is to experimentally evaluate the temperature non-uniformity caused by the discontinuous presence of pipes within the screed and thermal interactions with the upper space. The temperature profile on the surface is mapped by means of the Liquid Crystal Thermography (LCT), a tool which allows both qualitative and quantitative evaluations of the temperature on a restricted area [28 – 30]. Specifically, in our analysis we adopted a modeling-oriented approach and aimed to determine whether, at least under the conditions investigated in our test cases, the assumption of a uniform surface temperature in RFCS modeling methods is a justifiable choice. We examined both steady-state and unsteady conditions and evaluated the deviations that would result from using a single-node approach for the floor surface temperature instead of its entire distribution.

Furthermore, we conducted a more thorough investigation using the experimental results to assess the suitability of straightforward analytical and numerical methods for evaluating the surface temperature distribution. These methods provide an assessment of the distribution under highly ideal and simple system boundary conditions. The purpose of this analysis was thus to assess the robustness of these modeling approaches and their potential for practical use in estimating floor surface temperature non-uniformity in real-world applications where the boundary and initial conditions are highly non-ideal. Moreover, the models played a crucial role in our research as tools to better comprehend the phenomena observed in our experiments.

The most practical contribution of this study lies in providing valuable insights for the development of advanced control strategies for condensation prevention in radiant floor cooling applications. If a single node is employed to represent the surface temperature of the radiant floor in the model, the application of a corrective coefficient should be used to evaluate the actual minimum temperature present on the surface. Such a correction may come from the findings of our study.

The present appendix is organized in 3 other sections besides this initial introduction. Section 2 describes the experiment methodology, providing details on the experimental apparatus and numerical models used for further assessments. Section 3 presents and discusses the results of the experimental campaign and the comparison with the models for the evaluation of the temperature distribution. Finally, final remarks and future directions are presented in the Conclusion section.

C.2. Methods and Models

As mentioned earlier, the present research follows a modeling-oriented research approach by questioning the validity and robustness of selecting a single lumped node for the floor surface, thus assuming a uniform temperature. The outcomes of the experiment are compared with the results of Glück's analytical model [17, 18] for the temperature distribution on the floor surface in steady-state conditions. Moreover, a numerical model is used as a benchmark to describe the transient behavior of the floor system.

C.2.1. Methodology of the Experimental Analysis

Test rooms

The experimental campaign was conducted from August 28, 2023, to September 1, 2023, in two adjacent test rooms with different radiant floor geometries. The purpose of the experiment was to test and monitor an RFCS integrated into a building structure. The overall area of each room was 25 m^2 . The radiant floor in Room 1 contained 3 separate coils connected to the same distribution manifold, each measuring approximately 82 m in length, with a pipe spacing of 10 cm and an immersion depth in the screed of 5 cm . The same immersion depth was present in the second room, Room 2, but there the pipe spacing was larger (25 cm) and there were only 2 coils, with a length of 54 m each. The pipes have an identical structure, in PEX polyethylene, with an external diameter of 1.7 cm . In both rooms, a 0.5 cm thick ceramic tile coating was placed over the screed.

While the floor has a structure common to many practical applications, the walls of the rooms are not a typical example of the actual construction techniques used for buildings. They consist of two drywall panels separated by 10 cm of stone wool for thermal insulation. The ceiling is a multi-layer structure composed of a metal layer, an insulating layer, and typical floor assembly for the space above. The transmission gains of the two test rooms were controlled by varying the temperature of the adjacent rooms, with the exception of two walls that were in contact with an internal cavaedium and a service room, respectively. The overall transmission heat transfer coefficient for each room was estimated as 90 W/K . We could also directly influence the indoor air temperature with the activation of internal gains, such as electrical heaters.

The RFCS are fed by a commercial chiller. We had the opportunity of changing the supply water set-point to reproduce and monitoring typical steady-state and transient operating conditions. This was the primary method we employed to produce differing experimental conditions within the rooms. By lowering the supply temperature, we could also cause the onset of condensation on the floor surface.

Instrumentation

To comprehensively monitor the performance of a radiant floor, the two test rooms were equipped with multiple measurement sensors. One of the rooms, called "Room 1", was fully instrumented: all

wall, ceiling and floor temperatures were recorded, along with the indoor air temperature. The monitoring of relative humidity and global operating temperature was also carried out through a thermal microclimate station located in the room (see Figure C.1-a). The data on the piping systems and heat pump supplying the room were also recorded. Finally, we employed liquid crystal thermography to assess the two-dimensional temperature distribution on the floor tiles. Several crystal foils of the dimensions of 30 x 30 cm were thus placed in different positions on the room floor. The second room – “Room 2” – was instead only equipped with air temperature sensors and liquid crystals sheets. The characteristics of the instrumentation are presented in Table C.1.

Table C.1. Measuring instruments (placed on the floor, air, walls, and ceiling) utilized in the experimental campaign.

Name	Model	Measured variable/s	Number
NTC thermistor	GA10K3A1A	Surface temperatures	19
ZigBee sensor for temperature, humidity and light	4-noks ZED-THL-M	Air temperature, relative humidity, illuminance	3
Thermochromic liquid crystal foil	Bolmax R20C5W	Floor temperature distribution	9
Thermal microclimate station	DELTAOHM HD32.3 (globe thermometer TP3275, combined temperature and relative humidity probe HP3217R, omnidirectional hot wire AP3203)	WBGT, PMV, PPD, operative temperature, air temperature, relative humidity, radiant temperature, air speed	1

Figure C.1 shows the placement of the floor-mounted sensors in the two rooms, together with a picture of the equipped room.

Figure C.1. Photograph of the real, fully instrumented test room 1 (a) and schematic representation of the temperature sensors placed on the floor surface (b).

For NTC sensors, it is advisable to place them and their shielded wiring along isothermal lines to avoid introducing thermal sink behavior, which can impact measurements. But in our experiment,

the exact position of isothermal lines was unknown due to uncertainty about the pipe positions within the floor. However, preliminary infrared thermal camera measurements indicated minimal non-uniformity on the floor. Confirmation will come when discussing TLC results. Given the locally small temperature differences on the floor surface, it can be considered substantially isothermal, thus minimizing the impact of any errors from wire positioning on the measurements.

Liquid Crystal Thermography

The thermochromic liquid crystal (TLC) sheets have been employed to generate a continuous map of the surface temperature. The position of the 9 TLCs is shown in Figure C.1: 5 are placed in Room 1 and 4 in Room 2. To ensure effective adhesion to the floor, we positioned the adhesive layer beneath them directly over the floor tiles, with dimensions perfectly matching. The crystal foils were carefully laid out to avoid the formation of air bubbles, but after the set-up, the adhesion began to fail and some of the crystals showed macro imperfections that prevented some of them from being useable for the analysis. Therefore, in the end, only a single crystal foil could be analyzed in Room 1, while 3 were still usable in Room 2, as shown in Figure C.1-b.

To collect the measurement of the TLC, a photo camera or a video camera must be used to capture the image of the crystal foil. In our study, we employed a Nikon D80 digital camera as the acquisition device. Since the TLC foils are glued to the floor, the camera had to be moved around the two rooms, so we decided to build a support system that would allow the camera to be positioned correctly each time. Additionally, a 5 W white led light has been attached to the support system as illumination source for the crystal foil. Both the camera and the light were tiled to avoid reflections. Finally, as suggested by [31], the entire structure was covered with a wooden shield to prevent light interference from secondary sources such as reflections from other environments. This was especially important when calibrating, which was done in a confined space: a small climatic chamber. The acquisition system is visualized in Figure C.2.

Figure C.2. Photographs of the acquisition device for the TLC sheet. In a moment of transition (a) and during an actual acquisition (b).

Thermochromic liquid crystals possess the valuable characteristic of changing their internal structure in response to temperature variations, which then leads to a modified reflection of the incident radiation and consequent change in color appearance. The characterization of color variation is typically accomplished in terms of hue, a variable capable of distinctly representing a color in the entire color spectrum. This reading is converted to a temperature value after a calibration process in which the hue-T curve is determined. The crystal itself then becomes an actual temperature sensor. By employing an entire liquid crystal foil, the hue can be determined over a large area corresponding to the area of the foil allowing, after the conversion, a 2D temperature evaluation. However, to ensure accurate temperature measurement at each location, the TLC foil must be calibrated to account for variations in illumination, reflections, and other factors. Therefore, calibration should ideally be performed on a point-by-point basis.

Importantly, TLCs have a limited temperature range in which they can correctly operate. This corresponds to their color play, which in our case ranges from red to blue, passing through green. For our study, we used foils that were declared by the manufacturer to be usable in the range of $20 \sim 25^{\circ}\text{C}$, but in fact the calibration phase showed that it could be extended to cover a few degrees higher temperatures.

The choice of employing LCT to study the temperature distribution on a radiant heating/cooling panel finds no previous appearances in the scientific literature. On the other hand, Infrared Thermography (IRT) is usually the tool employed for experiments of this kind [23, 24]. IR thermography is certainly more versatile and easier to utilize in many applications, but it has some limitations that made us prefer the TLC technique. In fact, the IRT is generally not considered reliable for making accurate absolute measurements [32]; instead, it is usually used to provide relative, or even just qualitative, assessments [33]. In our case, we decided that an absolute measurement was important because of the presence of condensation issues in the radiant floor cooling process. However, besides that, the difficulty in correctly estimating the surface emissivity of the floor tiles is the main reason why IR thermography was found not completely reliable for our purposes. The emissivity evaluation was found problematic especially because, being in an enclosed space, we would have faced problems due to the significant influence of IR radiation emitted from other internal surfaces and reflected from the floor. This issue could be avoided with a proper *in-situ* calibration, but in our scenario, it would have been too challenging. Therefore, in order to achieve higher accuracy in both relative and absolute measurements, we decided to use liquid crystal thermography. However, this required a refined calibration procedure.

Calibration

As presented in Table C.1, several instruments have been used for our experimental campaign. A fundamental step needed to obtain reliable measures is their calibration.

For the thermal microclimate station, we did not perform any further calibration. We trusted the manufacturer's proven reliability and therefore accepted the instrument's outputs as an adequate representation of the variables we wished to measure. Similar considerations could have been made for the ZigBee combined sensors. However, having access to their calibration data from a preceding study [34], we adopted those calibration curves.

On the other hand, for the NTC sensors and the liquid crystal foils, there was no accurate data on the correlation between the sensed variable – resistance for NTCs and color hue for TLCs – and the

measured temperature. Hence, we had to extract the actual calibration curve in both cases.

Firstly, NTC thermistors were calibrated using a stirred thermostatic bath of FC-72 in which the temperature was varied from 15 to 40 °C, with a 1°C variation. The calibrating instrument's built-in sensor was used to maintain the bath set-point temperature, but the R-T curve was generated using readings from a PT100 reference thermometer immersed with the thermistors. Each of the 19 NTCs was considered with its actual calibration curve in further analysis.

The calibration of the TLCs demanded more effort. One liquid crystal sheet, considered representative of the other 9 used in the test rooms, was placed in a climate chamber where the temperature was first lowered to 18°C and then continuously increased up to 29°C. Photographs of the foil were taken at intervals of 0.5°C, following the reading of the chamber sensor. To determine the curve, however, the temperature measurements were taken from 5 NTC sensors, selected among the 19 previously calibrated, spaced symmetrically under the film.

Each acquired photo of the TLC sheet required a geometric transformation to create a processable image corresponding to the 30 cm x 30 cm area of the sheet. This was done using the MATLAB “fitgeotrans” function, which allowed the trapezoidal shape representing the TLC in the original image – due to perspective distortions – to be replaced by a square with the actual proportions of the sheet. Once all the photos and temperatures were recorded, the data was processed. First, for each measurement event, a temperature map of the crystal was reconstructed from the 5 NTC readings. At each (x, y) point, the temperature was evaluated with a weighted average of the 5 values, using the inverse of the distance between the (x, y) spot and each sensor as the weight. Then, the image was processed, and the colors of each pixel were determined. The colors were characterized by an RGB triplet, from which the hue value was extracted using the MATLAB function “rgb2hsv”, which implements the equations presented in [35]. The hue value was subsequently filtered using a two-dimensional moving average with a window of 10 x 10 pixels. Then, the hue-T curve for each point was computed.

The calibration procedure is summarized in Figure C.3. As presented for a generic (x, y) pixel, the hue-T curve has a linear behavior in the range of low temperatures and low hues, while the remaining points are well fitted with a 3rd order polynomial. This function is then used when processing the images taken during the experiment to evaluate the temperature field over the entire TLC sheet.

Figure C.3. Schematic representation of the calibration procedure. The temperature field is determined by 5 NTC readings, which are then interpolated (a); the hue field is obtained from the photograph, after geometric reshaping and RGB-to-hue conversion (b). The hue-T curve is then generated for each pixel by fitting the values of each calibration point (c).

Uncertainty Analysis

In the framework of this research, it is important to provide an estimate of the measurement inaccuracies that can occur when evaluating temperatures. While the primary focus has been on LCT measurement reliability, an evaluation of NTC sensors was also necessary.

Thus, we assessed measurement uncertainties in our experimental tests. Figure C.4 presents the methodology that was followed, along with the main results obtained at each stage, in terms of expanded uncertainty.

Figure C.4. Uncertainty map showing the numerous contributions that cause an error in the temperature reading from NTCs (a) and TLC sheets (b).

All reported errors are expressed in terms of expanded uncertainty, obtained with a 95% confidence interval, as typical in experimental investigations. Starting from the analysis of NTC, the first contribution to consider is the uncertainty in the voltage measurement, acquired with Labjack 7Pro. Two independent contributions were calculated and combined as the square root of the sum of the squared uncertainties, as suggested by the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement [36]. Type A uncertainty, the statistical component, was assessed by analyzing the distribution of the recorded readings for each measurement. Type B uncertainty, arising from the finite resolution of the Labjack reading, was assessed by considering a uniform distribution over the range provided by the manufacturer. The uncertainty in voltage was then converted to resistance error by considering the propagation of uncertainty from the input to the measurand. Given the circuitual scheme, the partial derivative $\frac{\partial R}{\partial V}$ could be easily calculated and the uncertainty on the NTC resistance computed as: $u(R) = \frac{\partial R}{\partial V} u(V)$. Finally, the uncertainty in resistance had to be propagated to provide an indication of the potential temperature error in temperature measurements. For each point evaluated during the calibration, we considered the temperature indication to be exact, since it came from a primary reference standard RTD. However, uncertainty arises when considering points in between the ones effectively measured, requiring an evaluation of the interpolation uncertainty. To derive the R-T curve for each NTC, we interpolated the measured points with cubic spline segments, making analytical evaluation of such uncertainty not straightforward. Therefore, the bootstrap method was used: we selected new points on the curve, as many as the calibration points, and used them to generate a new spline interpolation, yielding a new curve. By repeating the same process several times, a series of curves were created. To account for resistance uncertainty, previously evaluated, we repeated the same procedure while randomly altering the calibrating points R_i, T_i within the range $[R_i - u_R, R_i + u_R]$. Using the set of curves obtained, we could then estimate the

error, considering the distribution at every point. In the end, the uncertainty for the evaluation of temperature by the NTC was obtained: $u(T_{NTC}) = 0.04^{\circ}C$.

Regarding liquid crystal thermography, evaluating uncertainty was quite complex due to the number of unconventional steps involved in obtaining a temperature measurement. The measurement chain is quite long. Starting with the initial RGB value, which is the first information obtained from the processed image after proper cropping and transformation, Type B uncertainty originating from the 8-bit color sensor's resolution was quantified, and it was subsequently applied to the hue measurement. For this stage, we utilized the Monte Carlo methodology due to the analytical complexity of the relationship between the hue and RGB values. The Monte Carlo approach yielded a triangular distribution for the hue value, starting from the uniform distribution over the 2^8 resolution intervals of R, G, and $B \in [0, 1]$ values. The uncertainty for the hue could thus be calculated from the distribution. This is just one of the four independent contributions deemed relevant to the overall LCT temperature uncertainty, as shown in Figure C.4. The remaining contributions are: the previously determined NTC error, the fitting error resulting from the use of a piecewise function to fit the calibration points shown in Figure C.3 (c), and the spatial interpolation error. The latter contribution is due to the reconstruction of the temperature field only from 5 NTC readings. It was determined using the bootstrap method, which is analogous to that performed for NTCs, but in this case the random sampling was applied to a two-dimensional domain. After combining all the contributions, the analysis revealed that the error that could be made in the temperature measurements strongly depends on the part of the hue-T curve to which the measurement belongs: in the linear range ($T \leq 20.5^{\circ}C$) the accuracy is in the order of hundredths of a degree, while for higher temperatures the maximum uncertainty significantly worsens. Accordingly, the expanded uncertainty of the TLC measurement, with a 95% coverage factor, is:

$$u(T_{LCT}) = \begin{cases} 0.05^{\circ}C & \text{for } T \leq 20.5^{\circ}C \\ 1.29^{\circ}C & \text{for } T > 20.5^{\circ}C \end{cases}$$

These findings suggest that temperature measurements can be considered fairly accurate when carried out with NTCs or also with liquid crystal foils, but only in the color range where their response is linear. However, beyond this range, readings may not be reliable, but could still be used for qualitative evaluations after appropriate filtering.

In addition, due to the limited resolution of the camera, the acquisition of the TLC photos will also be affected by spatial noise. In fact, we conservatively estimate that the spatial resolution is 0.15 mm/pixel , which means that the measured temperature will not be punctual, but representative of an area with maximum dimensions of $0.15 \text{ mm} \times 0.15 \text{ mm}$.

Instrumentation-Induced Biases

Following the uncertainty analysis of the measurements, it is crucial also to evaluate the impact of the measuring system on the measurement itself. This evaluation is particularly significant in the case of TLC measurements, as the measurement system is considerably invasive.

Firstly, we consider the effects of the presence of the TLC sheet in terms of additional conductive thermal resistance between the floor and the room above. According to the sheet thickness ($175 \mu\text{m}$) and thermal conductivity (0.16 W/m/K), additional resistance was found to be less than 2% of the conductive resistance of the floor. Such a difference in resistance would result in temperature errors

on the order of 0.01°C , assuming typical heat exchange rates between air and floor. It is thus negligible.

Another important factor to consider is the presence of camera standing hardware, which includes a shielding box to prevent radiation noise and an LED light to be activated for photo acquisition. Such a device potentially affects the measurement, as the shielding would act as an enclosure, changing convective and radiative exchanges of the floor with the surroundings, and the LED would potentially heat up the TLC surface. To minimize interferences, the support was positioned over the TLC for the shortest possible time, and the LED was activated only for photo acquisition. However, we analyzed the effects of these perturbations in tailored tests. Four NTC sensors were placed on the floor surface, positioned at the corners of a $15\text{ cm} \times 15\text{ cm}$ square centered within the TLC sheet area. The temporal temperature variation was recorded with a 1 s sampling time. Figure 5 presents the response of the floor temperature to two types of disturbances. In (a), only the effect of activating the LED light is presented, while in (b), the effect of both activating the LED light and placing the support is shown. In both tests, the box was kept above the TLC sheet and the LED was kept activated after the 10 s time window to better show the deviation between short-term and long-term alterations.

Figure C.5: Effect of the TLC measurement system on the TLC measurement itself, recorded over time with 4 NTC sensors. In (a) only the effect of the LED light activation is considered; in (b) the effects of both the camera support placement and the LED activation are shown.

Based on the results presented in Figure 5, it appears that the LED does not cause a significant variation in temperature in the few seconds following its activation. Specifically, it causes a 0.01°C bias along the 10-second window in which the photo would be taken. On the other hand, the placement of the box causes a more significant variation, with an effect appearing immediately after its positioning. However, by turning on the LED light immediately after placing the support and taking the picture within a 10 s time window, the observed variations in the TLC temperature are limited to approximately 0.1°C . As shown in Figure 5, longer time would be required to introduce a significant alteration of the floor temperature, but in our real experiment, the box is promptly removed after the photo. Additionally, this research primarily focuses on the temperature spatial distribution on the floor surface and Figure 5 shows a similar small alteration for all the four NTCs, which does not alter the temperature difference among the points, ensuring the overall appropriateness of our measuring system and procedure.

C.2.2. Analytical Model for Steady-State Analysis

The heat transfer phenomena occurring on the floor surface might be enclosed in the category of the conjugate heat transfer studies. In fact, in this situation all three heat transfer mechanisms occur between the environment and the pipes. The multidimensional conduction within the slab creates a non-uniform temperature distribution, which then appears also on the surface. In the analytical study described by Glück [17] and subsequently covered by Koschenz and Lehmann [18], the steady-state equation for the conduction within the floor (Figure C.6):

$$\frac{\partial^2 T(x, y)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T(x, y)}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (\text{C.1})$$

is solved with the following boundary conditions:

$$-\lambda \frac{\partial T(x, 0)}{\partial y} = h_1(T(x, 0) - T_1) \quad \text{in } y = 0 \quad (\text{C.2})$$

$$-\lambda \frac{\partial T(x, z_1+z_2)}{\partial y} = h_2(T(x, z_1+z_2) - T_2) \quad \text{in } y = z_1+z_2 \quad (\text{C.3})$$

$$\frac{\partial T(\pm l/2, y)}{\partial x} = 0 \quad \text{in } x = \pm l/2 \quad (\text{C.4})$$

$$T(x, y) = T_{pipe} \quad \text{at the pipe edge} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

With these conditions, the solution for a generic point of the floor follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T(x, y) = T_1 + \frac{\frac{1}{h_1} + \frac{y}{\lambda}}{\frac{1}{U_1} + \frac{1}{U_2}} (T_2 - T_1) + \Gamma \left(T_{pipe} - T_1 + \frac{U_2}{U_1 + U_2} (T_2 - T_1) \right) \\ \left[\frac{\pi}{l} \left(\frac{U_1 - U_2}{U_1 + U_2} (z_1 - y) - \frac{2\lambda}{U_1 + U_2} + |z_1 - y| \right) \right. \\ \left. - \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{s} \left(e^{-\frac{2\pi s}{l}|z_1 - y|} + G_1(s) e^{-\frac{2\pi s}{l}(z_1 - y)} + G_2(s) e^{-\frac{2\pi s}{l}(z_1 - y)} \right) \cos\left(2\pi s \frac{x}{l}\right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.6})$$

In which the terms Γ , U , $G(s)$ and Bi are given, respectively, by:

$$\Gamma = \left[\ln\left(\frac{l}{\pi d}\right) + \frac{2\pi\lambda}{(U_1 + U_2)l} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{G_1(s) + G_2(s)}{s} \right]^{-1} \quad (\text{C.7})$$

$$U_i = \left(\frac{1}{h_i} + \frac{z_i}{\lambda} \right)^{-1} \quad (\text{C.8})$$

$$G_i(s) = \frac{\frac{Bi_i + 2\pi s}{Bi_i - 2\pi s} e^{-\frac{4\pi s}{l}z_{(3-i)}} - e^{-\frac{4\pi s}{l}(z_1+z_2)}}{e^{-\frac{4\pi s}{l}(z_1+z_2)} - \frac{Bi_1 + 2\pi s}{Bi_1 - 2\pi s}} \quad (\text{C.9})$$

$$Bi_i = \frac{h_i l}{\lambda} \quad (\text{C.10})$$

the latter representing an evaluation of the Biot number of the floor surface.

Focusing on the upper surface of the floor ($y = 0$) and imposing an adiabatic condition on the lower face:

$$\frac{\partial T(x, z_1 + z_2)}{\partial y} = 0 \text{ in } y = z_1 + z_2 \quad (\text{C.11})$$

which means $U_2 = 0$, the solution given in (6) becomes:

$$T(x)|_{y=0} = T_1 - \Gamma(T_{pipe} - T_1) \left[\frac{2\pi}{l} \left(z_1 - \frac{\lambda}{U_1} \right) - \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{e^{-\frac{2\pi s}{l} z_1} (1 + G(s))}{s} \right) \cos \left(\frac{2\pi s \left(x + \frac{l}{2} \right)}{l} \right) \right] \quad (\text{C.12})$$

where $G(s)$ is a new term which represents $(G_1(s) + G_2(s))|_{U_2=0}$, that is:

$$G(s) = \frac{\frac{Bi_1 + 2\pi s}{Bi_1 - 2\pi s} e^{-\frac{4\pi s}{l} z_2} - 2e^{-\frac{4\pi s}{l}(z_1+z_2)} - e^{-\frac{4\pi s}{l} z_2}}{\frac{Bi_1 + 2\pi s}{Bi_1 - 2\pi s} + e^{-\frac{4\pi s}{l}(z_1+z_2)}} \quad (\text{C.13})$$

The geometrical parameters appearing in the equations are schematically represented in Figure C.6.

Figure C.6. Schematic representation of the floor configuration evaluated by the analytical model, with indication of geometric parameters and generic boundary conditions.

This analytical model allows the solution of the temperature field within the floor slab in steady state conditions. It represents the analytical benchmark for our analysis and has also been used to investigate its robustness in practical cases where the assumptions of Eq. (2-5) may be violated. For the comparison with experimental results, we used actual measurements to evaluate the room mean radiant temperature, which was then used to evaluate the operative one, T_1 , and the radiative heat transfer coefficient [37]. As for the convective contribution, it could not be easily calculated from experimental results, so the value of the convective coefficient, $h_{1,conv}$, was taken from the literature: several expressions have been proposed to characterize convection in RFCS applications, however no clear agreement is present [2, 38, 39]. For this reason, and also because of its limited contribution compared to the radiative one, the convective coefficient is taken as constant and equal to $1 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$, as suggested by [40].

Shortly, the following values have been considered for as parameters for the analytical model chosen

to reproduce as closely as possible the experimental configuration.

- $h_{1,conv} = 1 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$
- $\lambda = 0.7 \text{ W/m/K}$
- $z_1 = 0.055 \text{ m}$
- $z_2 = 0.02 \text{ m}$
- $d = 0.017 \text{ m}$
- $l = [0.10, 0.25] \text{ m}$

T_{pipe} was extracted from experimental data according to the procedure described in Section 3.2.2.

C.2.3. Numerical Model for Transient Simulations

As a further tool for a comprehensive analysis, FEM simulations have also been employed in the study. A straightforward numerical model was built and simulated with COMSOL Multiphysics® software [41], in which the heat transfer equations within the solid were computed and the temperature field could be determined.

The radiant floor was schematically modeled as a 2D rectangle with circular holes to represent the pipelines. The screed consists of homogeneous material with typical thermal characteristics of a concrete layer. The geometry and thermophysical properties of the domain, along with the imposed boundary conditions needed to solve the heat transfer equations, are equivalent to the ones used in the analytical model.

The equations are discretized into finite elements arranged in an unstructured mesh automatically generated by COMSOL with a physics-controlled sequence maximum element size of 0.002 m . The mesh and boundary conditions are presented in Figure C.7. In a second part of the analysis (see Section 3.2.3), the geometry and thermal parameters were varied within specific ranges; however, the mesh specifications and boundary condition types remained unchanged.

Figure C.7. Schematic representation of the floor configuration evaluated by the numerical model, showing the mesh and the boundary conditions used.

Numerical analysis has been introduced in the present study as a method for the transient analysis of the cooling process by a radiant floor. Specifically, the simulated transient condition is a step change with a decrease of the pipe temperature T_{pipe} , namely a typical condition that occurs when

the supply temperature is lowered by the chiller. In each simulated instance, the initial condition was taken as a uniform state with all elements at the same temperature, equal to the air operative temperature above the floor, $T_1 = 26^\circ\text{C}$. This condition was assumed to be conservative and might correspond, for instance, to a start-up phase. Indeed, other possible operational conditions would start from a situation where the floor is already cooled, resulting in a lower magnitude of variation on the surface.

C.3. Results and Discussion

As previously mentioned, multiple cooling conditions were tested in the two experimental rooms. Surface temperature distribution is available both from the placement of the 9 NTC sensors on the floor of Room 1 and from the acquisition of photos of the TLC foils placed in the two test rooms. Therefore, based on the available data, we were able to assess both the local temperature distribution measured on a single TLC sheet, and also a general assessment of the macro temperature non-uniformity on the whole floor, considering the simultaneous measurements of the NTCs or of the different TLC sheets placed in the same room. On the local scale, we also carried out an assessment of the analytical and numerical modeling methods previously introduced, which were mainly used for comparison with experimental data, but were also important for further analysis on the subject.

C.3.1. Macro-Scale Floor Temperature Experimental Assessment

For an initial assessment, the floor surface is here analyzed with a macro-scale perspective, using the available temperature data from NTCs and TLCs in Room 1 and Room 2, respectively.

In Room 1, the 9 NTC sensors installed on the floor surface offered a proper assessment of the overall temperature differences, since they were distributed uniformly throughout the room (see again Figure C.1). Table C.2 reports values for simultaneous readings of the 9 NTCs (on each row). The initial 5 measurements were taken during five independent steady-state moments, i.e. when the inevitable oscillations in the measured quantities were rapid and small enough to be considered "noise". The second set of 5 measurements were instead acquired in different moments of a transient phase, in which the supply temperature set-point was changed from 20°C to 13°C .

Along with the NTC measurements, Table C.2 also shows the water dew point temperature, which is a useful indicator for condensation prevention. In the cases reported, condensation on the floor was never reached.

Table C.2. Experimental evaluation of the macro-scale temperature distribution in Room 1 using the measurements of the 9 NTCs. Representative conditions for steady-state and transient moments are shown, reporting the water supply and the operative temperatures between brackets. The last column includes the indication of the air dew point temperature.

	$T_{NTC,1}$ [°C]	$T_{NTC,2}$ [°C]	$T_{NTC,3}$ [°C]	$T_{NTC,4}$ [°C]	$T_{NTC,5}$ [°C]	$T_{NTC,6}$ [°C]	$T_{NTC,7}$ [°C]	$T_{NTC,8}$ [°C]	$T_{NTC,9}$ [°C]	T_{DP} [°C]
Steady-state – 1 ($T_{w,s} = 18.7^\circ\text{C}, T_{op} = 23.6^\circ\text{C}$)	20.9	20.9	20.2	20.2	19.9	20.4	20.4	20.2	20.4	15.1
Steady-state – 2 ($T_{w,s} = 20.3^\circ\text{C}, T_{op} = 24.4^\circ\text{C}$)	21.5	21.6	21.3	21.3	21.1	21.4	21.5	21.3	21.4	18.0
Steady-state – 3 ($T_{w,s} = 20.2^\circ\text{C}, T_{op} = 24.5^\circ\text{C}$)	21.9	21.9	21.5	21.5	21.3	21.7	21.7	21.4	21.6	17.9

Steady-state – 4 ($T_{w,s} = 19.4^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{op} = 24.0^{\circ}\text{C}$)	21.1	21.1	20.6	20.6	20.4	20.8	20.8	20.5	20.7	17.8
Steady-state – 5 ($T_{w,s} = 19.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{op} = 24.0^{\circ}\text{C}$)	21.3	21.2	20.6	20.5	20.3	20.9	20.8	20.5	20.7	17.6
Transient - 4 m before step change ($T_{w,s} = 18.1^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{op} = 24.6^{\circ}\text{C}$)	22.1	22.1	21.6	21.5	21.4	21.8	21.8	21.5	21.7	17.6
Transient - 1.5 h after step change ($T_{w,s} = 14.4^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{op} = 24.4^{\circ}\text{C}$)	21.8	21.7	20.2	19.8	19.8	20.5	20.3	19.5	20.0	17.1
Transient - 2.9 h after step change ($T_{w,s} = 14.1^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{op} = 24.2^{\circ}\text{C}$)	21.1	20.9	18.9	18.5	18.3	19.4	18.9	18.2	18.7	16.6
Transient - 4.3 h after step change ($T_{w,s} = 13.6^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{op} = 24.2^{\circ}\text{C}$)	20.5	20.2	18.1	17.8	17.5	18.6	18.2	17.5	18.0	16.7
Transient - 5.7 h after step change ($T_{w,s} = 13.3^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{op} = 23.6^{\circ}\text{C}$)	19.9	19.7	17.6	17.3	16.9	18.1	17.7	17.0	17.5	16.4

It appears that both in steady-state and time-dependent conditions, temperature variations are observed throughout the floor, although in some cases they are very low. In steady-state moments the variation is generally within the interval $0.5 \sim 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, with a maximum difference between the average floor temperature and the coldest temperature of approximately 0.5°C . Those values have a very narrow range of uncertainty (i.e., $< 0.02^{\circ}\text{C}$), as described in Section 2.1.5. In transient conditions the variations in the temperature field can be more significant, in this specific case up to 3°C . However, even in the cases where the temperature variation is higher, the delta between the average and the minimum temperature is generally 1°C . Note that the magnitude of the variation may be partially affected by the amplitude of the step change in the supply temperature. This aspect will be fully evaluated later in the numerical analysis.

The macro-scale variations in the floor surface are attributed not to the discrete spacing of the submerged pipes, but to other phenomena that may influence the surface temperature. Among these, the most influential seem to be the walls boundary conditions and the presence of obstacles to the heat transfer. For instance, it can be seen that the temperature of the fifth sensor is the lowest in every instance. This is due to its positioning, which was right under the workstation table, where a relevant reduction in the heat transfer performance.

This situation is representative of typical practical scenarios, where many objects and furnishings

could be placed on the radiant floor. These effects, together with proximity to cold/warm walls, windows, and internal gains, may cause a significant variation in temperature throughout the floor surface. And, specifically, this seems to be even more significant with transient behaviors.

On the other hand, a different macro-level assessment was performed in the second room: by analyzing the complete set of TLC measurements from all the sheets, a broad temperature distribution could be computed. The TLC measurements were recorded during two steady-state periods with only a few seconds interval between the photos. The temperatures provided in Table C.3 are the average temperatures of the very central region of each TLC sheet, having an area of 10×10 pixels, which corresponds to a square with a side length of 0.23 cm .

Table C.3. Experimental evaluation of the macro-scale temperature distribution in Room 2 using the measurements of the 3 TLC sheets located there. The water supply temperature is reported for each instance between brackets.

	$\bar{T}_{TLC,2} [^{\circ}\text{C}]$	$\bar{T}_{TLC,3} [^{\circ}\text{C}]$	$\bar{T}_{TLC,4} [^{\circ}\text{C}]$
Transient ($T_{w,s} = 17.8^{\circ}\text{C}$)	20.6	20.2	20.3
Steady-state ($T_{w,s} = 20.4^{\circ}\text{C}$)	22.9	22.3	22.2

In test room 2, the distribution is clearly more uniform. The macro variations are on the order of 0.3°C and 0.7°C for steady-state and transient conditions, respectively. Thus, they are overall less significant than the variations observed in the other room. This held true although the pipe spacing in the present room was larger. One potential explanation for this phenomenon could be that Room 2 had more homogeneous boundary conditions and fewer objects or other obstacles within the conditioned space. This may therefore be seen as further confirmation that the macro conditions and the use of the room strongly affect the floor surface temperature distribution.

Finally, still at the macro level, it is useful to give a final observation about the temperature difference of the water entering and leaving the room floor. The temperature readings on the temperature flow could not be considered reliable for absolute indications, as the used sensors were not calibrated, but could still be considered reliable for the detection of relative changes, if not as accurate absolute readings. Examining a period of steady-state operation, the average measured temperature difference between supply and return is 0.4°C . Moreover, a rough estimate can be obtained by conducting a few brief calculations to perform an analytical evaluation, considering the average operating temperature of the room as measured by the globe thermometer, the average floor temperature as measured by the 9 NTCs, a reference surface heat transfer coefficient, $h_1 = 6 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$, and the monitored mass flow:

$$\Delta T_w = \frac{h_1 A_{eff} (\bar{T}_{NTC,all} - T_{op})}{\dot{m} c} \approx 0.6^{\circ}\text{C} \quad (\text{C.14})$$

The latter ΔT_w is coherent with the experimental one. The actual temperature variation on the floor above sections of pipes with different water temperatures would be even less than the water temperature variation itself between those sections. Thus, considering that experimental surface variation (Table C.2) is even double than ΔT_w , we can conclude that floor temperature distribution is mainly affected by the macro effects at the room scale, rather than RFCS characteristics, at least

for standard values of coil depth. In addition, the ΔT_w value along the pipe validates the assumption of a single pipe temperature, as used in both analytical and numerical methods.

C.3.2. Local-Scale Floor Temperature Distribution Analysis

The primary aim of this study is to examine the temperature distribution caused by the presence of cylindrical pipes in the floor. When viewed as a two-dimensional cross section, the array of pipes appears as a discrete series of round holes within the floor plane. Due to the non-uniform configuration, the temperature gradients are not perpendicular to the floor at every point, but only over the exact position of the pipe axis, theoretically. This results in an uneven temperature distribution on the floor that is present regardless of the macro effects discussed in the previous paragraph. The next subsections present these non-uniformities considering experimental, analytical, and numerical methods.

This local scale analysis would benefit from the knowledge of the actual pipe temperature under that specific portion of the radiant floor in the test rooms, as it would allow a more accurate comparison between the experiment and the models. However, such precision was not our goal in the present research, since we were more interested in investigating the robustness of the models in practical non-ideal applications, focusing on the order of magnitude of the surface temperature variations. This is why we considered a 2D analysis a proper trade-off. Indeed, as we established in the end of the previous section, the total water temperature variations across the floor are limited, so the magnitude of the temperature variations at the floor surface would not be significantly affected.

Experimental Assessment

Images of the several liquid crystal sheets were taken at different times during the whole weekly test campaign in the two rooms. Thus, a considerable amount of data was collected, but only a selected subset is presented in the following analysis. Two measurements are presented in detail for the 10 cm pipe spacing and two more for the 25 cm pipe spacing.

First, this section presents measurements taken under steady-state conditions. In each horizontal couple presented in Figure C.8, the 2D temperature map and the 1D temperature distribution in the central plane of the crystal are shown for the same acquisition. Although the TLC sheet has an area of 30 cm x 30 cm, we analyzed and reported the hue and temperature maps over a confined area of 20 cm x 20 cm – obtained from a concentric cutting – because this way we could avoid the presence of boundary effects, such as imperfect adhesion to the ground. The chart displaying the centerline temperature, perpendicular to the pipe axis, was presented as a more comprehensible chart that could also be easily compared with the results of the analytical and numerical model.

In Figure C.8, the first and second row present the results for steady-state conditions for the TLCs in Room 1 and Room 2, respectively.

Figure C.8. Experimental measurements of LCT in steady-state cooling conditions. Two different representations are present: the 2D temperature map obtained after image processing and hue- T conversion (a, c) and the temperature profile on a central section perpendicular to the pipe axis, with the accuracy band and the moving average curve shown (b, d). Both Room 1 (a, b) and Room 2 (c, d) measurements are provided. The chiller supply temperature is $T_{w,s} = 16.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ in Room 1 and $T_{w,s} = 15.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ in Room 2; the operative temperature in Room 1 is $T_{op} = 24.6^{\circ}\text{C}$.

In Room 1 – frames (a) and (b) – with the 10 cm pipe spacing, a minor temperature variation is observed on the surface. The 2D temperature map reveals a 0.4°C spread between the warmest and coldest points. As expected from a measurement in the low error temperature range (where $T \leq 20.5^{\circ}\text{C}$), the temperature map shows a very low noise measurement. Considering a sample curve on a section perpendicular to the pipes' axes, the temperature variation is negligible, in the order of hundredths of a degree, especially when considering the moving average filtered profile. Based on the given curve, the difference between the average temperature and the coldest point (post filtering) is less than 0.1°C .

In the second row presented in Figure C.8, corresponding to a TLC foil placed in the second chamber with a larger pipe spacing, the temperature variation is more relevant. However, if the centerline temperature reading is considered (d), the variance is significantly smaller: 0.3°C , when looking at the filtered profile. Additionally, the delta between the average temperature and the coldest temperature is 0.1°C . Nonetheless, it is important to note that the TLC temperature was higher in this case, thus all the pixels of the image were in the cubic range of the hue- T curve, where the measurement uncertainty was more critical. This is why the unfiltered profile is extremely noisy. Still, the filtered profile could be an insightful evaluation worth presenting and discussing.

Therefore, previous figures demonstrate that temperature fluctuations on the surface are very limited, especially in the case of minor pipe spacing. In fact, in this case, the variation could be considered negligible, having an order of magnitude of hundredths of a degree, which is a precision difficult both to measure and to sense. A slightly different conclusion is reached for the larger pipe spacing, where the temperature variations are obviously more significant, but still small.

These local distributions should in fact be compared to the macro-level evaluations of the overall floor distribution, confirming that major floor oscillations arise from other phenomena that depend on the room's actual use and layout, rather than from the discontinuous presence of pipes. However,

as the spacing increases and the room is subjected to more stable conditions throughout, the temperature variations on the two levels become comparable.

Such stability of temperature fluctuations, however, is not generally valid. During a building's unsteady behavior, caused by a change in system settings such as a reduction of the water supply temperature, we noticed that the temperature field changes significantly and differs from the two examples previously presented. Indeed, larger variations in temperature are observed under transient conditions. The subsequent set of data plots presented in Figure C.9, corresponding to the same TLC sheet shown in Figure C.8 (a, b), proves that under these conditions the differences are more relevant, in the order of tenths of a degree, already in the first test room.

Figure C.9. Experimental measurements of LCT in transient cooling conditions for the sheet placed in Room 1. Two different representations are present: the 2D temperature map obtained after image processing and hue-T conversion (a) and the temperature profile on a central section perpendicular to the pipe axis, with the accuracy band and the moving average curve shown (b). The chiller supply temperature is $T_{w,s} = 14.6^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the room operative temperature is $T_{op} = 24.6^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Here, the peak to valley temperature difference is 2°C based on the 2D evaluation and 0.7°C when examining the filtered temperature in the central section. The minimum temperature is 0.2°C lower than the curve average. As anticipated, these findings indicate a greater variation compared to previous observations of the exact same floor region. The causes of this increased variation will be further discussed in a later section with the aid of numerical simulations. Presumably, however, we can say that the transient oscillations are more relevant because when the flow temperature is lowered, the path the heat flux must take just above the pipe is shorter than that going, for example, to the midpoint between two adjacent pipes. Therefore, during the transition, the temperature change "arrives" in advance in the region just above the tube.

The experimental analysis on the local temperature distributions shows limited maximum variations, especially concerning Room 1 results, both for steady and unsteady conditions. For scenarios like this, in which the pipe spacing is small, the room has objects and furnishings within, and the boundary conditions are significantly different, the floor temperature field appears to be more influenced by macro-scale phenomena. On the other hand, in Room 2, where the pipe spacing is wider and the conditions in the room are more uniform, the local fluctuations of the surface temperature are comparable with those recorded on different spots across the floor. Therefore, when the macro phenomena are not significant and the pipe spacing is wide enough, the local evaluation is needed to characterize the distribution.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that the magnitude of the results obtained so far is also applicable to

heating conditions. Room 2 was tested under various operating conditions, including heating mode. Figure C.10 shows the results of a distribution recorded during this phase. We can obviously see that when heating, the surface temperature is generally much higher. However, the variation was still very limited, in the order of a few tenths of a degree.

Figure C.10. Experimental measurements of LCT in unsteady heating conditions for the sheet placed in Room 2. Two different representations are present: the 2D temperature map obtained after image processing and hue- T conversion (a) and the temperature profile on a central section perpendicular to the pipe axis, with the accuracy band and the moving average curve shown (b). The chiller supply temperature is $T_{w,s} = 28.4^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Steady-State Analytical Model Assessment

The analytical model presented in Section 2.1 is capable of evaluating the two-dimensional temperature field over the entire thickness of the floor. Nevertheless, for our research needs, we are primarily interested in the superficial temperature fluctuations. This model is thus used as a further tool for the local analysis of the temperature distribution in a radiant floor.

To compare the model with the data collected from the test rooms, we plotted the experimental temperature reading at the center plane of the TLC sheet against the corresponding analytical temperature curve. As it was not possible to accurately measure the temperature of the pipe below each TLC foil during experimental tests, an iterative procedure is used to determine the value of T_{pipe} , which is the floor boundary condition imposed in the analytical model. The iteration is continued until the x -averaged values of both profiles coincide. Figure C.11 displays a comparison between the two steady-state results previously presented in Figure C.8 and Glück's model.

Figure C.11. Comparison between the LCT experimental measurements in steady-state conditions and Glück's analytical model results. For Room 1 (a) and Room 2 (b).

This qualitative comparison immediately reveals the substantial consistency between the model and the experimental results, with the uncertainty having the same order of magnitude of the maximum oscillation predicted by the analytical model. We conclude that Glück's analytical model (Eq. 12) can be used for evaluating the magnitude of the local temperature variation on the surface even in real-world situations, when various conditions and factors might deviate from the ideal assumptions of the analytical evaluation. For instance, the floor material might not be truly uniform, and both the tile and the plastic pipe may lack proper contact with the filling screed. Furthermore, many of the boundary conditions required by the analytical model are generally not satisfied: there are no fully adiabatic surfaces, the phenomenon has 3D effects as the temperature varies along the tubes, the spacing is not uniform throughout the floor, the convection coefficient varies with position and time, and so forth.

Transient Numerical Model Assessment

Under steady-state conditions, the surface temperature of the floor appears to be relatively uniform. However, in the practical operation of radiant floors, the system often operates in transient conditions. Both environmental factors, cooling load and indoor conditions may change rapidly, forcing the system to operate in an unsteady regime. To provide a comprehensive evaluation, we report here a comparison of the experimental results with a numerical FEM model suitable for transient simulations. First, however, the numerical model alone is used to study the phenomenon of non-stationary floor heat transfer.

For the first numerical analysis, the same geometric and thermal properties used for the analytical model are assumed. The uniform initial temperature is 26°C , which is the indoor operative temperature above the floor. The simulation then proceeds with a step change in the pipe temperature down to 10°C . The value of T_{pipe} can be considered as constant even in a transient simulation, considering the typical timescale of the water loop dynamics. According to RFCS standard design guidelines, the water velocity within the coils should be included in the $0.5 \sim 1.5 \text{ m/s}$ range. For the experimental Room 1, the water velocity is indeed estimated to be $v_w = 0.47 \text{ m/s}$. This results in a crossing time of the entire pipe equal to $t_{crossing} \approx 3 \text{ min}$, a value that is negligible when compared to typical characteristic times of radiant systems [42]. Together with the aforementioned discussion on limited ΔT_w , this fact supports the transient representation of the floor with only a 2D section with a single T_{pipe} value, since it can be assumed that the boundary condition for the pipe changes almost simultaneously in each region of the floor.

The numerical results are shown in Figure C.12 for different time steps of the simulations as a 2D map of the temperature distribution. A vectorial rendering of the gradient is also displayed on the corresponding temperature field. The surface temperature profile is shown above each map.

Figure C.12. Numerical results for the floor temperature distribution during a transient step change in the pipe temperature boundary condition. The entire internal temperature field, its gradient, and the surface temperature profile are shown for four representative time steps.

Four representative moments are shown in the figure. Initially, the temperature is uniform throughout the floor, then when a different boundary condition is activated on the pipes, the variation starts to diffuse within the floor till a new steady-state condition. The temperature amplitude of the surface oscillations increases and then decays. In agreement with the experimental results, this result proves that the temperature variations obtained in transient conditions are higher than those in steady conditions. During the transient moments, the gradient is higher above the pipe and, therefore, the part of the floor right above it cools down more rapidly, causing a greater oscillation on the surface temperature.

The occurrence of the maximum temperature variation during a transient period has been further investigated, considering several geometric configurations for the radiant floor, and different values of the total heat transfer coefficient and pipe temperature:

- Pipe spacing l : [0.10, 0.15, 0.25] m
- Pipe temperature T_{pipe} (after the step change): [14, 16, 18, 20, 22, 24]°C
- Surface heat transfer coefficient h_1 : [5, 6, 7, 8] W/m²/K
- Pipe depth z_1 : [0.025, 0.050, 0.100] m

This way, a matrix of 216 different simulations was created with the aim of obtaining a general indication of the maximum value and when it happens. Figure C.13 shows only some of these results – considering a single value for h_1 – in terms of the maximum surface temperature oscillation, calculated as:

$$\Delta T_{max-min}(t) = \max(T(x, y)|_{t, y=0}) - \min(T(x, y)|_{t, y=0}) \quad (C.15)$$

where $y = 0$ indicates that the evaluation was performed only on the surface of the floor. All the profiles of the $\Delta T_{max-min}$ are reported as a function of time.

Figure C.13. Maximum temperature change on the floor surface as a function of time, derived from numerical simulations. Each subgraph represents a different combination of spacing (l) and pipe immersion depth (z_1). The different colors represent the different pipe temperatures used as new boundary conditions. The curves refer to the simulations with surface heat transfer coefficient equal to $h_1 = 6 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$.

The figure shows that the highest peak of variation is reached in the range of 0.17 ~ 2.9 hours, then the values slowly decrease to the new steady conditions. A great variety of maximum values for the $\Delta T_{max-min}$ is obtained. For large z_1 , the temperature differences can be very low, but they can also reach up to 8.5°C if the pipes are located close to the surface and far apart from each other.

To better represent and aggregate the results, the maximum temperature change $\max(\Delta T_{max-min}(t))$ is normalized by the difference between the initial temperature condition (T_1) and the pipe temperature after the step change (T_{pipe}), resulting in the dimensionless variable:

$$\theta_{max} = \frac{\max(\Delta T_{max-min}(t))}{T_1 - T_{pipe}} \quad (C.16)$$

The metric was assessed across all 216 numerical simulations and also applied to experimental data. In the case of experimental results, the pipe temperature required calculation. We estimated the

temperature difference between the outer pipe surface and the water temperature as $\Delta T_{p-w} = 0.8^\circ\text{C}$, using the water enthalpy variation to determine the specific heat flux, considering turbulent forced convection within the pipe, and also calculating the thermal resistance of its plastic material. The value of ΔT_{p-w} was then summed to the average experimental water temperature to estimate the outer pipe temperature to be used in the current analysis.

Figure C.14 presents the θ_{max} values obtained from all the simulated configurations, together with the representation of the many values recorded on the liquid crystal sheet placed in Room 1.

Figure C.14. Dimensionless representation of the maximum temperature variation on the floor surface achieved over the whole transient, derived from numerical simulations (216 different scenarios). Data from experimental measurements with TLC are also shown along with the numerical results.

The dimensionless analysis indicates a clear aggregation of the values for several pipe temperatures and heat transfer coefficients, highlighting only two significant influencing parameters: the pipe spacing l and the depth of immersion z_1 . Particularly, the plot in Figure C.14 reveals three main trend lines originating from the numerical simulations, each for every pipe spacing. The numerical results could thus be used to create a useful map to evaluate the maximum local temperature oscillation recordable on a radiant floor, whichever the condition it is, since the steady-state variation is much smaller.

Experimental results are in general agreement with the numerical ones, as all the measurements are below the lower curve, representing the $l = 10$ cm simulations. The numerical estimate coherently appears to be conservative, since not all the experimental measurements were taken at the moment corresponding to the peak of the transient variation.

To give some quantitative examples, Table C.4 summarizes some important results for the numerical simulation scenarios where $l = 10$ cm, $z_1 = 5$ cm, and $h_1 = 6$ W/m²/K. This is considered a representative situation for typical applications. The actual results in terms of dimensional maximum temperature variations $\max(\Delta T_{max-min}(t))$ are more easily understandable.

Table C.4. Quantitative representation of the maximum temperature variation observed in numerical simulations, considering $l = 10 \text{ cm}$, $z_1 = 5 \text{ cm}$, and $h_1 = 6 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$. T_1 represents the initial condition, while T_{pipe} the new boundary condition after the step change.

T_1 [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	T_{pipe} [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	$\max(\Delta T_{\max-\min}(t))$ [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
26.00	14.00	0.96
26.00	16.00	0.81
26.00	18.00	0.61
26.00	20.00	0.47
26.00	22.00	0.30
26.00	24.00	0.15

Instead, in the experimental analysis, the higher variation measured on the TLC placed in Room 1 was 0.46°C .

C.4. Conclusions

This study employs a multi-perspective approach to assess the distribution of surface temperatures on radiant floor systems during cooling operation. The macro room scale and the local-scale distribution are experimentally analyzed using two test rooms equipped with liquid crystal thermography, NTCs, and microclimate monitoring station. Then, experimental results are compared with analytical and numerical models. In addition, the numerical method is used to more extensively study radiant floors in transient conditions, considering a variety of configurations.

The primary objective was to determine whether modeling a radiant floor by using a single temperature to represent its entire surface, as assumed a priori in many existing modeling methods, could be a justifiable assumption. Temperature variations are inevitably present due to both local and macro effects. However, if the magnitude of these variations is minimal, their presence and effect may be neglected. Furthermore, our research could also provide important insights for the control of RFCS. In fact, the knowledge of the surface temperature distribution in a radiant floor is a crucial feature to consider for condensation prevention, since a good estimate of its minimum value could help to maximize the cooling capacity of the system without causing condensation.

The temperature variations are initially evaluated at a macro scale, considering the spatial distribution over the entire floor of the two available test rooms. In the first test room, with 10 cm pipe spacing, the fluctuations on the temperature field in steady-state are within the interval $0.5 \sim 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, but in transient conditions they get as high as 3°C . However, the maximum recorded gap between the average and the coldest point temperature is 1°C . Considering that the temperature variation of the circulating water is almost 0.5°C , we conclude that the room-scale temperature distribution is mainly due to the interaction of the RFCS surface with the indoor environment, including envelope and objects, rather than pipe-surface heat transfer interactions, at least for standard configurations. This is confirmed by the data collected in the second test room, where the RFCS have a larger pipe spacing, but the monitored temperature is more uniform than in Room 1 (deviation of $0.3 \sim 0.7^{\circ}\text{C}$). The discrepancy between the two rooms is thus explained by the fact that the RFCS in the second room has more uniform boundary conditions and less interactions with the indoor environment, since the room is emptier.

At a local scale, with dimensions comparable to pipe spacing, the analysis demonstrates good agreement with both analytical and numerical models. These models can thus be used as validated

tools for RFCS modeling, even when some of the model assumptions are not fully satisfied. All the methods show that for typical pipe spacing and screed depth, steady-state floor surface temperature variations are limited to only a few hundredths of a degree. A similar result is observed in the transient numerical analysis, but the temperature fluctuations are shown to be amplified during the transient phases. More specifically, the numerical analysis shows that during a transient phase, the maximum non-uniformity appears after less than 3 h , but the maximum observed variation depends on the depth and spacing of the pipes and the pipe temperature, which is strictly related to the water supply temperature. Nevertheless, by using a dimensionless approach, it is possible to eliminate the dependence on the pipe temperature. Therefore, this study also proposes a simple dimensionless map to evaluate the temperature of the coldest spot on the floor surface. Finally, based on our extensive investigation of the local temperature distribution, we obtained a conservative estimate indicating that the deviation range between the average temperature of the floor and its minimum value is within a range of 1°C. This outcome should not invalidate the single-node modeling approach for RFCS, but it can be a useful indication in situations where a more thorough examination is desired, e.g., for condensation verification.

Other studies in the literature have reported higher maximum temperature variations in experimental assessments of radiant system temperature distribution. However, this was only observed in less massive systems such as chilled ceilings or novel light-weight floor configurations. In our study, the reduced oscillations were attributed to the screed, which helped to smooth the temperature variation across the floor. Such a configuration was considered representative of the typical radiant floor found in residential buildings.

In terms of future development on RFCS energy models, design and control guidelines, the present work has experimentally proven that a single node for the floor surface temperature is a valid assumption, but its actual value must be necessarily assessed jointly with the analysis of the indoor environment and conditions. This notable result has been reinforced by numerical and analytical analyses. While the investigation focused primarily on cooling applications, the results can be extended to heating applications as well, since the physical phenomenon is analogous.

C.5. Nomenclature

Acronyms

IRT – InfraRed Thermography

FEM – Finite Elements Method

LCT – Liquid Crystal Thermography

RFCS – Radiant Floor Cooling System

TLC – Thermochromic Liquid Crystals

Symbols

A_{eff} – effective exchanging area of the floor

Bi – Biot number

c – specific heat of water

d – pipe outer diameter

h_1 – global heat transfer coefficient above the floor (convective + radiant)

$h_{1,conv}$ – convective heat transfer coefficient above the floor

h_2 – global heat transfer coefficient above the floor (convective + radiant)
 l – pipe spacing
 \dot{m} – experimental mass flow within the pipe
 R – electric resistance of the NTC thermistor
 $t_{crossing}$ – water crossing time of the whole serpentine
 $T(x, y)$ – Floor temperature
 T_1 – operative temperature above the floor
 T_2 – temperature of the space below the floor
 T_{LCT} – surface temperature measured by liquid crystal thermography
 T_{NTC} – surface temperature measured by NTC thermistor
 $T_{NTC,i}$ – temperature measured by i^{th} NTC thermistor
 T_{op} – experimental operative temperature measured by globe thermometer
 T_{pipe} – temperature on the outer diameter of the buried pipes
 $\bar{T}_{TLC,i}$ – spatial averaged temperature on the central portion of the i^{th} TLC sheet
 T_w – water bulk temperature
 $T_{w,s}$ – experimental water supply temperature leaving the chiller
 u – expanded uncertainty (95% coverage factor)
 U_1 – floor Thermal transmittance above the pipes
 U_2 – floor Thermal transmittance below the pipes
 V – electric voltage for NTC resistance reading
 v_w – experimental water velocity within the pipes
 x – coordinate parallel to floor surface
 y – coordinate perpendicular to floor surface
 z_1 – pipe immersion depth
 z_2 – pipe distance from below surface
 $\Delta T_{max-min}(t)$ – temperature difference, for each timestep t , between the warmest and coldest points on the surface
 ΔT_{p-w} – difference between water bulk temperature and temperature on the external diameter of the pipe
 ΔT_w – water temperature difference between supply and return conditions

Greek Letters

λ – floor thermal conductivity
 θ_{max} – dimensionless indication of the maximum temperature variation on the floor surface
 σ – standard deviation for uncertainty in TLC temperature measurements

C.6. References

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Appendix D

Complete Results of the Parametric Simulative Study

This appendix presents the complete results of the parametric simulations introduced and partially discussed in Chapter 4. It includes all 288 case studies and the seasonal performance metrics defined in the main text. Results are shown first for the heating mode and then for cooling. Within each section, outcomes are reported separately for the living zone, the night zone, and the aggregated case.

D.1. Heating

D.1.1. Living Zone

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out, \%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym, \%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°Ch]	$PI_{in, \%}$ [%]	$PI_{in, \%}$ [%]	$T_{f, avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF, max, H}$ [W/m ²]
1	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.35	12.49	19.68	0.00	763.75	75.84	89.76	23.52	145.21
2	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.32	12.03	17.50	0.00	817.02	79.91	90.89	23.58	142.18
3	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.40	12.76	21.31	0.00	629.43	73.72	89.63	23.32	143.32
4	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.34	12.50	19.95	0.00	819.26	75.49	89.75	23.55	147.63
5	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.31	12.03	17.51	0.00	826.42	79.73	90.85	23.59	145.67
6	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.39	12.76	21.74	0.00	661.72	73.28	89.73	23.33	146.97
7	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.42	13.83	27.61	0.00	792.21	68.00	86.66	23.08	132.18
8	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.37	12.99	22.30	0.00	853.41	72.88	88.75	23.23	130.06
9	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.45	14.02	28.77	0.00	676.07	66.25	86.55	22.94	131.74
10	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.42	14.17	29.64	0.00	847.29	65.56	85.61	23.01	135.09
11	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.37	13.23	24.07	0.00	885.56	71.26	88.21	23.17	133.76
12	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.45	14.33	30.97	0.00	712.75	63.91	85.62	22.86	134.79
13	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.48	13.69	28.18	0.00	467.76	67.43	87.06	23.32	145.48
14	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.43	12.81	23.37	0.00	494.47	72.33	89.49	23.44	143.29
15	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.51	14.09	30.61	0.00	431.08	64.89	86.75	23.17	144.19
16	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.47	13.70	28.80	0.00	480.69	66.81	86.97	23.33	149.07
17	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.42	12.80	23.66	0.00	512.51	72.04	89.47	23.46	146.18
18	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.51	14.08	31.08	0.00	432.58	64.31	86.64	23.18	147.91
19	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.57	15.93	38.25	0.00	481.05	57.45	79.57	22.77	132.33
20	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.50	14.43	32.11	0.00	511.60	64.03	84.77	23.00	131.12
21	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.59	16.21	39.90	0.00	442.85	55.49	79.32	22.67	131.98
22	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.58	16.46	40.57	0.00	503.39	54.98	77.95	22.67	133.88
23	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.51	14.85	34.43	0.00	546.93	61.52	83.20	22.91	133.01
24	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.60	16.71	42.12	0.00	458.38	52.90	77.80	22.57	133.88
25	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.91	26.37	61.97	0.00	473.14	33.82	52.70	21.90	147.69
26	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.90	26.28	61.48	0.00	468.93	34.32	52.78	21.97	147.57
27	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.92	26.56	63.06	0.00	466.01	32.31	52.52	21.85	147.54
28	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.90	26.30	62.05	0.00	448.76	33.62	52.50	21.90	150.85

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asy\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
29	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.89	26.21	61.58	0.00	444.33	34.18	52.55	21.96	149.67
30	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.91	26.46	63.04	0.00	440.10	32.44	52.35	21.86	149.77
31	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.04	31.65	67.69	0.00	480.17	28.02	45.70	20.97	133.64
32	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-1.03	31.48	66.75	0.00	468.23	28.94	45.81	21.06	133.45
33	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.05	31.76	68.32	0.00	474.10	27.10	45.57	20.94	133.63
34	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.06	32.72	68.73	0.00	464.83	27.10	44.32	20.78	134.95
35	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.05	32.55	67.96	0.00	459.41	27.95	44.40	20.86	134.61
36	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.07	32.82	69.34	0.00	457.98	26.36	44.27	20.74	134.61
37	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-1.06	31.75	69.20	0.00	642.53	27.89	45.26	21.59	146.53
38	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-1.05	31.57	68.21	0.00	608.86	28.86	45.43	21.68	146.53
39	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-1.07	31.89	70.51	0.00	639.81	26.82	45.15	21.57	146.48
40	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-1.05	31.66	69.38	0.00	610.34	27.83	45.14	21.58	150.59
41	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-1.04	31.48	68.30	0.00	573.31	28.79	45.27	21.67	149.95
42	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.06	31.82	70.73	0.00	607.36	26.57	45.02	21.55	150.05
43	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.21	37.93	75.47	0.00	661.78	22.62	39.32	20.59	132.62
44	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-1.20	37.65	73.72	0.00	608.15	24.37	39.60	20.70	132.40
45	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.22	38.04	76.52	0.00	660.74	21.60	39.23	20.57	132.35
46	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.24	39.16	76.97	0.00	631.68	21.13	37.95	20.37	134.19
47	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.23	38.86	75.02	0.00	577.94	23.10	38.35	20.48	133.88
48	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.25	39.24	77.73	0.00	629.53	20.37	37.90	20.35	133.99
49	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.55	21.42	27.23	0.00	797.00	71.16	78.18	22.04	130.36
50	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.53	20.98	26.24	0.00	838.67	72.10	79.13	22.16	130.13
51	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.61	21.63	27.54	0.00	687.82	67.65	77.88	21.76	129.76
52	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.54	21.49	27.51	0.00	812.75	70.83	77.98	22.06	131.82
53	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.52	21.07	26.55	0.00	853.73	71.83	78.81	22.15	131.08
54	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.60	21.70	27.81	0.00	695.24	67.46	77.73	21.76	131.27
55	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.57	21.96	28.76	0.00	827.26	68.63	77.46	21.76	114.08
56	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.54	21.48	27.68	0.00	885.99	70.17	78.25	21.93	113.85
57	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.62	22.12	28.88	0.00	725.27	65.68	77.25	21.53	114.00
58	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.57	22.14	29.23	0.00	842.53	67.92	77.18	21.70	115.35
59	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.54	21.66	28.41	0.00	902.76	69.47	78.02	21.86	114.60
60	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.62	22.31	29.59	0.00	741.78	65.19	76.98	21.48	114.87

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
61	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.64	21.49	26.27	0.00	691.81	69.37	78.36	21.87	130.13
62	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.61	20.94	24.54	0.00	637.51	71.75	79.22	22.07	130.06
63	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.69	21.82	27.67	0.00	662.93	66.17	78.13	21.68	129.39
64	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.64	21.59	26.84	0.00	675.86	68.75	78.17	21.88	131.24
65	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.61	21.02	25.11	0.00	635.61	71.10	79.07	22.09	131.09
66	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.68	21.87	28.29	0.00	646.08	65.58	77.89	21.71	130.73
67	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.67	22.16	28.46	0.00	707.85	66.35	77.14	21.55	114.07
68	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.63	21.47	26.22	0.00	661.18	69.57	78.19	21.83	113.89
69	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.71	22.42	29.66	0.00	678.49	63.17	76.84	21.41	113.63
70	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.68	22.40	29.41	0.00	705.19	64.95	76.58	21.49	114.39
71	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.63	21.69	27.24	0.00	664.33	68.12	77.59	21.76	114.81
72	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.71	22.65	30.54	0.00	673.93	61.84	76.25	21.36	114.04
73	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.77	23.57	35.93	0.00	709.81	49.35	74.16	21.70	131.13
74	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.74	22.80	33.06	0.00	643.73	53.84	75.19	22.08	131.22
75	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.80	23.88	38.21	0.00	699.11	45.70	73.90	21.59	130.83
76	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.76	23.56	35.53	0.00	700.86	50.11	74.02	21.74	132.94
77	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.72	22.82	33.27	0.00	624.20	54.40	75.07	22.11	132.88
78	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.79	23.89	38.10	0.00	687.82	46.31	73.73	21.61	132.31
79	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.83	24.85	42.44	0.00	722.99	42.17	69.95	21.16	114.50
80	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.78	23.93	38.26	0.00	649.28	48.79	71.64	21.59	114.79
81	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.85	25.11	44.83	0.00	712.84	39.06	69.78	21.08	114.42
82	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.84	25.17	43.73	0.00	716.08	41.39	68.93	21.08	115.01
83	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.78	24.26	39.47	0.00	631.67	47.96	70.48	21.49	115.22
84	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.86	25.43	45.99	0.00	703.95	38.58	68.76	20.98	114.70
85	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.85	24.58	41.62	0.00	892.18	43.70	70.97	21.59	130.57
86	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.80	23.54	36.68	0.00	754.14	51.02	72.41	22.03	130.78
87	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.88	24.93	44.51	0.00	890.91	39.01	70.55	21.51	130.56
88	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.85	24.63	41.64	0.00	876.05	43.58	70.69	21.59	131.81
89	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.80	23.61	36.89	0.00	714.35	50.92	72.26	22.04	131.80
90	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.87	24.97	44.64	0.00	874.59	39.37	70.28	21.51	131.75
91	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.93	26.34	50.91	0.00	908.48	34.64	65.11	20.97	114.38
92	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.86	25.06	43.72	0.00	737.83	44.83	67.65	21.46	114.40

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
93	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.94	26.60	53.07	0.00	907.28	32.24	64.73	20.92	114.30
94	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.94	26.79	52.93	0.00	900.89	33.39	63.43	20.85	114.22
95	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.87	25.48	45.24	0.00	714.31	43.78	65.91	21.34	114.53
96	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.95	27.03	54.69	0.00	899.90	31.42	63.17	20.80	114.11
97	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.29	11.70	40.11	0.00	1709.96	75.81	79.95	23.48	68.52
98	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.35	12.86	44.60	0.00	1933.54	70.09	74.02	23.77	73.49
99	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.22	10.79	32.11	0.00	1451.90	77.20	83.19	23.01	67.71
100	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.29	11.53	40.23	0.00	1704.32	77.29	81.47	23.44	68.58
101	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.34	12.51	44.31	0.00	1872.08	71.14	75.56	23.63	73.33
102	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.21	10.50	30.31	0.00	1392.33	78.36	85.10	22.89	67.12
103	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.29	11.86	41.23	0.00	1786.62	75.01	79.62	23.48	61.56
104	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.35	13.03	46.19	0.00	1982.18	69.43	73.66	23.77	65.09
105	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.22	10.99	33.23	0.00	1501.18	76.25	82.78	23.04	60.34
106	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.29	11.71	41.40	0.00	1748.79	76.35	80.84	23.41	60.18
107	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.35	12.82	46.75	0.00	1961.47	69.91	74.80	23.67	64.47
108	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.22	10.78	32.31	0.00	1464.83	77.43	84.43	22.96	59.62
109	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.08	8.49	14.20	0.00	996.12	88.35	93.25	22.73	66.65
110	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.12	8.68	16.79	0.00	1136.60	87.70	92.28	23.05	71.42
111	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.02	8.22	12.06	0.00	851.52	86.12	93.67	22.45	66.81
112	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.08	8.49	13.94	0.00	982.85	88.16	93.79	22.70	67.02
113	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.13	8.76	17.33	0.00	1171.89	87.58	92.60	23.06	72.16
114	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.03	8.24	11.87	0.00	840.50	86.02	94.05	22.47	66.22
115	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.07	8.62	14.84	0.00	1035.13	87.34	93.10	22.70	59.74
116	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.13	8.88	18.16	0.00	1200.91	87.23	92.02	23.09	64.23
117	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.03	8.38	12.72	0.00	901.95	85.50	93.48	22.48	59.20
118	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.07	8.62	14.54	0.00	1028.70	87.32	93.61	22.67	59.17
119	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.14	9.01	19.01	0.00	1266.56	86.65	92.37	23.09	63.83
120	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.03	8.41	12.66	0.00	905.43	84.86	93.75	22.47	58.38
121	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.00	8.52	13.99	0.00	879.29	81.37	92.86	22.54	66.04
122	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.03	8.29	13.32	0.00	846.47	83.30	93.73	22.86	72.65
123	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.05	8.44	12.71	0.00	784.39	77.66	92.97	22.27	65.21
124	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.01	8.54	14.02	0.00	842.38	81.96	93.04	22.59	66.56

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
125	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.04	8.39	13.80	0.00	812.20	83.32	93.93	22.90	72.78
126	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.04	8.45	12.73	0.00	739.34	78.83	93.12	22.28	65.62
127	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.01	8.68	14.67	0.00	898.42	79.76	92.55	22.44	60.12
128	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.03	8.51	14.42	0.00	862.11	82.18	93.46	22.84	65.41
129	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.06	8.61	13.59	0.00	811.76	76.65	92.65	22.20	58.94
130	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.00	8.71	14.69	0.00	877.80	80.56	92.80	22.50	59.05
131	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.04	8.63	14.87	0.00	847.49	82.22	93.65	22.84	65.02
132	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.05	8.64	13.85	0.00	779.41	77.77	92.82	22.21	58.40
133	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.12	8.02	9.19	0.00	918.19	78.61	93.72	22.28	65.50
134	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.07	7.67	8.07	0.00	794.66	83.90	94.55	22.76	72.97
135	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.17	8.16	10.08	0.00	887.48	72.70	93.32	22.11	64.94
136	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.11	8.02	9.34	0.00	887.28	78.30	93.69	22.34	65.62
137	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.06	7.75	8.43	0.00	771.75	82.96	94.44	22.83	72.15
138	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.16	8.16	10.28	0.00	850.47	72.70	93.33	22.15	64.95
139	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.13	8.22	10.10	0.00	955.47	74.30	93.32	22.17	59.77
140	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.07	7.84	8.64	0.00	814.75	81.89	94.27	22.71	65.06
141	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.17	8.37	11.17	0.00	924.04	69.60	92.90	22.01	58.50
142	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.13	8.25	10.51	0.00	941.48	74.38	93.10	22.21	58.14
143	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.06	7.95	9.27	0.00	807.50	80.39	94.11	22.73	64.20
144	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.17	8.42	11.62	0.00	907.80	69.30	92.73	22.03	58.16
145	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.27	11.87	27.54	0.00	1119.12	80.75	83.89	23.26	76.41
146	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.31	12.88	31.94	0.00	1358.45	76.47	79.94	23.47	79.43
147	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.19	11.26	23.32	0.00	901.34	80.05	84.91	22.78	75.73
148	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.26	11.53	26.53	0.00	1089.82	81.42	84.95	23.14	77.43
149	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.30	12.44	30.58	0.00	1298.65	77.25	80.99	23.29	79.01
150	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.18	10.89	21.93	0.00	854.29	80.39	85.39	22.64	75.87
151	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.27	12.00	28.21	0.00	1149.77	80.27	83.55	23.25	67.53
152	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.32	13.04	32.76	0.00	1397.58	76.00	79.66	23.49	69.79
153	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.20	11.40	23.95	0.00	929.51	80.02	84.72	22.81	66.96
154	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.26	11.70	27.39	0.00	1124.78	80.77	84.43	23.14	67.58
155	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.31	12.68	31.86	0.00	1352.35	76.70	80.49	23.32	69.93
156	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.19	11.08	22.87	0.00	894.25	80.04	85.18	22.69	66.20

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
157	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.04	8.29	12.61	0.00	606.82	87.32	90.83	22.37	76.10
158	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.08	8.49	13.50	0.00	686.34	86.43	89.67	22.68	79.94
159	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.02	8.22	12.41	0.00	588.61	85.42	90.93	22.08	74.72
160	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.04	8.18	12.10	0.00	585.60	87.81	91.40	22.31	75.98
161	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.09	8.39	13.27	0.00	664.68	86.72	90.20	22.63	79.17
162	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.02	8.11	11.95	0.00	562.39	85.98	91.50	22.05	74.95
163	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.03	8.37	12.76	0.00	626.59	86.81	90.68	22.34	66.62
164	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.09	8.60	13.79	0.00	699.53	86.23	89.52	22.70	70.36
165	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.01	8.29	12.50	0.00	610.87	85.36	90.83	22.13	66.86
166	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.04	8.28	12.27	0.00	609.52	87.32	91.23	22.31	68.06
167	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.10	8.57	13.57	0.00	692.09	86.41	90.02	22.67	69.57
168	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.01	8.21	12.12	0.00	588.74	85.43	91.37	22.10	65.82
169	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.02	8.60	13.72	0.00	635.85	80.83	90.15	22.34	70.41
170	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.01	8.43	13.89	0.00	621.07	82.70	90.62	22.63	78.12
171	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.07	8.69	14.01	0.00	599.23	75.46	90.01	22.08	69.37
172	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.01	8.52	13.59	0.00	619.24	81.96	90.65	22.37	70.43
173	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.03	8.38	13.89	0.00	601.36	83.43	91.13	22.68	78.37
174	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.06	8.57	13.71	0.00	579.35	77.28	90.62	22.08	69.22
175	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.02	8.71	13.97	0.00	645.04	78.85	89.87	22.27	63.05
176	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.02	8.55	14.33	0.00	621.05	82.46	90.54	22.66	69.19
177	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.07	8.77	14.29	0.00	612.21	75.02	89.86	22.06	62.71
178	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.02	8.63	13.97	0.00	630.33	80.48	90.36	22.28	63.61
179	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.04	8.55	14.39	0.00	608.82	83.57	90.99	22.71	68.13
180	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.06	8.68	14.07	0.00	598.58	76.05	90.33	22.03	62.86
181	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.16	7.93	8.87	0.00	870.44	81.54	94.37	21.93	71.44
182	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.11	7.58	7.91	0.00	753.57	86.39	94.81	22.32	77.67
183	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.19	8.17	9.55	0.00	863.19	75.09	94.03	21.79	69.93
184	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.15	7.86	8.47	0.00	845.40	82.56	94.43	21.95	72.32
185	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.09	7.52	7.43	0.00	707.53	86.63	94.86	22.41	77.62
186	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.19	8.09	9.25	0.00	838.34	75.92	94.05	21.81	69.28
187	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.16	8.06	9.42	0.00	886.88	78.68	94.09	21.85	63.10
188	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.10	7.62	7.92	0.00	733.47	86.29	94.74	22.34	68.69

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
189	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.20	8.27	10.06	0.00	879.83	73.05	93.83	21.73	62.93
190	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.16	8.00	9.16	0.00	868.17	79.42	94.15	21.87	63.63
191	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.09	7.60	7.69	0.00	687.54	86.48	94.80	22.39	67.36
192	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.19	8.23	9.84	0.00	860.63	72.71	93.83	21.74	62.61
193	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.97	28.49	85.93	0.00	2040.21	32.37	33.17	26.05	37.95
194	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	1.09	33.38	89.94	0.00	2375.16	22.53	23.10	26.71	42.19
195	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.94	27.54	83.10	0.00	2007.54	35.89	36.81	25.86	37.24
196	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.95	27.38	86.14	0.00	1983.90	33.65	34.43	25.80	39.36
197	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	1.06	32.06	89.65	0.00	2238.48	24.33	24.76	26.41	45.11
198	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.91	26.42	82.84	0.00	1915.62	36.91	37.88	25.60	39.07
199	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.97	28.61	86.26	0.00	2051.59	31.83	32.69	26.08	35.77
200	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.09	33.46	89.84	0.00	2382.56	22.55	23.17	26.73	40.62
201	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.94	27.70	83.50	0.00	2023.86	35.18	36.14	25.90	35.13
202	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.95	27.66	86.45	0.00	2005.33	32.72	33.56	25.86	37.59
203	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.06	32.27	89.68	0.00	2263.87	24.32	24.75	26.46	40.67
204	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.92	26.66	83.17	0.00	1934.40	36.36	37.37	25.65	37.17
205	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.58	14.78	59.19	0.00	1411.57	68.55	69.39	24.31	40.59
206	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.64	16.49	65.76	0.00	1667.48	57.71	58.35	24.68	49.73
207	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.53	13.80	54.18	0.00	1349.44	72.90	73.96	24.05	41.65
208	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.56	14.29	57.95	0.00	1355.33	70.59	71.41	24.10	42.49
209	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.63	15.98	65.62	0.00	1619.44	60.33	60.97	24.49	46.53
210	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.52	13.38	53.29	0.00	1296.19	74.97	76.11	23.87	41.33
211	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.58	14.85	59.77	0.00	1440.17	67.89	68.74	24.34	38.13
212	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.65	16.71	66.81	0.00	1708.76	56.52	57.18	24.74	43.39
213	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.54	13.98	55.24	0.00	1438.99	72.15	73.28	24.11	37.34
214	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.57	14.47	58.80	0.00	1403.25	69.55	70.39	24.16	42.59
215	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.64	16.27	67.00	0.00	1675.82	58.85	59.49	24.57	41.26
216	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.53	13.62	54.62	0.00	1394.41	73.77	74.85	23.95	40.97
217	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.43	11.66	39.74	0.00	927.71	79.04	83.27	23.38	34.20
218	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.42	11.43	38.84	0.00	878.12	79.81	84.49	23.36	33.43
219	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.38	11.03	35.98	0.00	836.59	78.77	85.28	23.09	31.31
220	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.42	11.31	38.99	0.00	856.52	80.72	85.10	23.23	32.39

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asy\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°Ch]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
221	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.42	11.22	38.47	0.00	828.49	80.67	85.87	23.24	31.49
222	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.37	10.73	35.23	0.00	798.36	79.99	86.69	22.94	30.19
223	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.43	11.68	39.69	0.00	932.71	78.49	83.21	23.38	31.73
224	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.43	11.62	39.90	0.00	908.22	78.94	83.85	23.42	31.82
225	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.38	11.15	36.44	0.00	850.83	78.31	85.13	23.13	29.79
226	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.42	11.37	39.10	0.00	889.27	80.23	84.95	23.24	31.19
227	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.43	11.47	39.97	0.00	873.64	79.75	85.15	23.32	28.38
228	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.38	10.86	35.87	0.00	814.72	79.38	86.32	22.99	27.70
229	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.22	7.76	15.67	0.00	645.14	89.14	96.07	22.69	36.54
230	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.24	7.83	15.89	0.00	605.93	90.39	96.25	22.91	37.63
231	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.18	7.53	14.55	0.00	609.32	86.50	96.27	22.49	33.31
232	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.22	7.67	15.08	0.00	623.37	89.65	96.62	22.63	34.04
233	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.25	7.90	16.10	0.00	601.80	90.49	96.69	22.91	31.91
234	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.18	7.45	13.99	0.00	580.84	86.61	96.75	22.41	30.95
235	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.22	7.80	15.83	0.00	659.89	88.37	96.01	22.68	34.07
236	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.25	8.00	16.69	0.00	634.95	89.67	95.92	22.98	33.77
237	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.18	7.60	14.85	0.00	624.80	85.72	96.17	22.50	31.68
238	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.21	7.69	15.09	0.00	630.08	88.83	96.54	22.60	31.92
239	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.26	8.12	17.65	0.00	645.53	89.80	96.39	22.99	29.75
240	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.18	7.53	14.34	0.00	593.96	85.61	96.60	22.41	29.15
241	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	3.78	99.86	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.72	27.78
242	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	3.95	99.92	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.64	30.22
243	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	3.78	99.86	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.72	27.78
244	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	3.75	99.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.41	26.42
245	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	3.91	99.92	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.31	29.06
246	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	3.75	99.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.41	26.42
247	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	3.78	99.86	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.75	26.47
248	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	3.95	99.92	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.66	28.53
249	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	3.78	99.86	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.75	26.47
250	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	3.75	99.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.47	25.81
251	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	3.92	99.92	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.37	28.48
252	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	3.75	99.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.47	25.81

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°Ch]	$PI_{H\%}$ [%]	$PI_{U\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
253	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	3.24	99.35	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.14	23.10
254	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	3.37	99.63	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.88	24.94
255	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	3.24	99.35	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.14	23.10
256	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	3.22	99.31	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.90	22.79
257	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	3.35	99.61	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.62	24.60
258	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	3.22	99.31	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.90	22.79
259	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	3.24	99.35	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.16	22.38
260	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	3.38	99.64	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.90	23.84
261	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	3.24	99.35	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.16	22.38
262	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	3.22	99.32	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.94	22.13
263	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	3.36	99.62	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.67	24.45
264	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	3.22	99.32	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.94	22.13
265	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	2.95	97.44	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.24	14.83
266	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	2.95	97.44	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.24	14.83
267	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	2.95	97.44	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.24	14.83
268	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	2.93	97.34	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.00	15.60
269	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	2.93	97.34	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.00	15.60
270	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	2.93	97.34	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.00	15.60
271	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	2.96	97.45	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.26	14.49
272	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	2.96	97.45	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.26	14.49
273	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	2.96	97.45	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.26	14.49
274	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	2.94	97.37	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.05	15.07
275	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	2.94	97.37	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.05	15.07
276	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	2.94	97.37	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.05	15.07
277	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	2.61	93.58	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.71	12.66
278	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	2.61	93.58	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.71	12.66
279	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	2.61	93.58	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.71	12.66
280	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	2.59	93.39	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.50	14.65
281	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	2.59	93.39	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.50	14.65
282	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	2.59	93.39	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.50	14.65
283	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	2.61	93.61	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.73	12.15
284	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	2.61	93.61	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.73	12.15

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°Ch]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RR,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
285	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	2.61	93.61	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.73	12.15
286	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	2.59	93.45	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.54	14.49
287	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	2.59	93.45	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.54	14.49
288	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	2.59	93.45	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.54	14.49

D.1.2. Night Zone

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OH_{OH} [°C/h]	$PI_{I,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{II,\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$Q_{RR,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
1	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.90	24.76	23.98	0.00	180.33	37.97	66.33	23.20	156.73
2	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.86	23.19	22.15	0.00	193.24	39.19	72.15	23.22	155.84
3	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.98	26.40	26.35	0.00	177.61	24.07	63.65	22.76	156.15
4	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.93	25.69	24.68	0.00	174.90	34.93	62.67	23.00	160.74
5	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.89	24.00	22.14	0.00	188.92	36.71	68.76	23.02	159.12
6	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.00	27.27	26.71	0.00	171.68	21.84	60.02	22.57	159.37
7	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.10	31.41	32.22	0.00	191.44	27.62	49.60	22.02	141.70
8	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-1.03	28.76	27.64	0.00	198.10	30.39	54.87	22.20	141.19
9	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.14	32.61	33.40	0.00	189.34	16.67	48.05	21.71	141.01
10	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.16	33.93	34.10	0.00	187.62	23.74	45.49	21.60	143.15
11	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.08	31.00	29.37	0.00	193.59	26.38	49.71	21.80	142.75
12	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.21	35.03	35.57	0.00	184.64	14.79	44.27	21.32	142.24
13	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.61	15.56	16.27	0.00	65.53	50.29	75.11	22.92	155.69
14	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.55	13.73	10.97	0.00	74.44	55.65	81.03	23.08	155.27
15	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.69	16.86	17.95	0.00	65.31	37.08	73.96	22.50	155.44
16	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.63	16.63	16.68	0.00	49.13	48.64	70.65	22.71	158.83
17	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.58	14.63	11.35	0.00	62.96	52.79	77.79	22.88	158.24
18	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.71	17.84	17.70	0.00	48.96	39.53	69.50	22.32	158.17
19	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.80	22.47	26.93	0.00	66.76	41.16	54.45	21.55	139.69
20	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.73	19.46	19.43	0.00	72.16	44.94	62.00	21.86	139.71
21	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.86	23.48	27.88	0.00	66.68	29.53	53.81	21.27	139.18
22	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.88	25.64	29.46	0.00	47.48	36.85	49.89	21.08	141.45
23	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.79	22.29	22.14	0.00	56.57	40.78	54.42	21.42	141.24
24	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.92	26.46	29.89	0.00	47.90	30.48	49.32	20.83	141.34
25	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-1.82	58.68	65.63	0.00	372.50	5.43	23.78	20.28	161.03
26	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-1.79	57.72	65.28	0.00	351.15	11.30	25.71	20.47	160.96
27	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-1.84	59.28	66.69	0.00	372.53	1.47	22.53	20.16	160.96
28	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-1.87	60.31	65.79	0.00	379.05	4.66	21.75	19.97	163.83
29	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-1.84	59.30	65.31	0.00	350.75	10.38	23.53	20.16	163.69
30	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.88	60.78	66.76	0.00	379.02	1.76	20.70	19.87	163.42

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
31	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-2.12	67.64	71.28	0.00	419.01	2.65	15.49	18.35	143.64
32	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-2.08	66.21	70.20	0.00	364.69	7.83	19.14	18.62	143.64
33	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-2.13	67.90	71.83	0.00	418.91	1.46	14.51	18.30	143.64
34	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-2.22	70.10	72.41	0.00	432.59	2.21	12.70	17.75	143.76
35	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-2.17	68.63	71.30	0.00	371.44	7.06	16.79	18.02	143.76
36	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-2.22	70.29	72.92	0.00	432.59	1.37	12.33	17.72	143.95
37	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-1.53	51.35	63.33	0.00	133.50	8.26	29.25	19.81	160.63
38	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-1.51	50.83	63.20	0.00	125.37	14.69	30.15	20.07	160.63
39	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-1.55	51.89	65.70	0.00	133.49	1.25	28.51	19.71	160.45
40	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-1.59	53.53	62.36	0.00	128.10	8.37	27.44	19.49	163.12
41	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-1.56	52.93	61.90	0.00	112.51	15.15	28.18	19.75	163.11
42	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.60	53.92	63.53	0.00	128.10	2.93	26.63	19.41	163.00
43	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.83	61.58	72.76	0.00	153.78	2.37	18.08	17.78	142.27
44	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-1.80	60.60	71.13	0.00	123.49	10.48	20.15	18.10	142.26
45	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.84	61.82	74.29	0.00	153.97	0.64	17.90	17.73	142.26
46	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.95	64.92	73.63	0.00	160.00	1.38	15.35	17.14	142.11
47	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.91	63.86	71.67	0.00	118.37	9.59	17.34	17.46	142.18
48	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.95	65.10	74.09	0.00	159.99	0.64	15.05	17.10	142.09
49	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.95	27.29	30.13	0.00	209.34	53.52	72.61	22.21	134.22
50	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.93	26.47	29.11	0.00	200.00	55.95	73.94	22.24	133.90
51	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-1.04	28.83	30.52	0.00	209.22	30.52	71.40	21.63	133.25
52	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.97	27.77	30.46	0.00	208.02	49.48	71.67	22.05	135.83
53	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.93	26.76	29.89	0.00	196.68	53.76	72.94	22.10	135.63
54	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.05	29.16	31.25	0.00	207.82	30.06	70.27	21.52	135.80
55	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.04	29.29	31.69	0.00	216.83	39.72	68.48	21.49	119.06
56	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.99	27.90	30.73	0.00	206.68	46.13	71.14	21.67	118.99
57	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.10	30.57	32.16	0.00	216.68	22.84	67.19	21.05	118.22
58	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.08	30.30	32.55	0.00	216.94	33.19	65.80	21.17	120.18
59	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.02	28.72	32.13	0.00	203.06	41.77	69.65	21.39	119.24
60	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.13	31.47	33.46	0.00	216.79	20.74	64.31	20.79	119.35
61	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.66	20.19	22.29	0.00	97.78	67.50	79.60	22.19	134.79
62	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.64	19.47	20.40	0.00	101.24	71.04	81.65	22.38	134.70

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
63	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.75	21.34	23.66	0.00	97.78	42.13	79.18	21.61	134.45
64	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.66	20.40	22.71	0.00	88.94	66.80	79.21	21.98	136.61
65	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.63	19.58	20.82	0.00	94.45	69.66	80.85	22.21	135.75
66	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.74	21.36	23.57	0.00	88.70	49.66	78.48	21.49	135.38
67	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.74	21.85	23.38	0.00	101.70	56.43	75.55	21.29	118.22
68	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.69	20.68	21.46	0.00	100.37	63.11	78.08	21.71	118.10
69	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.81	22.80	24.24	0.00	101.69	34.21	74.79	20.90	117.94
70	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.77	22.67	23.90	0.00	96.42	48.48	72.41	20.91	119.40
71	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.71	21.23	22.10	0.00	91.74	59.45	75.98	21.38	119.24
72	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.83	23.49	23.81	0.00	96.42	36.04	70.79	20.60	118.53
73	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-1.36	38.39	39.51	0.00	364.52	6.21	41.41	21.11	138.02
74	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-1.26	35.20	36.43	0.00	320.10	19.05	48.64	21.88	138.37
75	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-1.39	39.20	42.03	0.00	364.51	1.62	38.24	20.89	137.71
76	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-1.39	39.47	38.66	0.00	374.35	5.53	37.24	20.87	139.57
77	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-1.29	36.19	36.73	0.00	318.78	17.34	45.84	21.60	139.64
78	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.42	40.27	42.12	0.00	374.33	2.43	32.81	20.66	139.57
79	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.52	44.14	45.99	0.00	400.42	3.46	22.53	19.83	120.81
80	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-1.41	40.28	42.02	0.00	328.71	12.25	37.00	20.68	121.09
81	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.54	44.73	48.06	0.00	400.41	1.03	20.93	19.69	120.53
82	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.58	46.26	47.34	0.00	414.00	2.46	19.13	19.40	119.62
83	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.46	42.32	43.22	0.00	330.16	9.78	32.96	20.21	119.91
84	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.59	46.76	49.77	0.00	413.99	1.10	17.44	19.28	119.64
85	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-1.06	29.77	36.16	0.00	154.04	13.69	51.22	20.86	137.77
86	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.97	27.25	31.49	0.00	131.28	27.71	56.86	21.81	137.95
87	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-1.09	30.57	39.30	0.00	154.04	2.87	47.07	20.67	137.62
88	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-1.09	30.80	36.04	0.00	155.77	13.11	46.95	20.63	138.62
89	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.99	28.19	31.10	0.00	125.80	27.04	54.70	21.55	138.65
90	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.12	31.54	37.68	0.00	155.76	5.95	42.74	20.46	138.57
91	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.23	35.77	47.41	0.00	171.27	6.89	28.75	19.48	119.96
92	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-1.12	32.40	38.78	0.00	129.82	20.27	44.97	20.49	120.25
93	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.25	36.32	49.60	0.00	171.27	2.29	27.44	19.37	119.64
94	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.30	38.25	48.45	0.00	177.80	4.45	25.27	19.05	118.56

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
95	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.18	34.75	39.45	0.00	125.50	18.35	38.26	20.00	118.81
96	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.31	38.77	49.57	0.00	177.79	2.29	23.05	18.95	118.41
97	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.11	9.85	39.12	0.00	327.44	80.80	90.64	22.97	71.00
98	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.08	9.88	42.67	0.00	381.21	77.87	87.82	22.97	76.11
99	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.21	10.50	33.87	0.00	312.49	63.19	89.77	22.29	70.23
100	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.11	9.90	39.97	0.00	312.63	80.59	90.45	23.00	71.25
101	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.08	9.89	42.67	0.00	373.11	78.52	88.13	22.97	77.20
102	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.21	10.49	32.30	0.00	293.54	63.98	89.75	22.29	70.81
103	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.14	10.21	40.04	0.00	346.36	77.67	90.01	22.81	63.25
104	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.09	10.10	44.29	0.00	381.05	76.42	87.94	22.87	68.36
105	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.22	10.82	35.08	0.00	326.27	60.39	89.14	22.20	62.71
106	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.14	10.39	41.19	0.00	331.47	74.53	89.79	22.76	63.65
107	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.09	10.16	45.23	0.00	369.32	77.16	88.07	22.85	69.22
108	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.23	10.92	34.40	0.00	316.16	59.98	88.79	22.17	62.60
109	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.04	7.57	10.08	0.00	115.06	92.90	95.59	22.71	71.40
110	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.04	7.30	12.44	0.00	111.57	93.15	96.09	22.64	74.41
111	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.15	7.74	8.82	0.00	103.70	79.12	95.17	21.95	69.57
112	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.00	7.62	8.78	0.00	101.16	93.40	95.67	22.69	70.19
113	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.01	7.35	12.48	0.00	95.50	93.61	96.05	22.65	75.80
114	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.13	7.64	8.57	0.00	88.20	84.71	95.25	21.94	69.66
115	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.05	7.63	10.38	0.00	122.69	92.44	95.46	22.41	63.83
116	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.04	7.41	13.28	0.00	109.56	92.77	95.97	22.53	69.19
117	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.15	7.82	8.82	0.00	112.70	77.90	95.04	21.79	62.90
118	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.03	7.69	8.91	0.00	111.78	90.50	95.59	22.29	62.54
119	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.00	7.48	13.24	0.00	91.95	93.19	95.80	22.49	69.09
120	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.14	7.78	8.61	0.00	100.63	80.59	95.04	21.70	61.54
121	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.44	12.85	17.48	0.00	440.76	35.94	86.09	22.32	73.70
122	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.36	10.96	16.48	0.00	368.51	56.37	89.05	22.89	83.30
123	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.50	13.90	16.33	0.00	437.27	24.33	83.25	21.82	72.95
124	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.46	13.25	17.82	0.00	450.73	35.76	83.25	22.20	73.75
125	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.37	11.26	17.48	0.00	374.75	55.33	87.54	22.75	84.04
126	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.52	14.26	16.46	0.00	446.97	25.67	80.46	21.72	72.94

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
127	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.51	14.62	18.78	0.00	493.41	29.70	77.80	21.74	65.47
128	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.40	11.80	18.20	0.00	384.28	51.60	86.16	22.58	75.32
129	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.56	15.43	17.86	0.00	490.65	22.73	73.78	21.39	65.04
130	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.54	15.31	19.05	0.00	507.73	27.54	71.72	21.52	64.99
131	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.42	12.43	19.18	0.00	399.62	47.44	82.52	22.34	74.70
132	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.58	16.10	18.31	0.00	504.05	22.82	67.28	21.20	64.71
133	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.27	8.72	6.26	0.00	174.49	59.33	93.28	22.16	75.24
134	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.22	7.92	5.88	0.00	151.03	79.45	95.42	23.06	84.75
135	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.36	9.60	6.34	0.00	174.38	30.59	92.02	21.67	74.28
136	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.27	8.81	6.22	0.00	178.01	55.59	92.48	22.05	75.68
137	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.19	7.77	5.97	0.00	133.97	84.33	95.17	22.96	85.23
138	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.35	9.58	6.30	0.00	177.84	37.06	90.21	21.58	73.64
139	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.35	9.90	6.30	0.00	201.29	42.18	85.88	21.48	66.74
140	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.24	8.26	5.97	0.00	144.72	72.77	93.87	22.65	75.21
141	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.41	10.58	6.47	0.00	201.21	28.61	83.11	21.15	66.30
142	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.37	10.38	6.26	0.00	215.13	37.02	81.97	21.28	65.80
143	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.23	8.44	5.97	0.00	141.79	69.24	93.11	22.45	74.23
144	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.43	11.00	6.34	0.00	214.87	29.96	78.74	20.96	65.62
145	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.14	10.65	27.64	0.00	184.24	79.18	86.16	22.75	75.82
146	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.13	10.75	32.04	0.00	216.10	74.61	84.75	22.66	81.13
147	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.25	11.58	25.18	0.00	178.97	55.62	85.71	22.08	75.68
148	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.14	10.60	27.32	0.00	183.17	79.42	86.31	22.76	77.45
149	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.13	10.77	30.81	0.00	211.60	74.78	84.80	22.66	81.14
150	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.24	11.55	23.81	0.00	177.60	57.33	85.69	22.08	75.78
151	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.17	10.92	28.39	0.00	192.97	76.82	85.77	22.61	68.04
152	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.14	10.96	32.45	0.00	216.96	73.10	84.56	22.58	71.75
153	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.26	11.85	25.71	0.00	188.25	53.41	85.26	21.99	66.79
154	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.17	11.01	28.34	0.00	191.75	75.19	85.82	22.59	68.17
155	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.14	11.01	31.75	0.00	212.90	73.42	84.71	22.57	71.62
156	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.26	11.92	24.77	0.00	186.97	53.35	85.10	21.97	66.94
157	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.05	6.88	9.66	0.00	85.33	95.88	96.09	22.52	75.00
158	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.05	6.96	10.59	0.00	86.63	94.33	95.21	22.41	80.29

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
159	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.16	7.40	9.62	0.00	86.84	75.08	96.39	21.76	73.02
160	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.02	6.82	9.62	0.00	71.81	95.76	96.26	22.47	74.60
161	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.04	6.90	10.50	0.00	82.30	94.54	95.29	22.36	78.80
162	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.14	7.23	9.37	0.00	73.38	82.86	96.47	21.75	72.55
163	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.06	6.96	9.66	0.00	83.29	94.62	96.09	22.24	66.92
164	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.05	6.98	10.63	0.00	85.51	94.29	95.21	22.32	71.63
165	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.16	7.46	9.62	0.00	85.08	73.78	96.34	21.63	66.52
166	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.04	6.91	9.62	0.00	74.20	93.95	96.18	22.10	66.37
167	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.03	6.91	10.55	0.00	79.67	94.37	95.25	22.24	70.76
168	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.15	7.31	9.62	0.00	75.80	79.37	96.47	21.54	65.45
169	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.44	13.09	14.91	0.00	352.83	28.41	87.35	22.36	76.60
170	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.35	11.10	15.31	0.00	316.22	59.79	89.64	23.02	84.11
171	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.51	14.36	15.71	0.00	352.37	14.35	85.88	21.84	75.43
172	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.46	13.53	14.93	0.00	363.01	25.69	86.60	22.19	76.51
173	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.35	11.25	15.31	0.00	312.27	61.03	88.79	22.90	84.91
174	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.52	14.67	15.44	0.00	362.77	14.69	84.35	21.72	75.78
175	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.52	14.95	15.20	0.00	394.93	18.63	82.50	21.73	67.54
176	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.37	11.67	15.71	0.00	319.92	55.11	88.28	22.79	75.93
177	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.56	15.79	16.12	0.00	394.53	13.69	79.54	21.43	67.57
178	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.55	15.64	15.31	0.00	407.57	17.22	78.01	21.47	66.80
179	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.39	12.00	15.88	0.00	316.46	50.73	87.14	22.59	76.68
180	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.59	16.45	15.88	0.00	407.22	13.84	74.63	21.21	66.61
181	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.25	7.83	4.58	0.00	161.05	56.76	97.10	22.11	78.98
182	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.18	7.10	4.50	0.00	137.84	85.38	97.31	23.20	85.92
183	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.34	8.91	4.54	0.00	160.35	16.09	96.43	21.65	76.55
184	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.26	7.95	3.78	0.00	164.53	51.81	96.81	21.96	77.87
185	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.15	6.90	3.66	0.00	128.04	92.98	97.31	23.07	87.04
186	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.33	8.81	3.49	0.00	163.79	19.75	96.18	21.54	77.03
187	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.32	8.84	4.62	0.00	181.99	32.61	95.46	21.44	69.87
188	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.18	7.12	4.54	0.00	135.19	86.89	97.31	22.90	77.31
189	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.37	9.55	4.66	0.00	181.41	16.01	94.87	21.15	68.83
190	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.35	9.29	3.87	0.00	191.36	28.40	93.36	21.20	68.88

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
191	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.17	7.09	3.82	0.00	124.46	84.79	97.31	22.65	78.20
192	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.39	9.88	3.57	0.00	190.79	17.98	90.71	20.94	68.66
193	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.47	13.43	80.23	0.00	391.60	69.94	71.48	24.58	36.41
194	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.56	15.67	84.22	0.00	478.20	58.35	59.58	25.03	37.69
195	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.43	13.01	78.31	0.00	377.50	71.36	73.70	24.27	36.87
196	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.47	13.37	80.73	0.00	391.43	70.48	71.98	24.60	36.15
197	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.56	15.63	84.11	0.00	468.20	58.58	59.81	25.06	38.44
198	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.43	12.93	77.89	0.00	373.48	72.13	74.51	24.29	35.76
199	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.46	13.42	80.54	0.00	394.06	70.13	71.75	24.56	33.68
200	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.55	15.63	84.07	0.00	477.68	58.62	59.88	25.00	36.41
201	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.43	13.02	78.46	0.00	381.06	71.71	73.82	24.28	34.01
202	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.47	13.35	80.84	0.00	392.81	70.56	72.21	24.58	33.85
203	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.55	15.54	83.99	0.00	465.89	58.96	60.23	25.01	36.46
204	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.43	12.92	78.04	0.00	375.52	72.40	74.51	24.29	33.81
205	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.37	8.99	65.35	0.00	89.71	93.68	93.86	23.14	37.51
206	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.35	8.90	75.00	0.00	83.78	91.32	91.32	22.85	39.48
207	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.27	7.95	55.61	0.00	65.45	94.91	95.35	22.47	37.54
208	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.38	9.03	62.19	0.00	87.11	94.04	94.12	23.16	35.73
209	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.35	8.85	74.91	0.00	77.80	91.67	91.67	22.87	38.19
210	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.28	7.93	53.60	0.00	60.97	95.09	95.44	22.49	35.35
211	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.36	8.90	65.88	0.00	89.20	93.86	94.04	23.03	34.28
212	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.36	8.99	75.61	0.00	85.07	91.23	91.23	22.87	36.30
213	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.28	8.02	57.63	0.00	74.05	94.74	95.26	22.46	33.50
214	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.37	8.94	64.56	0.00	87.60	93.95	94.12	23.03	31.53
215	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.36	8.95	76.05	0.00	78.23	91.23	91.32	22.87	33.63
216	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.29	8.01	55.70	0.00	70.98	94.74	95.35	22.48	32.06
217	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.05	7.89	40.54	0.00	326.91	73.36	97.31	22.40	37.75
218	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.07	7.75	39.92	0.00	317.78	71.79	97.35	22.23	41.16
219	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.11	8.33	36.58	0.00	323.96	60.81	96.89	21.87	35.55
220	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.05	7.85	40.04	0.00	323.46	73.78	97.54	22.40	35.40
221	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.06	7.76	39.50	0.00	314.52	72.86	97.35	22.29	39.57
222	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.11	8.30	35.82	0.00	322.68	61.84	96.97	21.88	32.93

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
223	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.07	8.11	40.54	0.00	342.82	68.41	97.08	22.24	34.85
224	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.07	7.86	41.07	0.00	322.63	70.40	97.12	22.23	39.16
225	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.12	8.51	36.89	0.00	340.55	59.85	96.62	21.81	31.66
226	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.07	8.12	39.92	0.00	345.38	68.41	97.08	22.20	32.30
227	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.07	7.89	41.07	0.00	319.64	72.09	97.27	22.26	36.42
228	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.12	8.51	36.62	0.00	343.30	60.92	96.55	21.79	29.97
229	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.04	5.96	14.12	0.00	102.57	93.60	100.00	21.97	41.83
230	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.03	5.86	13.42	0.00	100.81	98.95	100.00	22.14	49.25
231	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.05	6.22	12.63	0.00	100.95	66.32	100.00	21.43	40.63
232	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.05	5.93	12.89	0.00	98.86	93.25	100.00	21.95	38.39
233	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.07	5.85	13.16	0.00	85.66	99.82	100.00	22.22	45.68
234	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.04	6.13	11.93	0.00	97.30	72.98	100.00	21.41	37.89
235	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.02	6.04	14.21	0.00	109.65	88.60	100.00	21.74	37.71
236	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.04	5.87	14.47	0.00	96.81	99.47	100.00	22.12	46.22
237	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.05	6.29	12.81	0.00	108.43	64.47	99.91	21.29	37.61
238	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.02	6.07	13.07	0.00	110.19	87.54	100.00	21.63	34.21
239	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.07	5.85	14.04	0.00	84.02	99.39	100.00	22.13	41.02
240	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.05	6.23	12.54	0.00	109.16	71.75	99.91	21.23	34.20
241	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	3.57	99.81	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.05	29.72
242	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	3.72	99.91	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.85	31.16
243	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	3.57	99.81	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.05	29.72
244	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	3.57	99.81	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.07	28.87
245	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	3.72	99.90	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.88	30.47
246	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	3.57	99.81	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.07	28.87
247	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	3.57	99.81	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.05	28.14
248	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	3.72	99.90	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.85	29.50
249	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	3.57	99.81	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.05	28.14
250	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	3.57	99.81	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.06	27.85
251	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	3.72	99.90	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.86	28.87
252	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	3.57	99.81	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.06	27.85
253	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	3.04	98.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.83	22.55
254	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	3.16	99.30	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.44	23.60

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
255	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	3.04	98.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.83	22.55
256	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	3.04	98.82	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.83	23.07
257	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	3.15	99.29	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.45	24.11
258	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	3.04	98.82	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.83	23.07
259	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	3.05	98.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.83	21.61
260	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	3.16	99.31	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.44	22.64
261	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	3.05	98.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.83	21.61
262	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	3.04	98.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.83	22.73
263	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	3.16	99.31	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.44	23.37
264	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	3.04	98.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.83	22.73
265	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	2.88	97.08	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.34	21.34
266	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	2.88	97.08	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.34	21.34
267	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	2.88	97.08	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.34	21.34
268	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	2.87	97.02	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.33	21.13
269	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	2.87	97.02	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.33	21.13
270	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	2.87	97.02	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.33	21.13
271	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	2.88	97.06	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.33	20.36
272	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	2.88	97.06	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.33	20.36
273	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	2.88	97.06	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.33	20.36
274	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	2.87	97.01	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.32	20.29
275	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	2.87	97.01	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.32	20.29
276	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	2.87	97.01	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.32	20.29
277	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	2.60	93.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.55	17.21
278	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	2.60	93.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.55	17.21
279	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	2.60	93.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.55	17.21
280	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	2.59	93.66	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.49	18.40
281	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	2.59	93.66	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.49	18.40
282	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	2.59	93.66	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.49	18.40
283	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	2.60	93.88	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.55	16.23
284	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	2.60	93.88	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.55	16.23
285	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	2.60	93.88	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.55	16.23
286	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	2.59	93.73	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.50	17.24

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{L,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{U,\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RR,max,H}$ [W/m ²]
287	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	2.59	93.73	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.50	17.24
288	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	2.59	93.73	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.50	17.24

D.1.3. Aggregated

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out, \%}$ [%]	$PD_{avg, \%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{I, \%}$ [%]	$PI_{II, \%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{RE, max, H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{HR, F}$ [kW/h/m ²]	E_H [kWh/h]	SCOP [-]	$Q_{unmet, \%H}$ [%]
1	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.63	18.63	21.83	0.00	472.04	56.90	78.04	23.36	150.97	226.92	19240.77	2.36	-0.03
2	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.59	17.61	19.83	0.00	505.13	59.55	81.52	23.40	149.01	213.04	17954.25	2.39	-0.06
3	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.69	19.58	23.83	0.00	403.52	48.89	76.64	23.04	149.74	222.63	18622.15	2.40	-0.08
4	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.64	19.10	22.32	0.00	497.08	55.21	76.21	23.27	154.19	211.16	18349.33	2.30	-0.04
5	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.60	18.01	19.82	0.00	507.67	58.22	79.80	23.31	152.40	198.27	17107.40	2.34	-0.07
6	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.69	20.02	24.22	0.00	416.70	47.56	74.88	22.95	153.17	207.35	17867.84	2.33	-0.08
7	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.76	22.62	29.92	0.00	491.83	47.81	68.13	22.55	136.94	216.39	18855.99	2.30	-0.04
8	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.70	20.87	24.97	0.00	525.75	51.63	71.81	22.71	135.62	203.48	17672.51	2.32	-0.05
9	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.80	23.31	31.08	0.00	432.70	41.46	67.30	22.32	136.37	213.42	18340.54	2.34	-0.06
10	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.79	24.05	31.87	0.00	517.45	44.65	65.55	22.31	139.12	201.81	17961.52	2.24	-0.05
11	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.73	22.11	26.72	0.00	539.57	48.82	68.96	22.49	138.25	190.28	16867.55	2.27	-0.06
12	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.83	24.68	33.27	0.00	448.70	39.35	64.94	22.09	138.51	199.50	17547.36	2.28	-0.06
13	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.54	14.62	22.23	0.00	266.65	58.86	81.09	23.12	150.59	256.27	20961.20	2.42	-0.03
14	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.49	13.27	17.17	0.00	284.45	63.99	85.26	23.26	149.28	242.60	19889.66	2.43	-0.04
15	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.60	15.48	24.28	0.00	248.19	50.99	80.36	22.84	149.82	252.44	20374.36	2.46	-0.05
16	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.55	15.17	22.74	0.00	264.91	57.72	78.81	23.02	153.95	237.49	20069.09	2.34	-0.04
17	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.50	13.71	17.50	0.00	287.73	62.42	83.63	23.17	152.21	225.24	19067.46	2.35	-0.05
18	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.61	15.96	24.39	0.00	240.77	51.92	78.07	22.75	153.04	234.42	19650.30	2.37	-0.06
19	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.69	19.20	32.59	0.00	273.91	49.31	67.01	22.16	136.01	243.69	20550.11	2.35	-0.04
20	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.61	16.94	25.77	0.00	291.88	54.49	73.39	22.43	135.42	231.57	19582.01	2.35	-0.05
21	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.73	19.84	33.89	0.00	254.77	42.51	66.56	21.97	135.58	241.20	20116.37	2.38	-0.05
22	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.73	21.05	35.01	0.00	275.43	45.92	63.92	21.87	137.67	226.42	19565.76	2.29	-0.05
23	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.65	18.57	28.28	0.00	301.75	51.15	68.81	22.16	137.12	215.74	18671.77	2.29	-0.05
24	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.76	21.58	36.00	0.00	253.14	41.69	63.56	21.70	137.61	224.55	19222.48	2.31	-0.05
25	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-1.36	42.53	63.80	0.00	422.82	19.62	38.24	21.09	154.36	350.44	24671.07	2.79	0.02
26	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-1.35	42.00	63.38	0.00	410.04	22.81	39.24	21.22	154.27	352.30	24648.38	2.80	0.02
27	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-1.38	42.92	64.87	0.00	419.27	16.89	37.53	21.01	154.25	348.49	24332.92	2.81	0.02
28	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-1.38	43.30	63.92	0.00	413.90	19.14	37.13	20.93	157.34	322.13	23889.51	2.64	0.00
29	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-1.36	42.76	63.44	0.00	397.54	22.28	38.04	21.06	156.68	324.17	23877.31	2.66	0.00
30	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.40	43.62	64.90	0.00	409.56	17.10	36.52	20.86	156.60	320.45	23639.61	2.66	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{lr\%}$ [%]	$PI_{ll\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF,max,H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{H,RF}$ [kW/h/m ²]	E_H [kWh]	SCOP [-]	$Q_{summer,H}$ [%]
31	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.58	49.64	69.48	0.00	449.59	15.34	30.60	19.66	138.64	325.33	23986.30	2.66	0.00
32	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-1.56	48.84	68.48	0.00	416.46	18.38	32.47	19.84	138.54	328.03	24082.97	2.67	0.00
33	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.59	49.83	70.08	0.00	446.50	14.28	30.04	19.62	138.63	324.21	23857.29	2.66	0.00
34	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.64	51.41	70.57	0.00	448.71	14.65	28.51	19.27	139.36	298.80	23105.19	2.53	-0.02
35	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.61	50.59	69.63	0.00	415.42	17.51	30.59	19.44	139.19	301.90	23220.30	2.54	-0.02
36	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.65	51.55	71.13	0.00	445.28	13.86	28.30	19.23	139.28	297.96	23021.24	2.53	-0.02
37	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-1.29	41.55	66.26	0.00	388.01	18.08	37.26	20.70	153.58	373.85	25560.21	2.85	0.03
38	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-1.28	41.20	65.70	0.00	367.12	21.77	37.79	20.87	153.58	376.25	25652.62	2.86	0.03
39	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-1.31	41.89	68.10	0.00	386.65	14.03	36.83	20.64	153.46	372.27	25271.25	2.87	0.04
40	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-1.32	42.59	65.87	0.00	369.22	18.10	36.29	20.54	156.85	343.28	24722.83	2.71	0.01
41	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-1.30	42.20	65.10	0.00	342.91	21.97	36.72	20.71	156.53	345.79	24806.55	2.71	0.01
42	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.33	42.87	67.13	0.00	367.73	14.75	35.82	20.48	156.53	341.80	24553.71	2.71	0.01
43	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.52	49.75	74.12	0.00	407.78	12.50	28.70	19.19	137.45	346.70	24756.91	2.73	0.01
44	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-1.50	49.13	72.42	0.00	365.82	17.43	29.87	19.40	137.33	349.93	24913.51	2.73	0.01
45	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.53	49.93	75.41	0.00	407.36	11.12	28.57	19.15	137.30	345.83	24713.39	2.73	0.01
46	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.59	52.04	75.30	0.00	395.84	11.26	26.65	18.75	138.15	317.94	23772.07	2.60	-0.02
47	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.57	51.36	73.34	0.00	348.15	16.34	27.85	18.97	138.03	321.55	23935.26	2.61	-0.02
48	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.60	52.17	75.91	0.00	394.76	10.50	26.47	18.73	138.04	317.25	23717.89	2.60	-0.02
49	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.75	24.36	28.68	0.00	503.17	62.34	75.39	22.13	132.29	157.76	9890.07	3.21	0.10
50	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.73	23.73	27.67	0.00	519.34	64.02	76.54	22.20	132.02	155.90	9285.75	3.37	0.11
51	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.82	25.23	29.03	0.00	448.52	49.08	74.64	21.69	131.51	152.50	9113.50	3.38	0.10
52	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.76	24.63	28.99	0.00	510.38	60.16	74.82	22.06	133.82	146.55	9475.89	3.11	0.08
53	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.73	23.91	28.22	0.00	525.21	62.79	75.87	22.13	133.35	144.81	9017.15	3.22	0.08
54	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.82	25.43	29.53	0.00	451.53	48.76	74.00	21.64	133.53	141.91	8859.76	3.23	0.08
55	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.81	25.62	30.23	0.00	522.04	54.18	72.97	21.63	116.57	147.83	9720.40	3.06	0.07
56	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.77	24.69	29.21	0.00	546.33	58.15	74.70	21.80	116.42	145.69	9257.44	3.17	0.07
57	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.86	26.34	30.52	0.00	470.98	44.26	72.22	21.29	116.11	143.38	9091.75	3.18	0.07
58	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.83	26.22	30.89	0.00	529.74	50.55	71.49	21.43	117.77	137.31	9304.45	2.96	0.04
59	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.78	25.19	30.27	0.00	552.91	55.62	73.84	21.62	116.92	135.81	8964.37	3.04	0.04
60	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.88	26.89	31.53	0.00	479.28	42.97	70.65	21.14	117.11	133.71	8798.88	3.06	0.04
61	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.65	20.84	24.28	0.00	394.80	68.43	78.98	22.03	132.46	179.81	11062.35	3.22	0.09
62	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.63	20.21	22.47	0.00	369.38	71.39	80.43	22.23	132.38	178.15	10589.56	3.32	0.10

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{lr\%}$ [%]	$PI_{ll\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF,max,H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{H,RF}$ [kW/h/m ²]	E_H [kWh]	SCOP [-]	$Q_{summer,H}$ [%]
63	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.72	21.58	25.66	0.00	380.35	54.15	78.65	21.64	131.92	174.94	10315.45	3.37	0.10
64	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.65	20.99	24.78	0.00	382.40	67.78	78.69	21.93	133.93	166.57	10555.58	3.13	0.07
65	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.62	20.30	22.97	0.00	365.03	70.38	79.96	22.15	133.42	165.17	10191.22	3.20	0.07
66	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.71	21.62	25.93	0.00	367.39	57.62	78.18	21.60	133.06	162.38	9979.36	3.23	0.07
67	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.71	22.00	25.92	0.00	404.77	61.39	76.35	21.42	116.15	168.63	10771.15	3.10	0.06
68	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.66	21.07	23.84	0.00	380.78	66.34	78.13	21.77	115.99	167.14	10455.70	3.16	0.06
69	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.76	22.61	26.95	0.00	390.09	48.69	75.81	21.15	115.79	164.71	10204.69	3.21	0.06
70	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.72	22.54	26.66	0.00	400.81	56.71	74.49	21.20	116.89	156.29	10239.04	3.02	0.04
71	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.67	21.46	24.67	0.00	378.04	63.78	76.78	21.57	117.02	155.52	10027.52	3.06	0.04
72	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.77	23.07	27.18	0.00	385.17	48.94	73.52	20.98	116.28	153.11	9785.24	3.10	0.04
73	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-1.07	30.98	37.72	0.00	537.17	27.78	57.79	21.41	134.58	232.48	14167.48	3.23	0.09
74	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-1.00	29.00	34.75	0.00	481.91	36.44	61.91	21.98	134.79	242.17	14654.04	3.23	0.09
75	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-1.10	31.54	40.12	0.00	531.81	23.66	56.07	21.24	134.27	228.48	13609.27	3.30	0.10
76	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-1.08	31.52	37.10	0.00	537.61	27.82	55.63	21.30	136.26	213.97	13483.70	3.12	0.07
77	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-1.01	29.51	35.00	0.00	471.49	35.87	60.46	21.86	136.26	223.36	13993.52	3.11	0.07
78	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.11	32.08	40.11	0.00	531.08	24.37	53.27	21.13	135.94	210.47	13053.67	3.17	0.07
79	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.18	34.49	44.22	0.00	561.71	22.82	46.24	20.50	117.66	214.83	13562.07	3.11	0.06
80	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-1.09	32.10	40.14	0.00	488.99	30.52	54.32	21.14	117.94	225.03	14173.88	3.10	0.06
81	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.20	34.92	46.44	0.00	556.62	20.04	45.35	20.38	117.47	212.15	13287.47	3.14	0.06
82	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.21	35.71	45.54	0.00	565.04	21.92	44.03	20.24	117.32	197.34	12648.96	3.06	0.04
83	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.12	33.29	41.35	0.00	480.92	28.87	51.72	20.85	117.57	207.66	13294.98	3.04	0.04
84	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.23	36.09	47.88	0.00	558.97	19.84	43.10	20.13	117.17	195.17	12440.25	3.08	0.04
85	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.96	27.18	38.89	0.00	523.11	28.69	61.09	21.23	134.17	252.88	15106.65	3.26	0.09
86	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.88	25.39	34.09	0.00	442.71	39.37	64.64	21.92	134.36	263.48	15782.89	3.22	0.09
87	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.99	27.75	41.90	0.00	522.47	20.94	58.81	21.09	134.09	248.73	14558.20	3.33	0.10
88	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.97	27.71	38.84	0.00	515.91	28.35	58.82	21.11	135.21	232.16	14247.99	3.17	0.07
89	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.89	25.90	33.99	0.00	420.08	38.98	63.48	21.79	135.23	242.63	14886.70	3.14	0.07
90	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-1.00	28.25	41.16	0.00	515.18	22.66	56.51	20.99	135.16	228.54	13901.14	3.20	0.07
91	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-1.08	31.06	49.16	0.00	539.88	20.77	46.93	20.23	117.17	233.19	14321.61	3.16	0.06
92	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.99	28.73	41.25	0.00	433.83	32.55	56.31	20.98	117.33	244.93	15086.71	3.13	0.06
93	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-1.10	31.46	51.34	0.00	539.28	17.26	46.09	20.15	116.97	230.77	14088.21	3.18	0.06
94	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-1.12	32.52	50.69	0.00	539.34	18.92	44.35	19.95	116.39	213.61	13373.95	3.10	0.04

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	PMV_{out} [%]	PD_{asym} [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	PI_{in} [%]	PI_{in} [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF,max,H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{H,RF}$ [kW/h/m ²]	E_H [kWh]	SCOP [-]	$Q_{summer,H}$ [%]
95	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-1.03	30.11	42.34	0.00	419.90	31.07	52.09	20.67	116.67	225.25	14150.59	3.06	0.04
96	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-1.13	32.90	52.13	0.00	538.85	16.85	43.11	19.88	116.26	211.75	13196.48	3.11	0.04
97	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.09	10.78	39.61	0.00	1018.70	78.30	85.29	23.23	69.76	36.68	1514.77	4.07	0.00
98	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.13	11.37	43.63	0.00	1157.38	73.98	80.92	23.37	74.80	35.71	1328.57	4.73	0.00
99	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.00	10.65	32.99	0.00	882.20	70.19	86.48	22.65	68.97	33.42	1199.96	4.67	0.00
100	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.09	10.71	40.10	0.00	1008.48	78.94	85.96	23.22	69.92	35.11	1456.56	4.05	0.00
101	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.13	11.20	43.49	0.00	1122.59	74.83	81.84	23.30	75.27	33.82	1288.68	4.59	0.00
102	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.00	10.50	31.30	0.00	842.94	71.17	87.42	22.59	68.96	31.94	1163.95	4.57	0.00
103	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.08	11.03	40.64	0.00	1066.49	76.34	84.82	23.14	62.41	35.41	1485.51	4.02	0.00
104	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.13	11.56	45.24	0.00	1181.62	72.92	80.80	23.32	66.73	33.87	1314.58	4.57	0.00
105	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.00	10.90	34.16	0.00	913.72	68.32	85.96	22.62	61.52	32.38	1197.04	4.57	0.00
106	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.07	11.05	41.30	0.00	1040.13	75.44	85.31	23.08	61.91	33.81	1416.02	4.01	0.00
107	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.13	11.49	45.99	0.00	1165.39	73.53	81.44	23.26	66.85	32.71	1285.53	4.48	0.00
108	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.00	10.85	33.35	0.00	890.50	68.70	86.61	22.57	61.11	31.18	1177.50	4.46	0.00
109	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.02	8.03	12.14	0.00	555.59	90.62	94.42	22.72	69.02	51.91	2017.88	4.19	0.00
110	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.04	7.99	14.61	0.00	624.09	90.42	94.19	22.85	72.92	51.00	1896.25	4.49	0.00
111	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.07	7.98	10.44	0.00	477.61	82.62	94.42	22.20	68.19	48.98	1747.10	4.55	0.00
112	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.04	8.06	11.36	0.00	542.00	90.78	94.73	22.70	68.60	48.96	1906.22	4.18	0.00
113	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.06	8.06	14.90	0.00	633.69	90.59	94.32	22.86	73.98	48.54	1865.86	4.31	0.00
114	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.05	7.94	10.22	0.00	464.35	85.36	94.65	22.20	67.94	46.70	1699.18	4.47	0.00
115	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.01	8.12	12.61	0.00	578.91	89.89	94.28	22.56	61.78	49.93	1948.21	4.18	0.00
116	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.05	8.14	15.72	0.00	655.23	90.00	93.99	22.81	66.71	49.03	1858.43	4.42	0.00
117	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.06	8.10	10.77	0.00	507.33	81.70	94.26	22.14	61.05	47.42	1705.99	4.54	0.00
118	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.02	8.16	11.72	0.00	570.24	88.91	94.60	22.48	60.86	47.17	1846.27	4.15	0.00
119	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.07	8.25	16.12	0.00	679.25	89.92	94.08	22.79	66.46	47.34	1828.11	4.32	0.00
120	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.05	8.10	10.63	0.00	503.03	82.72	94.40	22.08	59.96	45.33	1664.80	4.44	0.00
121	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.22	10.68	15.74	0.00	660.02	58.66	89.47	22.43	69.87	81.53	3182.54	4.17	0.00
122	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.17	9.62	14.90	0.00	607.49	69.83	91.39	22.87	77.98	87.75	3430.25	4.21	0.00
123	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.28	11.17	14.52	0.00	610.83	51.00	88.11	22.04	69.08	77.09	2792.20	4.44	0.00
124	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.22	10.90	15.92	0.00	646.55	58.86	88.15	22.40	70.16	76.13	2960.64	4.18	0.00
125	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.17	9.83	15.64	0.00	593.47	69.33	90.74	22.82	78.41	82.68	3245.68	4.17	0.00
126	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.28	11.35	14.60	0.00	593.16	52.25	86.79	22.00	69.28	72.20	2636.95	4.41	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF,max,H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{H,RF}$ [kW/h/m ²]	E_H [kWh]	SCOP [-]	$Q_{summer,H}$ [%]
127	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.26	11.65	16.73	0.00	695.91	54.73	85.17	22.09	62.80	77.36	2991.52	4.21	0.00
128	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.18	10.16	16.31	0.00	623.19	66.89	89.81	22.71	70.37	84.65	3323.37	4.20	0.00
129	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.31	12.02	15.72	0.00	651.20	49.69	83.21	21.79	61.99	73.75	2681.79	4.44	0.00
130	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.27	12.01	16.87	0.00	692.76	54.05	82.26	22.01	62.02	72.43	2813.83	4.18	0.00
131	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.19	10.53	17.02	0.00	623.55	64.83	88.08	22.59	69.86	80.32	3184.74	4.14	0.00
132	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.31	12.37	16.08	0.00	641.73	50.30	80.05	21.70	61.55	69.26	2548.56	4.38	0.00
133	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.20	8.37	7.73	0.00	546.34	68.97	93.50	22.22	70.37	98.14	3714.17	4.26	0.00
134	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.14	7.79	6.97	0.00	472.84	81.67	94.99	22.91	78.86	105.19	4106.89	4.16	0.00
135	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.26	8.88	8.21	0.00	530.93	51.64	92.67	21.89	69.61	93.51	3347.06	4.46	0.00
136	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.19	8.42	7.78	0.00	532.65	66.95	93.08	22.20	70.65	91.19	3437.42	4.27	0.00
137	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.12	7.76	7.20	0.00	452.86	83.64	94.80	22.89	78.69	98.37	3842.60	4.16	0.00
138	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.26	8.87	8.29	0.00	514.16	54.88	91.77	21.87	69.30	87.08	3130.11	4.45	0.00
139	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.24	9.06	8.20	0.00	578.38	58.24	89.60	21.82	63.25	93.13	3468.62	4.32	0.00
140	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.15	8.05	7.30	0.00	479.74	77.33	94.07	22.68	70.14	101.38	3946.02	4.18	0.00
141	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.29	9.47	8.82	0.00	562.63	49.11	88.01	21.58	62.40	89.53	3184.91	4.49	0.00
142	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.25	9.31	8.39	0.00	578.31	55.70	87.54	21.74	61.97	86.58	3236.69	4.30	0.00
143	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.15	8.20	7.62	0.00	474.64	74.82	93.61	22.59	69.21	95.41	3750.87	4.13	0.00
144	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.30	9.71	8.98	0.00	561.34	49.63	85.73	21.50	61.89	83.45	2996.15	4.45	0.00
145	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.06	11.26	27.59	0.00	651.68	79.96	85.03	23.00	76.11	28.68	1154.95	4.62	0.00
146	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.09	11.82	31.99	0.00	787.27	75.54	82.34	23.06	80.28	28.70	1043.50	5.22	0.00
147	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.03	11.42	24.25	0.00	540.15	67.84	85.31	22.43	75.71	25.69	904.92	5.33	0.00
148	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.06	11.06	26.92	0.00	636.50	80.42	85.63	22.95	77.44	27.21	1101.05	4.60	0.00
149	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.09	11.61	30.70	0.00	755.12	76.01	82.90	22.98	80.07	27.17	1007.99	5.11	0.00
150	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.03	11.22	22.87	0.00	515.95	68.86	85.54	22.36	75.83	24.49	880.53	5.22	0.00
151	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.05	11.46	28.30	0.00	671.37	78.54	84.66	22.93	67.79	27.68	1131.13	4.56	0.00
152	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.09	12.00	32.61	0.00	807.27	74.55	82.11	23.03	70.77	27.16	1024.40	5.10	0.00
153	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.03	11.63	24.83	0.00	558.88	66.72	84.99	22.40	66.87	24.82	904.21	5.19	0.00
154	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.05	11.36	27.86	0.00	658.27	77.98	85.13	22.86	67.88	26.19	1078.44	4.52	0.00
155	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.09	11.85	31.81	0.00	782.62	75.06	82.60	22.95	70.77	26.00	1004.56	4.97	0.00
156	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.03	11.50	23.82	0.00	540.61	66.70	85.14	22.33	66.57	23.71	880.34	5.08	0.00
157	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.01	7.58	11.14	0.00	346.08	91.60	93.46	22.44	75.55	42.81	1621.85	4.67	0.00
158	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.02	7.73	12.04	0.00	386.49	90.38	92.44	22.54	80.11	42.86	1536.03	5.02	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF,max,H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{H,RF}$ [kW/h/m ²]	E_H [kWh]	SCOP [-]	$Q_{summer,H}$ [%]
159	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.09	7.81	11.02	0.00	337.73	80.25	93.66	21.92	73.87	39.92	1384.83	5.11	0.00
160	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.01	7.50	10.86	0.00	328.70	91.78	93.83	22.39	75.29	40.23	1527.99	4.65	0.00
161	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.02	7.65	11.89	0.00	373.49	90.63	92.75	22.49	78.98	40.54	1504.31	4.83	0.00
162	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.08	7.67	10.66	0.00	317.89	84.42	93.98	21.90	73.75	37.92	1338.27	5.03	0.00
163	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.01	7.67	11.21	0.00	354.94	90.71	93.39	22.29	66.77	40.96	1575.13	4.59	0.00
164	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.02	7.79	12.21	0.00	392.52	90.26	92.37	22.51	71.00	40.97	1534.65	4.84	0.00
165	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.09	7.87	11.06	0.00	347.97	79.57	93.59	21.88	66.69	38.67	1373.24	5.01	0.00
166	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.00	7.59	10.95	0.00	341.86	90.64	93.70	22.21	67.22	38.65	1491.13	4.57	0.00
167	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.04	7.74	12.06	0.00	385.88	90.39	92.64	22.46	70.17	39.41	1515.44	4.69	0.00
168	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.08	7.76	10.87	0.00	332.27	82.40	93.92	21.82	65.64	36.99	1336.51	4.93	0.00
169	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.23	10.85	14.32	0.00	494.34	54.62	88.75	22.35	73.51	70.31	2589.40	4.75	0.00
170	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.17	9.76	14.60	0.00	468.65	71.24	90.13	22.82	81.11	76.52	2837.56	4.74	0.00
171	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.29	11.52	14.86	0.00	475.80	44.91	87.94	21.96	72.40	66.02	2264.20	5.07	0.00
172	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.23	11.02	14.26	0.00	491.13	53.82	88.62	22.28	73.47	65.42	2418.62	4.74	0.00
173	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.16	9.82	14.60	0.00	456.82	72.23	89.96	22.79	81.64	72.42	2734.35	4.65	0.00
174	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.29	11.62	14.58	0.00	471.06	45.98	87.49	21.90	72.50	61.66	2145.67	5.00	0.00
175	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.27	11.83	14.58	0.00	519.98	48.74	86.18	22.00	65.29	66.54	2473.25	4.71	0.00
176	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.17	10.11	15.02	0.00	470.48	68.78	89.41	22.72	72.56	74.30	2854.72	4.59	0.00
177	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.31	12.28	15.21	0.00	503.37	44.35	84.70	21.74	65.14	63.11	2213.24	4.97	0.00
178	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.28	12.14	14.64	0.00	518.95	48.85	84.18	21.87	65.21	62.04	2330.08	4.66	0.00
179	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.17	10.28	15.14	0.00	462.64	67.15	89.07	22.65	72.40	70.75	2762.34	4.50	0.00
180	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.32	12.56	14.98	0.00	502.90	44.95	82.48	21.62	64.74	59.04	2096.94	4.90	0.00
181	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	-0.20	7.88	6.72	0.00	515.74	69.15	95.74	22.02	75.21	85.36	3086.30	4.76	0.00
182	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	-0.14	7.34	6.20	0.00	445.71	85.88	96.06	22.76	81.80	92.86	3512.19	4.55	0.00
183	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	-0.27	8.54	7.05	0.00	511.77	45.59	95.23	21.72	73.24	81.12	2777.27	5.00	0.00
184	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	-0.20	7.90	6.13	0.00	504.96	67.18	95.62	21.95	75.10	79.13	2878.52	4.73	0.00
185	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	-0.12	7.21	5.54	0.00	417.79	89.81	96.08	22.74	82.33	87.19	3341.05	4.48	0.00
186	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	-0.26	8.45	6.37	0.00	501.06	47.84	95.12	21.67	73.16	75.40	2609.85	4.94	0.00
187	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	-0.24	8.45	7.02	0.00	534.43	55.64	94.78	21.65	66.49	81.03	2931.80	4.74	0.00
188	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	-0.14	7.37	6.23	0.00	434.33	86.59	96.03	22.62	73.00	89.98	3486.92	4.45	0.00
189	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	-0.28	8.91	7.36	0.00	530.62	44.53	94.35	21.44	65.88	77.73	2691.95	4.94	0.00
190	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	-0.25	8.65	6.51	0.00	529.76	53.91	93.75	21.54	66.26	75.18	2745.61	4.70	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{lr\%}$ [%]	$PI_{hl\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF,max,H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{H,F}$ [kW/h/m ²]	E_H [kWh]	SCOP [-]	$Q_{summer,H}$ [%]
191	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	-0.13	7.34	5.76	0.00	406.00	85.64	96.05	22.52	72.78	85.04	3327.90	4.38	0.00
192	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	-0.29	9.05	6.71	0.00	525.71	45.35	92.27	21.34	65.64	72.24	2532.63	4.88	0.00
193	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.72	20.96	83.08	0.00	1215.90	51.16	52.32	25.32	37.18	1.70	44.56	5.10	0.00
194	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.82	24.52	87.08	0.00	1426.68	40.44	41.34	25.87	39.94	1.61	34.32	6.79	0.00
195	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.68	20.28	80.70	0.00	1192.52	53.63	55.26	25.07	37.06	1.35	22.65	7.20	0.00
196	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.71	20.38	83.44	0.00	1187.67	52.06	53.20	25.20	37.75	1.61	42.90	5.05	0.00
197	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.81	23.85	86.88	0.00	1353.34	41.46	42.29	25.74	41.78	1.52	30.96	7.10	0.00
198	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.67	19.68	80.37	0.00	1144.55	54.52	56.19	24.95	37.42	1.27	22.46	6.75	0.00
199	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.72	21.02	83.40	0.00	1222.82	50.98	52.22	25.32	34.73	1.64	44.17	5.10	0.00
200	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.82	24.54	86.95	0.00	1430.12	40.58	41.53	25.87	38.51	1.50	31.34	7.06	0.00
201	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.68	20.36	80.98	0.00	1202.46	53.44	54.98	25.09	34.57	1.27	22.44	7.00	0.00
202	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.71	20.51	83.65	0.00	1199.07	51.64	52.88	25.22	35.72	1.57	42.76	5.06	0.00
203	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.81	23.90	86.83	0.00	1364.88	41.64	42.49	25.74	38.56	1.44	28.84	7.34	0.00
204	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.67	19.79	80.61	0.00	1154.96	54.38	55.94	24.97	35.49	1.20	21.86	6.79	0.00
205	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.47	11.88	62.27	0.00	750.64	81.12	81.62	23.72	39.05	5.80	145.39	5.35	0.00
206	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.49	12.69	70.38	0.00	875.63	74.51	74.83	23.76	44.61	5.11	108.94	6.62	0.00
207	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.40	10.88	54.90	0.00	707.44	83.91	84.65	23.26	39.59	4.95	99.23	6.24	0.00
208	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.47	11.66	60.07	0.00	721.22	82.31	82.77	23.63	39.11	5.47	138.82	5.29	0.00
209	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.49	12.41	70.26	0.00	848.62	76.00	76.32	23.68	42.36	4.99	108.50	6.53	0.00
210	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.40	10.65	53.44	0.00	678.58	85.03	85.78	23.18	38.34	4.74	98.00	6.13	0.00
211	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.47	11.88	62.82	0.00	764.69	80.88	81.39	23.68	36.20	5.51	141.09	5.27	0.00
212	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.50	12.85	71.21	0.00	896.91	73.87	74.20	23.80	39.84	4.97	110.76	6.47	0.00
213	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.41	11.00	56.44	0.00	756.52	83.44	84.27	23.29	35.42	4.81	100.44	6.18	0.00
214	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.47	11.70	61.68	0.00	745.43	81.75	82.25	23.59	37.06	5.26	134.86	5.21	0.00
215	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.50	12.61	71.53	0.00	877.03	75.04	75.40	23.72	37.45	4.97	113.12	6.35	0.00
216	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.41	10.82	55.16	0.00	732.69	84.25	85.10	23.21	36.52	4.67	99.86	6.03	0.00
217	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.19	9.77	40.14	0.00	627.31	76.20	90.29	22.89	35.97	12.60	272.77	5.56	0.00
218	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.18	9.59	39.38	0.00	597.95	75.80	90.92	22.79	37.29	13.46	275.01	6.06	0.00
219	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.13	9.68	36.28	0.00	580.28	69.79	91.08	22.48	33.43	11.21	205.22	6.14	0.00
220	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.18	9.58	39.52	0.00	589.99	77.25	91.32	22.81	33.90	11.76	255.05	5.52	0.00
221	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.18	9.49	38.99	0.00	571.50	76.77	91.61	22.76	35.53	12.84	276.66	5.77	0.00
222	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.13	9.52	35.53	0.00	560.52	70.92	91.83	22.41	31.56	10.64	201.99	6.01	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{lr\%}$ [%]	$PI_{hl\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{FE,max,H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{H,F}$ [kW/h/m ²]	E_H [kWh]	SCOP [-]	$Q_{summer,H}$ [%]
223	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.18	9.90	40.11	0.00	637.77	73.45	90.15	22.81	33.29	12.04	259.06	5.51	0.00
224	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.18	9.74	40.49	0.00	615.42	74.67	90.49	22.82	35.49	13.04	282.53	5.78	0.00
225	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.13	9.83	36.66	0.00	595.69	69.08	90.88	22.47	30.72	10.86	202.35	6.06	0.00
226	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.17	9.74	39.51	0.00	617.32	74.32	91.02	22.72	31.74	11.18	243.13	5.46	0.00
227	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.18	9.68	40.52	0.00	596.64	75.92	91.21	22.79	32.40	12.84	291.23	5.52	0.00
228	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.13	9.69	36.25	0.00	579.01	70.15	91.43	22.39	28.84	10.25	199.01	5.92	0.00
229	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.13	6.86	14.90	0.00	373.86	91.37	98.03	22.33	39.19	18.73	413.15	5.63	0.00
230	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.14	6.85	14.65	0.00	353.37	94.67	98.13	22.53	43.44	20.65	470.96	5.58	0.00
231	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.06	6.88	13.59	0.00	355.13	76.41	98.13	21.96	36.97	17.38	348.83	5.99	0.00
232	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.13	6.80	13.99	0.00	361.11	91.45	98.31	22.29	36.22	17.52	390.39	5.57	0.00
233	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.16	6.87	14.63	0.00	343.73	95.16	98.34	22.57	38.79	19.98	478.43	5.34	0.00
234	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.07	6.79	12.96	0.00	339.07	79.79	98.38	21.91	34.42	16.37	336.27	5.89	0.00
235	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.12	6.92	15.02	0.00	384.77	88.48	98.01	22.21	35.89	17.77	391.03	5.63	0.00
236	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.15	6.94	15.58	0.00	365.88	94.57	97.96	22.55	40.00	20.23	484.48	5.34	0.00
237	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.06	6.95	13.83	0.00	366.61	75.10	98.04	21.90	34.65	16.62	339.00	5.92	0.00
238	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.11	6.88	14.08	0.00	370.13	88.19	98.27	22.11	33.07	16.62	366.37	5.56	0.00
239	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.17	6.99	15.84	0.00	364.78	94.59	98.19	22.56	35.39	19.92	491.94	5.16	0.00
240	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.06	6.88	13.44	0.00	351.56	78.68	98.26	21.82	31.67	15.71	324.14	5.84	0.00
241	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	3.68	99.84	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.39	28.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
242	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	3.84	99.91	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.25	30.69	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
243	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	3.68	99.84	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.39	28.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
244	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	3.66	99.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.24	27.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
245	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	3.81	99.91	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.09	29.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
246	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	3.66	99.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.24	27.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
247	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	3.68	99.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.40	27.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
248	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	3.84	99.91	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.26	29.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
249	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	3.68	99.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.40	27.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
250	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	3.66	99.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.27	26.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
251	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	3.82	99.91	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.12	28.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
252	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	3.66	99.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	38.27	26.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
253	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	3.14	99.09	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.48	22.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
254	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	3.27	99.47	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.16	24.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OH_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{lr\%}$ [%]	$PI_{hl\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{FE,max,H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{H,FE}$ [kW/h/m ²]	E_H [kWh]	SCOP [-]	$Q_{summer,H}$ [%]
255	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	3.14	99.09	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.48	22.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
256	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	3.13	99.06	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.36	22.93	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
257	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	3.25	99.45	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.03	24.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
258	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	3.13	99.06	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.36	22.93	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
259	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	3.14	99.10	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.50	21.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
260	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	3.27	99.48	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.17	23.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
261	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	3.14	99.10	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.50	21.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
262	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	3.13	99.08	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.38	22.43	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
263	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	3.26	99.46	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.06	23.91	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
264	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	3.13	99.08	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.38	22.43	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
265	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	2.92	97.26	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.29	18.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
266	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	2.92	97.26	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.29	18.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
267	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	2.92	97.26	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.29	18.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
268	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	2.90	97.18	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.17	18.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
269	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	2.90	97.18	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.17	18.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
270	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	2.90	97.18	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.17	18.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
271	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	2.92	97.26	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.30	17.43	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
272	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	2.92	97.26	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.30	17.43	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
273	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	2.92	97.26	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.30	17.43	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
274	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	2.90	97.19	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.19	17.68	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
275	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	2.90	97.19	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.19	17.68	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
276	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	2.90	97.19	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	34.19	17.68	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
277	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	2.60	93.70	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.63	14.93	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
278	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	2.60	93.70	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.63	14.93	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
279	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	2.60	93.70	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.63	14.93	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
280	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	2.59	93.52	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.50	16.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
281	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	2.59	93.52	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.50	16.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
282	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	2.59	93.52	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.50	16.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
283	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	2.60	93.74	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.64	14.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
284	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	2.60	93.74	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.64	14.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
285	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	2.60	93.74	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.64	14.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
286	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	2.59	93.59	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.52	15.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	PMV_{out} [%]	PD_{asym} [%]	OH_{DH} [°Ch]	PI_{in} [%]	PI_{in} [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF,max,H}$ [W/m ²]	$q_{H,RF}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_H [kWh]	$SCOP$ [-]	$Q_{summer,H}$ [%]
287	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	2.59	93.59	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.52	15.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
288	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	2.59	93.59	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.52	15.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

D.2. Cooling

D.2.1. Living Zone

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out, \%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym, \%}$ [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{I, \%}$ [%]	$PI_{II, \%}$ [%]	$T_{f, avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF, max, C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
1	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.56	13.74	52.45	0.00	79.54	59.63	90.65	23.65	20.36	35.80	0.00
2	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.46	11.33	50.26	0.09	130.10	75.75	95.64	22.92	26.44	36.62	0.00
3	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.64	15.73	59.72	0.00	66.16	47.71	84.71	24.09	21.24	35.19	0.00
4	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.55	13.38	52.32	0.00	81.28	61.11	91.36	23.58	19.14	35.98	0.00
5	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.44	11.13	49.98	0.00	156.01	75.23	95.15	22.89	23.62	36.84	0.00
6	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.62	15.28	58.89	0.00	74.02	49.69	85.86	24.01	19.97	35.38	0.00
7	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.61	15.14	55.20	0.00	76.00	51.03	85.40	24.00	17.83	35.46	0.00
8	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.50	12.18	53.57	0.00	112.65	71.36	94.27	23.22	22.28	36.36	0.00
9	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.69	17.13	61.31	0.00	59.89	41.40	78.81	24.42	18.52	34.89	0.00
10	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.60	14.99	54.62	0.00	74.48	51.35	85.26	23.99	16.31	35.56	0.00
11	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.49	12.09	53.30	0.00	130.91	70.32	94.05	23.24	19.52	36.52	0.00
12	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.68	16.93	61.31	0.00	64.72	42.25	79.06	24.39	16.89	35.01	0.00
13	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.39	10.39	38.41	0.00	45.42	75.43	96.46	23.53	20.46	37.36	0.00
14	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.38	9.87	38.75	0.50	64.77	80.06	97.87	23.37	30.00	37.36	0.00
15	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.47	11.91	41.83	0.00	33.12	66.28	95.40	24.04	21.07	36.82	0.00
16	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.37	10.03	35.99	0.00	47.85	76.06	96.20	23.44	19.06	37.61	0.00
17	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.36	9.54	37.44	0.13	61.09	78.48	97.52	23.30	26.50	37.65	0.00
18	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.45	11.55	40.50	0.00	33.43	67.28	94.97	23.92	19.75	37.05	0.00
19	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.43	11.13	40.99	0.00	46.51	70.16	95.40	23.78	17.67	37.14	0.00
20	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.41	10.40	40.66	0.00	63.03	77.19	97.82	23.58	24.99	37.19	0.00
21	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.50	12.66	44.28	0.00	32.73	60.44	93.55	24.24	18.27	36.63	0.00
22	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.41	10.90	40.07	0.00	46.44	69.68	95.14	23.72	16.03	37.33	0.00
23	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.39	10.21	40.30	0.00	54.53	75.99	97.31	23.56	21.28	37.41	0.00
24	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.48	12.38	42.72	0.00	30.21	61.43	93.42	24.16	16.55	36.82	0.00
25	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.31	10.87	41.27	0.00	154.82	63.03	87.69	23.02	19.79	38.01	0.00
26	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.28	10.25	38.91	0.00	159.93	67.17	88.62	22.85	25.76	38.34	0.00
27	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.38	12.13	44.47	0.00	129.18	58.76	85.73	23.44	20.73	37.49	0.00
28	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.29	10.64	40.64	0.00	148.33	60.84	87.31	22.85	19.02	38.18	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{II,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III,\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{R,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
29	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.26	10.14	38.66	0.00	157.96	63.58	87.62	22.71	22.87	38.50	0.00
30	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.35	11.83	43.60	0.00	136.80	57.85	85.21	23.26	19.93	37.67	0.00
31	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.34	11.57	43.05	0.00	146.20	59.94	85.64	23.25	17.12	37.80	0.00
32	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.30	10.71	41.13	0.00	150.89	65.34	87.59	23.03	21.68	38.18	0.00
33	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.40	12.75	45.36	0.00	126.10	56.59	83.56	23.63	17.91	37.33	0.00
34	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.33	11.44	42.65	0.00	149.38	59.05	84.95	23.15	16.01	37.90	0.00
35	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.28	10.65	40.37	0.00	151.35	61.47	86.90	22.94	18.64	38.31	0.00
36	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.38	12.57	44.72	0.00	129.45	55.19	83.12	23.50	16.80	37.45	0.00
37	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.10	10.21	46.93	0.00	50.31	53.93	77.54	22.68	19.90	40.32	0.00
38	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.08	9.94	47.32	0.00	48.94	54.96	77.18	22.58	26.33	40.49	0.00
39	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.14	10.89	49.34	0.00	41.59	52.69	78.07	22.96	20.36	40.01	0.00
40	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.07	10.10	46.62	0.00	55.69	51.60	75.79	22.44	18.88	40.56	0.00
41	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.05	9.88	47.11	0.00	60.54	52.08	74.81	22.36	23.36	40.75	0.00
42	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.11	10.71	49.51	0.00	45.62	50.67	76.50	22.72	19.27	40.24	0.00
43	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.12	10.56	48.51	0.00	47.70	52.54	77.77	22.84	17.02	40.19	0.00
44	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.09	10.23	47.85	0.00	53.22	53.32	77.49	22.71	21.87	40.39	0.00
45	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.16	11.20	50.42	0.00	39.53	50.66	77.39	23.09	17.46	39.91	0.00
46	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.09	10.47	48.52	0.00	49.60	50.03	76.23	22.66	15.73	40.37	0.00
47	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.07	10.18	48.11	0.00	56.62	50.66	75.64	22.54	18.72	40.59	0.00
48	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.13	11.08	50.60	0.00	42.95	48.50	75.96	22.90	15.96	40.09	0.00
49	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.83	22.08	82.30	0.00	58.72	31.48	72.61	24.10	16.19	47.71	0.00
50	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.69	17.32	76.65	0.05	76.31	58.29	86.53	23.24	25.00	49.19	0.00
51	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.90	24.54	85.07	0.00	50.72	19.69	63.74	24.51	16.43	46.96	0.00
52	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.82	21.74	82.06	0.00	60.94	32.60	73.49	24.12	15.47	47.88	0.00
53	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.68	17.16	77.51	0.00	82.35	57.91	86.05	23.31	22.09	49.39	0.00
54	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.89	24.18	84.84	0.00	52.15	21.56	64.86	24.51	15.70	47.14	0.00
55	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.89	24.46	84.19	0.00	54.62	23.44	63.14	24.56	14.11	47.16	0.00
56	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.74	19.00	79.09	0.00	68.36	51.84	81.55	23.64	21.40	48.74	0.00
57	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.95	26.63	86.06	0.00	48.79	16.40	54.50	24.90	14.28	46.54	0.00
58	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.89	24.44	84.58	0.00	56.00	23.47	62.97	24.64	12.99	47.24	0.00
59	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.74	19.07	79.88	0.00	72.10	50.71	81.00	23.76	18.38	48.85	0.00
60	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.95	26.59	86.23	0.00	49.49	17.30	53.99	24.96	13.22	46.63	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{II,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III,\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{R,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
61	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.70	17.64	77.68	0.00	43.96	51.84	89.39	23.97	18.52	48.09	0.00
62	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.62	15.17	71.58	0.10	64.26	66.85	92.73	23.34	25.98	48.88	0.00
63	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.78	20.04	79.56	0.00	38.86	33.98	83.09	24.40	18.18	47.36	0.00
64	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.70	17.42	76.75	0.00	27.03	52.56	89.97	23.99	16.46	48.28	0.00
65	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.61	14.86	72.73	0.00	48.10	67.81	92.78	23.41	23.23	49.17	0.00
66	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.77	19.72	78.88	0.00	38.21	36.41	83.98	24.41	15.91	47.57	0.00
67	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.75	19.21	79.12	0.00	41.59	42.26	82.98	24.31	15.78	47.70	0.00
68	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.66	16.31	73.95	0.00	56.11	62.15	90.66	23.66	22.46	48.56	0.00
69	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.82	21.58	80.86	0.00	37.67	27.18	75.78	24.72	15.43	47.03	0.00
70	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.75	19.24	78.43	0.00	41.32	42.02	82.60	24.40	13.72	47.81	0.00
71	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.65	16.20	75.54	0.00	38.11	62.63	89.94	23.77	19.99	48.78	0.00
72	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.82	21.54	80.27	0.00	37.30	29.18	75.27	24.78	13.70	47.15	0.00
73	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.69	18.41	73.76	0.00	71.18	45.26	81.44	23.87	15.49	49.45	0.00
74	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.60	15.51	71.88	0.00	92.93	61.65	88.70	23.31	23.52	50.44	0.00
75	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.76	20.27	78.17	0.00	59.79	35.84	78.38	24.27	15.67	48.77	0.00
76	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.68	18.15	72.79	0.00	70.81	46.05	81.86	23.85	15.06	49.58	0.00
77	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.59	15.35	71.59	0.00	75.60	59.56	88.92	23.31	21.34	50.60	0.00
78	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.75	20.01	77.55	0.00	62.53	36.41	78.33	24.24	15.26	48.90	0.00
79	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.73	19.88	76.41	0.00	66.30	38.97	77.07	24.20	13.21	49.09	0.00
80	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.64	16.70	73.21	0.00	89.12	57.05	86.22	23.63	20.71	50.11	0.00
81	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.79	21.69	79.06	0.00	56.91	31.44	72.95	24.57	13.38	48.46	0.00
82	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.73	19.89	75.01	0.00	63.73	38.24	76.61	24.23	12.47	49.14	0.00
83	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.63	16.65	73.21	0.00	93.46	55.70	85.55	23.67	18.22	50.22	0.00
84	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.79	21.62	79.23	0.00	58.16	31.58	72.59	24.58	12.57	48.54	0.00
85	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.56	15.00	67.66	0.00	19.62	58.70	88.12	23.79	16.01	49.99	0.00
86	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.51	13.47	63.98	0.00	33.43	68.08	89.66	23.42	23.35	50.53	0.00
87	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.62	16.62	69.59	0.00	13.37	50.68	87.03	24.17	15.80	49.42	0.00
88	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.55	14.69	66.44	0.00	21.87	58.98	88.43	23.74	14.77	50.18	0.00
89	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.50	13.21	64.22	0.00	37.06	67.34	89.77	23.41	20.84	50.74	0.00
90	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.61	16.33	68.93	0.00	15.06	51.31	86.99	24.12	15.30	49.58	0.00
91	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.59	15.97	69.05	0.00	17.55	53.73	86.09	24.04	13.77	49.73	0.00
92	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.53	14.15	66.17	0.00	28.46	65.23	88.79	23.64	19.86	50.35	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{II,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III,\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{R,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Conda$ [h]
93	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.64	17.44	70.47	0.00	12.36	45.40	84.53	24.38	14.30	49.23	0.00
94	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.59	15.89	68.39	0.00	18.86	53.88	85.93	24.06	12.71	49.84	0.00
95	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.53	14.07	66.27	0.00	30.51	64.24	88.35	23.69	17.61	50.49	0.00
96	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.64	17.30	69.63	0.00	13.36	45.82	84.31	24.37	13.23	49.34	0.00
97	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.82	20.51	82.71	0.00	91.70	27.52	72.64	23.64	26.83	31.74	0.00
98	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.58	13.41	60.73	0.45	155.04	75.77	94.02	22.27	30.09	33.48	0.00
99	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.87	22.41	85.35	0.00	66.02	18.64	63.95	23.94	27.36	31.28	0.00
100	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.81	20.30	82.72	0.00	96.39	28.30	73.41	23.72	25.56	31.85	0.00
101	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.58	13.41	66.33	0.31	176.04	75.98	93.92	22.43	28.08	33.62	0.00
102	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.87	22.21	85.27	0.00	67.95	19.55	65.12	24.02	26.19	31.40	0.00
103	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.89	23.28	84.93	0.00	80.87	19.14	58.67	24.22	23.51	31.28	0.00
104	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.63	14.75	72.42	0.10	127.34	68.24	91.39	22.72	26.31	33.18	0.00
105	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.94	24.98	87.11	0.00	61.07	15.01	49.83	24.47	23.80	30.91	0.00
106	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.90	23.49	85.27	0.00	82.83	19.49	57.48	24.36	21.77	31.31	0.00
107	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.63	14.93	76.96	0.00	145.04	67.25	90.49	22.93	23.92	33.27	0.00
108	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.94	25.18	87.82	0.00	61.41	15.47	47.66	24.61	22.11	30.95	0.00
109	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.67	15.59	77.97	0.00	38.00	53.85	91.38	23.44	30.93	31.75	0.00
110	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.52	11.81	66.39	0.38	107.06	84.74	95.99	22.45	31.41	32.75	0.00
111	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.73	17.57	80.32	0.00	30.48	35.70	85.58	23.79	28.89	31.23	0.00
112	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.66	15.35	77.50	0.00	41.14	54.92	91.65	23.51	29.03	31.89	0.00
113	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.50	11.59	66.60	0.31	124.07	85.21	95.92	22.57	28.99	32.95	0.00
114	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.72	17.32	79.76	0.00	32.32	39.02	85.70	23.86	26.00	31.37	0.00
115	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.72	17.34	79.55	0.00	33.70	40.34	84.52	23.91	27.47	31.42	0.00
116	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.55	12.71	72.22	0.00	82.70	79.51	95.47	22.83	27.35	32.53	0.00
117	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.78	19.23	81.66	0.00	27.68	26.22	76.87	24.21	25.12	30.96	0.00
118	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.72	17.38	79.03	0.00	35.11	40.65	83.91	24.04	26.18	31.49	0.00
119	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.55	12.65	72.84	0.00	94.86	79.31	95.34	23.00	25.08	32.68	0.00
120	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.78	19.36	81.65	0.00	28.82	27.84	74.92	24.36	22.33	31.02	0.00
121	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.70	17.69	75.22	0.00	95.38	38.43	75.40	23.42	26.65	32.84	0.00
122	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.51	12.50	63.94	0.32	172.76	72.94	89.99	22.32	27.92	34.21	0.00
123	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.74	19.02	77.57	0.00	74.66	30.39	71.22	23.70	27.14	32.48	0.00
124	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.69	17.54	74.68	0.00	93.62	38.47	76.30	23.47	25.48	32.92	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{II,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III,\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{heat,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
125	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.51	12.47	65.70	0.00	198.59	72.07	89.57	22.42	26.77	34.34	0.00
126	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.73	18.84	77.13	0.00	78.27	31.19	71.93	23.73	25.90	32.58	0.00
127	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.75	19.72	77.80	0.00	88.61	29.69	66.35	23.90	23.12	32.49	0.00
128	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.55	13.61	69.70	0.00	151.76	66.56	87.89	22.72	24.51	33.97	0.00
129	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.79	20.91	79.52	0.00	69.25	24.66	62.47	24.13	23.42	32.19	0.00
130	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.76	19.91	77.92	0.00	85.76	29.44	65.40	24.01	21.24	32.50	0.00
131	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.55	13.78	69.85	0.00	171.22	65.13	87.11	22.88	22.78	34.04	0.00
132	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.80	21.09	79.66	0.00	70.09	24.80	61.11	24.24	21.45	32.21	0.00
133	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.55	14.06	74.34	0.00	62.44	57.08	86.65	23.26	31.29	32.85	0.00
134	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.42	11.08	67.43	0.17	127.82	79.55	89.68	22.43	30.90	33.66	0.00
135	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.60	15.37	75.74	0.00	53.89	46.49	84.11	23.54	28.52	32.45	0.00
136	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.54	13.81	73.47	0.00	69.62	58.05	86.84	23.29	28.55	32.96	0.00
137	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.41	10.96	67.11	0.00	149.73	78.86	89.60	22.53	28.05	33.79	0.00
138	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.59	15.08	75.17	0.00	58.47	48.58	84.48	23.57	26.05	32.56	0.00
139	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.59	15.33	75.94	0.00	58.77	46.82	82.03	23.65	28.43	32.60	0.00
140	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.46	11.83	70.90	0.00	108.62	74.98	89.19	22.78	27.00	33.49	0.00
141	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.64	16.59	77.31	0.00	54.38	38.31	78.18	23.90	24.68	32.25	0.00
142	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.59	15.36	75.69	0.00	59.69	46.34	81.09	23.74	25.31	32.65	0.00
143	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.45	11.82	70.89	0.00	127.11	73.57	89.00	22.92	23.71	33.59	0.00
144	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.63	16.57	77.24	0.00	52.76	39.79	77.23	23.99	22.64	32.31	0.00
145	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.40	46.15	95.18	0.00	20.22	14.35	38.67	25.52	16.31	59.70	0.50
146	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	1.36	44.68	94.02	0.00	38.50	23.74	42.75	25.22	24.33	60.12	0.40
147	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.44	47.77	95.69	0.00	14.99	9.13	33.88	25.75	16.37	59.20	0.20
148	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.39	45.71	95.04	0.00	21.86	14.59	38.90	25.53	15.37	59.91	0.70
149	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	1.35	44.32	94.11	0.00	41.38	22.61	42.69	25.25	21.97	60.33	0.70
150	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.43	47.35	95.57	0.00	15.63	9.18	33.99	25.76	15.46	59.41	0.10
151	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.46	48.84	95.71	0.00	17.23	11.07	33.58	25.97	14.47	58.97	0.10
152	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.42	47.12	94.46	0.00	32.29	20.67	39.94	25.63	20.47	59.42	0.10
153	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.49	50.31	95.97	0.00	13.31	6.67	28.01	26.17	14.52	58.53	0.00
154	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.46	48.85	95.78	0.00	17.82	10.62	32.87	26.03	13.24	59.03	0.30
155	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.42	47.15	94.62	0.00	34.22	19.46	39.52	25.72	18.04	59.51	0.30
156	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.49	50.32	96.16	0.00	13.64	6.64	27.14	26.23	13.29	58.61	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{II,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III,\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{R,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Conda$ [h]
157	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.20	37.27	93.78	0.00	28.41	26.38	49.82	25.06	16.55	61.10	4.50
158	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	1.19	37.02	92.36	0.00	45.87	29.81	49.82	24.89	22.08	61.16	3.90
159	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.26	39.50	94.77	0.00	20.38	16.56	47.36	25.38	16.13	60.36	2.90
160	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.19	36.98	93.62	0.00	29.40	26.01	49.85	25.08	15.34	61.27	5.30
161	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	1.18	36.64	92.21	0.00	42.11	28.89	49.76	24.93	20.07	61.38	4.70
162	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.25	39.19	94.57	0.00	21.18	17.30	47.27	25.40	15.22	60.55	4.10
163	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.25	39.41	94.27	0.00	25.56	21.43	47.94	25.42	14.28	60.52	3.50
164	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	1.23	38.99	93.09	0.00	41.03	26.43	48.19	25.23	19.97	60.62	2.30
165	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.30	41.45	95.12	0.00	19.26	13.56	44.34	25.70	14.08	59.88	0.90
166	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.25	39.50	94.35	0.00	25.67	20.73	47.40	25.51	13.03	60.59	2.90
167	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.23	38.97	93.17	0.00	37.31	26.03	47.56	25.33	18.08	60.75	2.50
168	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.30	41.52	95.03	0.00	19.48	13.41	43.49	25.78	12.98	59.95	1.70
169	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.29	41.47	92.98	0.00	58.14	22.19	45.93	25.28	15.38	61.53	2.40
170	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	1.26	40.59	92.42	0.00	72.29	27.50	47.40	25.13	22.52	61.84	2.40
171	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.33	42.98	93.66	0.00	39.79	17.41	43.62	25.55	15.45	61.03	0.80
172	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.28	41.08	93.19	0.00	60.84	22.05	46.06	25.27	14.38	61.71	3.90
173	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	1.26	40.29	92.56	0.00	77.15	26.50	47.55	25.13	20.17	62.00	5.00
174	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.32	42.59	93.90	0.00	40.77	17.18	43.54	25.53	14.46	61.21	3.40
175	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.33	43.36	93.21	0.00	50.64	19.11	43.18	25.64	13.27	61.02	0.50
176	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.30	42.32	92.92	0.00	65.24	24.87	45.76	25.46	18.67	61.35	1.00
177	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.37	44.72	93.89	0.00	36.56	15.08	40.43	25.87	13.32	60.58	0.30
178	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.33	43.32	93.39	0.00	51.27	18.83	42.92	25.68	12.11	61.08	0.60
179	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.30	42.32	93.10	0.00	67.40	23.44	45.35	25.52	16.44	61.42	0.90
180	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.36	44.67	94.17	0.00	36.46	14.46	39.96	25.90	12.17	60.65	0.30
181	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.11	33.76	87.14	0.00	29.79	30.35	51.67	24.95	15.12	62.68	6.90
182	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	1.11	33.77	86.45	0.00	35.10	31.02	51.73	24.92	19.36	62.69	6.50
183	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.16	35.65	87.89	0.00	24.28	26.13	51.08	25.28	15.20	62.03	3.20
184	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.10	33.46	86.86	0.00	29.81	30.23	51.48	24.95	14.15	62.83	7.20
185	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	1.10	33.45	86.15	0.00	36.68	30.64	51.60	24.93	17.56	62.86	6.40
186	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.15	35.33	87.73	0.00	26.10	25.80	51.03	25.27	14.23	62.18	3.70
187	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.14	35.26	87.62	0.00	27.39	28.57	50.59	25.23	13.12	62.27	5.00
188	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	1.14	35.11	86.80	0.00	32.35	29.90	50.85	25.18	17.03	62.34	4.40

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{II,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III,\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{REmax,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
189	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.19	36.93	88.28	0.00	24.44	23.78	49.76	25.52	13.12	61.71	2.90
190	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.14	35.21	87.52	0.00	27.45	27.89	50.45	25.27	11.98	62.36	4.50
191	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.14	35.05	86.85	0.00	34.92	29.36	50.45	25.23	15.71	62.44	3.70
192	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.19	36.87	88.27	0.00	24.51	23.51	49.35	25.55	12.02	61.80	3.10
193	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.03	28.84	93.78	0.00	4.51	18.51	59.02	22.97	30.95	30.52	0.00
194	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.83	22.49	83.68	0.00	60.58	58.68	76.87	21.86	29.87	31.90	0.00
195	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.05	29.88	94.17	0.00	3.09	13.45	54.50	23.09	30.57	30.31	0.00
196	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.02	28.50	94.05	0.00	4.67	19.73	60.69	23.10	29.72	30.67	0.00
197	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.83	22.23	86.37	0.00	66.85	59.82	77.62	22.04	28.93	32.07	0.00
198	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.05	29.53	94.50	0.00	3.22	14.74	56.00	23.23	29.68	30.46	0.00
199	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.13	33.16	95.84	0.00	3.60	5.86	41.75	23.78	27.37	29.84	0.00
200	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.92	25.43	90.83	0.00	28.36	48.91	70.78	22.56	26.38	31.34	0.00
201	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.15	33.94	96.08	0.00	2.79	3.95	36.78	23.87	26.98	29.70	0.00
202	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.14	33.60	96.61	0.00	3.60	5.14	39.01	24.03	25.66	29.85	0.00
203	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.92	25.61	92.17	0.00	34.06	48.21	70.46	22.82	24.85	31.41	0.00
204	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.16	34.33	96.93	0.00	2.78	3.78	34.23	24.12	25.37	29.72	0.00
205	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.85	21.77	91.92	0.00	6.87	48.98	81.13	22.55	31.41	30.73	0.00
206	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.72	18.11	85.88	0.04	107.47	72.82	84.62	21.72	30.44	31.60	0.00
207	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.90	23.56	92.66	0.00	3.61	32.40	77.55	22.79	30.97	30.30	0.00
208	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.84	21.44	92.15	0.00	7.47	52.03	81.41	22.69	29.61	30.90	0.00
209	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.71	17.88	87.25	0.00	105.92	73.84	85.03	21.93	29.66	31.78	0.00
210	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.89	23.15	92.85	0.00	3.84	35.79	78.61	22.93	29.64	30.49	0.00
211	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.93	24.79	93.69	0.00	4.66	28.90	73.72	23.27	27.48	30.21	0.00
212	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.78	20.05	90.10	0.00	52.69	66.05	81.78	22.32	27.29	31.21	0.00
213	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.97	26.36	94.03	0.00	3.04	16.59	67.50	23.46	27.37	29.87	0.00
214	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.94	24.97	94.07	0.00	4.83	28.10	72.75	23.51	26.04	30.28	0.00
215	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.78	20.12	91.20	0.00	47.48	66.25	81.55	22.59	25.94	31.33	0.00
216	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.98	26.43	94.59	0.00	3.14	16.92	66.91	23.69	25.58	29.96	0.00
217	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.08	31.38	95.26	0.00	17.96	15.74	50.98	23.29	31.28	29.97	0.00
218	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.92	25.74	90.83	0.00	66.51	49.71	69.09	22.27	30.73	31.11	0.00
219	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.10	32.04	95.82	0.00	12.01	11.69	48.82	23.39	31.26	29.84	0.00
220	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.07	31.05	95.59	0.00	18.50	16.19	51.98	23.40	30.41	30.10	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{II,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III,\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{ref,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
221	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.91	25.37	91.51	0.00	77.91	50.67	69.95	22.41	29.97	31.28	0.00
222	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.09	31.72	96.07	0.00	12.37	12.24	49.83	23.50	30.19	29.97	0.00
223	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.17	35.32	96.44	0.00	14.67	8.56	36.96	24.06	27.92	29.41	0.00
224	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.00	28.79	93.37	0.00	46.44	39.58	61.97	23.00	27.28	30.60	0.00
225	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.19	35.84	96.87	0.00	12.45	6.39	34.67	24.14	27.55	29.31	0.00
226	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.18	35.72	96.68	0.00	14.92	8.14	34.65	24.29	26.35	29.42	0.00
227	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.00	28.92	94.11	0.00	55.32	39.01	61.79	23.22	26.00	30.67	0.00
228	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.20	36.22	97.06	0.00	12.45	6.17	32.26	24.36	26.20	29.33	0.00
229	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.91	24.47	92.99	0.00	9.42	37.80	73.48	22.94	31.63	30.13	0.00
230	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.79	20.80	89.85	0.01	69.13	64.54	79.20	22.13	30.85	30.90	0.00
231	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.95	25.64	93.63	0.00	9.62	27.71	70.70	23.12	30.99	29.86	0.00
232	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.90	24.10	93.11	0.00	11.64	39.53	74.34	23.05	30.79	30.29	0.00
233	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.78	20.50	90.07	0.00	71.19	66.04	79.72	22.29	30.00	31.07	0.00
234	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.94	25.20	93.81	0.00	10.18	30.57	72.02	23.23	29.61	30.03	0.00
235	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.99	27.54	94.62	0.00	6.78	23.38	62.02	23.64	27.78	29.66	0.00
236	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.85	23.06	91.92	0.00	39.18	55.03	74.77	22.78	27.47	30.52	0.00
237	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.02	28.51	95.02	0.00	9.05	16.81	58.52	23.79	27.22	29.45	0.00
238	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.00	27.71	94.73	0.00	7.57	23.09	61.09	23.86	26.57	29.72	0.00
239	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.85	23.11	92.45	0.00	45.35	54.82	74.65	23.02	25.74	30.62	0.00
240	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.02	28.63	95.20	0.00	9.24	16.74	57.72	24.00	25.44	29.52	0.00
241	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	2.39	87.10	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.37	16.49	65.88	0.00
242	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	2.42	87.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.48	16.89	65.40	0.00
243	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	2.39	87.12	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.38	16.49	65.87	0.00
244	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	2.37	86.68	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.21	15.53	66.25	0.00
245	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	2.39	87.40	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.32	15.90	65.80	0.00
246	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	2.37	86.70	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.22	15.53	66.25	0.00
247	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	2.46	88.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.80	14.86	64.97	0.00
248	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	2.49	89.61	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.93	15.28	64.44	0.00
249	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	2.46	88.87	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.81	14.86	64.96	0.00
250	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	2.44	88.76	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.70	13.57	65.17	0.00
251	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	2.47	89.53	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.83	13.93	64.65	0.00
252	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	2.44	88.78	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.71	13.57	65.16	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out,\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym,\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{II,\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III,\%}$ [%]	$T_{r,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{perm,c}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Conda$ [h]
253	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	2.07	77.31	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	28.30	14.85	69.89	3.80
254	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	2.09	78.18	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.38	15.15	69.48	3.00
255	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	2.08	77.52	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.32	14.81	69.79	3.80
256	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	2.05	76.84	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	28.20	14.09	70.19	5.30
257	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	2.08	77.70	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.28	14.36	69.78	3.40
258	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	2.06	77.04	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.23	14.06	70.09	5.60
259	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	2.12	79.48	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.67	13.35	69.12	1.20
260	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	2.15	80.38	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.77	13.62	68.68	0.70
261	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	2.13	79.61	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.69	13.36	69.05	1.10
262	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	2.12	79.40	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.63	12.31	69.26	0.90
263	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	2.14	80.31	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.72	12.57	68.83	1.00
264	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	2.12	79.52	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.65	12.28	69.20	1.40
265	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	2.24	82.61	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	28.87	13.92	68.61	0.00
266	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	2.24	82.61	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	28.87	13.92	68.61	0.00
267	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	2.24	82.66	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08	28.87	13.93	68.59	0.00
268	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	2.21	82.11	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	28.73	13.12	68.94	0.00
269	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	2.21	82.11	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	28.73	13.12	68.94	0.00
270	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	2.21	82.15	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	28.73	13.12	68.93	0.10
271	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	2.28	84.07	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	29.19	12.40	68.02	0.00
272	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	2.28	84.07	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	29.19	12.40	68.02	0.00
273	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	2.28	84.10	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	29.19	12.41	68.00	0.00
274	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	2.26	83.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	29.10	11.21	68.23	0.00
275	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	2.26	83.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	29.10	11.21	68.23	0.00
276	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	2.26	83.88	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	29.10	11.21	68.22	0.00
277	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.97	72.98	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24	28.02	13.18	71.89	8.00
278	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	1.97	73.05	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.22	28.03	13.19	71.86	7.90
279	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.97	73.24	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.16	28.05	13.09	71.79	7.90
280	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.95	72.50	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.23	27.93	12.39	72.15	8.80
281	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	1.95	72.56	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.22	27.94	12.40	72.11	8.80
282	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.96	72.75	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14	27.96	12.42	72.05	10.00
283	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	2.00	74.61	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14	28.31	11.77	71.38	8.20
284	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	2.00	74.65	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12	28.31	11.77	71.36	6.60

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out, \%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym, \%}$ [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{II, \%}$ [%]	$PI_{III, \%}$ [%]	$T_{f, avg}$ [°C]	$q_{REmax, C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
285	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	2.01	74.81	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	28.33	11.78	71.31	5.50
286	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.99	74.43	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12	28.26	11.00	71.53	6.80
287	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.99	74.47	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	28.27	11.00	71.51	6.60
288	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	2.00	74.60	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	28.29	11.00	71.47	6.50

D.2.2. Night Zone

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Soreed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PDD_{avg} [%]	PMV_{out} [%]	PD_{avg} [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	PI_{in} [%]	PI_{in} [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$Q_{RP,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Condi [h]
1	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.45	12.50	56.64	0.00	37.03	64.83	95.55	24.65	22.07	34.16	0.00
2	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.44	11.97	55.48	0.20	30.97	74.17	96.78	24.38	29.96	34.25	0.00
3	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.52	13.73	63.47	0.00	27.35	53.54	92.89	24.99	22.48	33.68	0.00
4	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.46	12.71	57.00	0.00	34.26	61.45	95.27	24.69	21.18	34.17	0.00
5	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.45	12.31	57.63	0.00	30.89	70.79	96.07	24.45	26.91	34.29	0.00
6	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.52	13.90	63.20	0.00	27.67	52.38	92.69	25.01	21.62	33.73	0.00
7	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.49	13.61	59.22	0.00	38.80	55.76	92.01	24.86	19.66	33.89	0.00
8	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.46	12.72	59.18	0.00	30.34	67.73	95.39	24.52	25.99	34.08	0.00
9	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.55	14.80	64.94	0.00	26.89	49.01	87.36	25.17	19.99	33.45	0.00
10	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.51	14.08	59.86	0.00	34.83	53.97	88.75	24.93	18.52	33.83	0.00
11	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.48	13.15	61.05	0.00	29.96	63.28	94.55	24.63	23.42	34.07	0.00
12	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.56	15.23	65.98	0.00	26.83	48.01	83.78	25.24	18.87	33.43	0.00
13	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.45	12.26	57.97	0.00	3.00	62.78	97.29	24.17	20.68	38.57	0.00
14	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.49	12.38	61.38	0.00	1.82	61.12	98.86	24.13	25.76	38.43	0.00
15	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.48	12.87	59.81	0.00	2.88	52.54	97.46	24.35	20.89	38.39	0.00
16	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.45	12.16	54.29	0.00	2.94	63.66	97.46	24.14	19.59	38.74	0.00
17	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.48	12.25	59.02	0.00	1.77	63.66	99.04	24.14	23.55	38.63	0.00
18	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.47	12.80	56.74	0.00	2.88	54.73	96.50	24.34	19.84	38.54	0.00
19	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.48	12.96	59.89	0.00	2.86	56.30	95.27	24.33	18.32	38.42	0.00
20	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.50	12.90	63.40	0.00	3.90	57.01	98.86	24.24	22.24	38.32	0.00
21	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.50	13.53	61.30	0.00	2.76	49.82	93.35	24.48	18.55	38.24	0.00
22	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.48	13.01	56.30	0.00	2.85	56.92	93.17	24.35	17.00	38.53	0.00
23	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.50	12.86	60.77	0.00	1.85	59.37	97.90	24.29	20.49	38.50	0.00
24	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.50	13.52	58.14	0.00	2.76	52.36	91.86	24.48	17.18	38.37	0.00
25	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.18	12.29	41.38	0.00	65.27	47.97	82.47	23.82	22.39	36.54	0.00
26	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.16	11.86	40.26	0.00	56.83	51.79	83.43	23.67	26.10	36.69	0.00
27	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.21	12.90	44.91	0.00	70.21	44.95	81.80	24.03	22.90	36.25	0.00
28	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.18	12.34	41.34	0.00	57.47	46.18	82.35	23.80	22.02	36.56	0.00
29	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.16	11.98	41.22	0.00	44.89	47.22	83.35	23.70	24.29	36.72	0.00
30	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.21	12.95	43.92	0.00	62.98	43.68	80.76	24.03	22.30	36.29	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RR,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Condh$ [h]
31	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.20	13.03	44.04	0.00	72.88	45.87	79.77	23.97	19.84	36.36	0.00
32	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.18	12.45	42.25	0.00	55.85	47.58	81.92	23.79	22.53	36.57	0.00
33	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.23	13.55	46.66	0.00	70.13	43.48	78.14	24.14	20.02	36.13	0.00
34	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.21	13.25	44.32	0.00	65.29	44.08	77.86	23.99	18.90	36.35	0.00
35	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.18	12.64	43.12	0.00	45.31	44.04	81.24	23.83	20.72	36.58	0.00
36	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.23	13.79	46.10	0.00	62.31	41.45	73.89	24.18	19.06	36.12	0.00
37	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.12	12.00	50.44	0.00	0.06	50.44	73.12	23.10	21.19	41.83	0.00
38	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.11	11.77	48.86	0.00	0.04	51.40	73.12	23.02	24.39	41.96	0.00
39	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.13	12.33	51.40	0.00	0.74	45.71	72.94	23.22	21.25	41.72	0.00
40	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.11	12.02	50.26	0.00	0.00	50.00	72.33	23.10	20.34	41.86	0.00
41	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.10	11.88	48.86	0.00	0.08	49.12	73.03	23.03	23.69	42.01	0.00
42	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.13	12.36	51.05	0.00	0.88	45.80	72.15	23.21	20.36	41.75	0.00
43	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.13	12.35	51.05	0.00	0.13	49.39	72.24	23.21	18.68	41.74	0.00
44	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.12	12.06	49.21	0.00	0.04	47.99	72.68	23.10	21.44	41.90	0.00
45	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.14	12.64	51.58	0.00	0.70	44.66	71.63	23.31	18.72	41.65	0.00
46	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.13	12.41	50.53	0.00	0.00	48.95	71.63	23.21	17.64	41.78	0.00
47	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.12	12.21	49.56	0.00	0.07	47.11	71.28	23.14	20.22	41.92	0.00
48	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.14	12.72	51.66	0.00	0.82	44.66	70.75	23.31	17.76	41.67	0.00
49	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.73	19.06	85.16	0.00	22.77	32.14	83.82	24.65	19.06	46.10	0.00
50	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.61	15.79	77.96	0.85	27.89	56.61	90.98	24.01	28.62	46.88	0.00
51	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.78	20.46	87.55	0.00	20.50	24.20	80.19	24.90	19.19	45.59	0.00
52	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.74	19.43	85.78	0.00	22.02	30.40	82.97	24.70	18.60	46.05	0.00
53	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.63	16.19	79.58	0.00	27.00	53.45	90.48	24.06	25.81	46.90	0.00
54	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.79	20.81	87.86	0.00	19.49	24.01	78.88	24.95	18.54	45.59	0.00
55	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.80	21.41	87.17	0.00	21.41	24.62	73.22	24.99	16.57	45.49	0.00
56	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.66	17.24	80.04	0.00	26.20	50.52	89.09	24.24	24.54	46.48	0.00
57	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.84	22.68	89.02	0.00	19.73	18.50	67.55	25.21	16.67	45.08	0.00
58	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.82	22.15	88.09	0.00	20.65	22.12	69.36	25.09	15.78	45.37	0.00
59	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.69	18.14	82.27	0.00	23.45	44.86	87.01	24.37	21.82	46.36	0.00
60	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.86	23.51	89.48	0.00	18.98	16.53	63.39	25.33	15.80	44.96	0.00
61	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.85	21.73	91.57	0.00	2.51	20.52	85.04	24.74	17.77	48.55	0.00
62	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.81	20.06	91.65	0.00	2.56	28.00	91.83	24.27	25.22	48.97	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{R,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Condh$ [h]
63	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.88	22.85	91.83	0.00	2.64	14.09	78.52	24.92	17.89	48.19	0.00
64	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.86	22.36	91.30	0.00	0.02	18.87	79.13	24.81	17.24	48.80	0.00
65	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.84	21.30	91.30	0.00	0.16	17.30	88.87	24.40	23.58	49.27	0.00
66	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.89	23.53	91.48	0.00	2.43	15.39	67.30	25.02	17.32	48.42	0.00
67	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.89	23.29	91.48	0.00	2.75	16.26	70.00	24.98	15.55	48.36	0.00
68	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.84	21.36	91.74	0.00	2.58	17.57	86.70	24.46	22.35	48.77	0.00
69	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.92	24.48	92.00	0.00	2.60	13.13	62.17	25.16	15.88	47.93	0.00
70	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.91	24.18	91.30	0.00	2.51	15.83	59.48	25.10	14.63	48.46	0.00
71	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.88	23.00	91.39	0.00	0.14	14.17	76.43	24.67	20.14	48.98	0.00
72	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.94	25.39	91.74	0.00	2.73	14.00	53.04	25.30	14.89	48.07	0.00
73	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.66	17.86	79.31	0.00	19.73	42.20	84.59	24.61	20.08	47.58	0.00
74	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.59	15.80	75.76	0.27	22.82	56.96	89.36	24.22	26.52	48.02	0.00
75	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.70	19.04	82.20	0.00	16.12	33.22	83.39	24.89	20.12	47.09	0.00
76	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.67	18.14	79.54	0.00	18.31	39.85	83.51	24.64	19.53	47.57	0.00
77	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.60	16.20	76.92	0.00	10.74	53.53	88.82	24.27	24.95	48.05	0.00
78	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.71	19.34	82.85	0.00	15.47	33.99	80.81	24.94	19.44	47.09	0.00
79	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.71	19.57	81.46	0.00	17.79	34.72	78.84	24.90	17.50	47.16	0.00
80	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.63	16.99	77.11	0.00	21.34	50.98	88.29	24.45	23.19	47.73	0.00
81	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.75	20.56	83.28	0.00	15.46	30.71	75.18	25.13	17.60	46.76	0.00
82	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.73	20.07	81.50	0.00	16.37	34.10	75.14	24.98	16.76	47.09	0.00
83	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.65	17.69	78.54	0.00	19.20	45.13	86.55	24.56	21.32	47.65	0.00
84	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.76	21.11	84.24	0.00	14.65	29.40	70.60	25.22	16.86	46.70	0.00
85	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.72	19.57	79.39	0.00	0.57	30.87	78.61	24.56	19.03	50.61	0.00
86	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.70	18.68	79.83	0.00	0.21	32.78	85.83	24.27	25.20	50.94	0.00
87	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.75	20.38	79.83	0.00	0.63	28.52	77.04	24.74	19.49	50.32	0.00
88	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.73	19.92	78.35	0.00	0.13	30.70	76.87	24.60	18.48	50.76	0.00
89	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.71	19.19	78.87	0.00	0.23	31.57	81.74	24.35	23.57	51.10	0.00
90	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.76	20.81	79.13	0.00	0.59	29.39	71.22	24.80	18.92	50.45	0.00
91	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.75	20.73	79.65	0.00	0.51	28.78	71.74	24.77	17.36	50.41	0.00
92	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.73	19.67	79.83	0.00	0.19	29.30	82.61	24.46	22.15	50.79	0.00
93	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.77	21.44	80.09	0.00	0.59	27.57	68.00	24.93	17.69	50.18	0.00
94	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.77	21.34	78.70	0.00	0.50	29.57	66.52	24.87	16.42	50.49	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PDD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{d50\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RR,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
95	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.74	20.29	79.22	0.00	0.21	29.91	75.83	24.57	20.07	50.93	0.00
96	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.79	22.09	79.39	0.00	0.54	28.70	63.13	25.02	16.72	50.27	0.00
97	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.78	19.63	87.64	4.18	27.76	23.77	71.15	24.08	33.04	29.98	0.00
98	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.55	13.68	63.80	19.90	43.41	74.78	93.29	22.83	35.65	31.22	0.00
99	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.82	20.90	89.18	5.01	21.23	19.69	63.31	24.32	33.18	29.63	0.00
100	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.80	20.46	87.84	3.62	27.25	21.84	64.40	24.24	31.95	29.92	0.00
101	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.58	14.31	71.37	13.48	43.58	68.55	92.73	22.99	34.48	31.23	0.00
102	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.84	21.66	89.20	4.07	20.22	18.53	57.01	24.47	32.06	29.61	0.00
103	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.88	23.28	89.56	1.11	26.19	19.11	46.80	24.66	29.27	29.41	0.00
104	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.63	15.43	77.16	4.47	38.99	58.56	88.79	23.20	31.58	30.85	0.00
105	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.91	24.45	90.65	1.17	19.75	16.09	39.63	24.86	29.43	29.14	0.00
106	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.92	24.84	90.31	0.53	24.16	18.17	38.92	24.90	27.71	29.26	0.00
107	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.67	16.51	81.57	2.39	34.76	46.89	86.39	23.43	30.29	30.77	0.00
108	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.95	26.01	91.50	0.55	18.20	15.25	34.24	25.11	27.84	29.01	0.00
109	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.82	20.46	92.54	0.82	0.16	12.21	75.67	24.00	33.65	31.55	0.00
110	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.72	16.97	93.20	9.30	0.16	32.04	95.33	23.13	36.45	32.16	0.00
111	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.87	22.13	92.87	0.86	0.06	9.30	52.68	24.22	34.08	31.12	0.00
112	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.84	21.31	92.38	0.12	0.21	12.33	60.34	24.17	32.39	31.66	0.00
113	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.76	18.27	92.99	1.52	0.05	18.31	93.53	23.39	35.17	32.38	0.00
114	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.89	23.01	92.75	0.25	0.09	10.61	43.47	24.40	32.67	31.27	0.00
115	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.88	22.84	92.75	0.04	0.09	10.04	44.57	24.45	29.68	31.24	0.00
116	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.77	18.61	93.57	0.57	0.12	15.81	91.56	23.53	32.52	31.91	0.00
117	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.93	24.53	93.08	0.04	0.05	8.19	33.06	24.66	29.99	30.84	0.00
118	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.92	24.10	92.59	0.00	0.12	10.32	35.68	24.69	27.93	31.27	0.00
119	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.82	20.25	93.08	0.00	0.07	13.07	78.41	23.84	30.74	32.07	0.00
120	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.96	25.96	93.24	0.00	0.05	8.85	28.80	24.93	28.20	30.88	0.00
121	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.73	20.04	80.34	8.27	31.43	24.59	56.20	24.02	33.98	30.78	0.00
122	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.55	14.63	67.32	34.32	41.18	56.60	83.19	22.94	37.83	31.84	0.00
123	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.77	20.97	82.17	8.54	24.49	20.24	52.09	24.23	34.24	30.53	0.00
124	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.75	20.74	80.55	6.41	30.20	23.84	52.88	24.16	32.90	30.74	0.00
125	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.57	15.30	70.02	25.57	40.77	47.81	81.70	23.10	36.66	31.82	0.00
126	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.78	21.69	82.42	6.41	24.87	19.77	47.66	24.36	32.98	30.52	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PDD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RR,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Condh$ [h]
127	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.82	23.27	83.13	2.64	28.89	19.56	43.52	24.56	29.87	30.34	0.00
128	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.62	16.68	73.37	7.73	34.91	41.05	76.31	23.38	33.70	31.50	0.00
129	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.84	24.00	84.21	2.73	24.86	17.45	39.94	24.71	29.95	30.16	0.00
130	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.85	24.58	83.40	0.75	28.32	18.81	38.73	24.78	28.27	30.23	0.00
131	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.66	17.79	75.08	4.24	33.75	33.98	72.28	23.59	31.88	31.40	0.00
132	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.87	25.35	84.49	0.79	24.56	16.72	35.41	24.94	28.33	30.06	0.00
133	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.74	20.19	86.81	1.84	0.00	18.80	54.61	23.87	34.65	32.55	0.00
134	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.65	16.78	85.50	18.07	0.04	24.91	84.97	23.06	37.06	33.11	0.00
135	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.77	21.43	87.22	2.13	0.00	18.23	45.88	24.04	35.02	32.23	0.00
136	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.76	21.04	85.54	0.74	0.00	18.72	45.92	24.02	33.46	32.62	0.00
137	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.68	17.86	83.12	5.61	0.01	21.34	78.74	23.27	35.96	33.25	0.00
138	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.80	22.34	86.11	0.74	0.00	18.52	40.35	24.21	33.78	32.32	0.00
139	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.80	22.36	87.30	0.45	0.00	18.35	42.20	24.32	30.35	32.29	0.00
140	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.69	18.38	85.91	3.07	0.03	20.24	76.28	23.49	32.87	32.94	0.00
141	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.83	23.54	87.79	0.45	0.00	18.11	37.65	24.48	30.58	32.02	0.00
142	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.82	23.57	86.24	0.00	0.00	18.44	37.53	24.53	28.60	32.29	0.00
143	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.73	19.75	84.15	0.45	0.02	19.91	57.97	23.76	30.86	33.01	0.00
144	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.85	24.81	86.85	0.00	0.00	18.19	34.62	24.70	28.88	32.04	0.00
145	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.32	43.29	96.17	0.00	9.51	21.22	43.55	25.77	22.26	57.75	0.00
146	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	1.31	42.78	95.16	0.00	12.84	25.93	44.42	25.59	26.27	57.83	0.00
147	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.35	44.24	96.83	0.00	7.68	17.68	42.35	25.93	22.34	57.40	0.00
148	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.33	43.64	96.17	0.00	9.64	20.39	42.88	25.80	21.50	57.69	0.20
149	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	1.31	43.18	95.23	0.00	14.09	25.22	43.91	25.63	23.91	57.77	0.30
150	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.36	44.66	96.65	0.00	7.59	16.66	41.12	25.97	21.49	57.34	0.00
151	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.40	46.68	96.83	0.00	7.99	16.98	38.90	26.20	19.29	56.76	0.00
152	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.38	45.95	95.83	0.00	11.60	22.82	40.93	25.99	23.04	56.90	0.00
153	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.42	47.42	96.95	0.00	7.15	14.59	37.22	26.33	19.31	56.50	0.00
154	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.43	47.74	97.04	0.00	7.81	15.91	37.13	26.34	18.34	56.50	0.00
155	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.40	46.99	95.80	0.00	12.68	21.37	39.31	26.12	21.25	56.67	0.00
156	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.44	48.48	97.17	0.00	6.71	13.76	35.26	26.47	18.34	56.26	0.00
157	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.30	41.45	99.59	0.00	0.00	7.05	47.60	25.50	19.70	61.14	1.70
158	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	1.30	41.29	99.55	0.00	0.00	10.73	48.50	25.38	22.10	61.04	1.40

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RR,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
159	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.33	42.65	99.88	0.00	0.00	4.96	43.83	25.66	18.86	60.65	1.00
160	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.31	41.97	99.59	0.00	0.00	6.64	44.53	25.55	18.59	61.19	1.60
161	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	1.31	42.08	99.55	0.00	0.01	7.70	46.42	25.44	20.83	61.14	1.20
162	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.34	43.17	99.84	0.00	0.00	5.37	41.13	25.71	18.07	60.75	1.00
163	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.36	43.96	99.71	0.00	0.00	5.98	40.93	25.79	17.37	60.52	1.40
164	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	1.35	43.93	99.55	0.00	0.00	8.44	44.86	25.67	19.99	60.44	1.20
165	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.38	45.13	99.92	0.00	0.00	4.51	36.58	25.94	17.15	60.10	0.30
166	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.38	44.89	99.84	0.00	0.00	6.02	36.38	25.90	16.16	60.46	1.70
167	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.38	45.10	99.55	0.00	0.00	5.33	39.70	25.79	18.18	60.41	1.10
168	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.40	46.10	99.92	0.00	0.00	4.83	31.95	26.06	16.02	60.06	0.50
169	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.28	41.54	94.78	0.00	25.23	24.65	45.68	25.77	21.47	59.04	0.00
170	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	1.26	41.06	93.89	0.00	27.65	27.31	46.40	25.69	23.37	59.13	0.00
171	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.30	42.25	95.02	0.00	21.23	22.62	45.27	25.92	21.46	58.75	0.00
172	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.28	41.89	94.76	0.00	24.01	24.18	45.38	25.82	20.64	58.98	0.00
173	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	1.27	41.44	94.03	0.00	27.40	26.37	46.17	25.73	21.76	59.09	0.00
174	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.30	42.56	95.21	0.00	20.07	21.88	45.01	25.96	20.53	58.71	0.00
175	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.33	43.82	94.87	0.00	24.12	22.26	43.29	26.11	18.68	58.39	0.00
176	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.31	43.29	94.27	0.00	26.31	25.16	44.48	26.01	20.30	58.51	0.00
177	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.35	44.51	95.19	0.00	20.27	19.39	43.08	26.25	18.76	58.13	0.00
178	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.35	44.56	94.87	0.00	23.32	21.33	42.89	26.22	17.67	58.23	0.20
179	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.33	44.08	94.36	0.00	25.95	24.22	43.40	26.13	18.88	58.35	0.10
180	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.36	45.22	95.36	0.00	19.23	18.83	41.73	26.35	17.74	57.99	0.00
181	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.27	40.71	97.30	0.00	0.67	16.35	49.94	25.48	19.58	62.23	1.00
182	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	1.27	40.70	97.21	0.00	0.66	16.47	49.82	25.46	21.20	62.22	1.30
183	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.30	41.72	97.83	0.00	0.63	14.46	46.87	25.65	18.93	61.85	0.60
184	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.28	41.10	97.01	0.00	0.74	15.65	47.77	25.52	18.37	62.26	1.80
185	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	1.28	41.22	97.13	0.00	0.74	15.40	47.15	25.51	19.95	62.28	1.40
186	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.30	42.11	97.83	0.00	0.69	14.09	43.26	25.70	17.93	61.91	0.70
187	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.32	42.78	97.62	0.00	0.61	14.67	45.19	25.76	17.16	61.76	1.70
188	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	1.32	42.67	97.38	0.00	0.61	15.12	46.29	25.71	18.97	61.80	1.20
189	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.34	43.62	97.99	0.00	0.59	13.72	42.24	25.90	16.93	61.45	0.40
190	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.33	43.41	97.62	0.00	0.67	14.22	41.29	25.84	16.24	61.73	1.50

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asy\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{f, max, c}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
191	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.33	43.41	97.34	0.00	0.67	14.63	42.07	25.81	17.94	61.78	0.70
192	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.35	44.28	98.16	0.00	0.63	13.72	39.08	25.99	15.81	61.43	0.40
193	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.14	34.18	95.72	38.10	1.85	11.28	41.57	23.31	40.57	28.03	0.00
194	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.92	26.86	86.39	47.02	16.03	47.69	68.30	22.00	42.70	29.37	0.00
195	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.16	34.93	96.20	39.00	1.35	8.96	37.69	23.42	40.61	27.87	0.00
196	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.17	35.47	96.07	33.56	1.89	9.31	36.15	23.54	39.63	27.90	0.00
197	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.95	27.81	88.96	42.02	14.00	43.99	66.56	22.17	41.48	29.24	0.00
198	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.19	36.21	96.80	34.66	1.31	7.17	31.36	23.66	39.68	27.75	0.00
199	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.31	41.74	98.19	20.64	1.40	4.16	19.30	24.38	36.40	27.00	0.00
200	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.08	32.74	92.20	21.96	6.76	28.78	54.18	22.91	38.45	28.40	0.00
201	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.32	42.28	98.37	21.17	1.28	3.73	17.05	24.45	36.42	26.90	0.00
202	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.37	44.55	98.61	15.93	1.38	3.73	14.76	24.80	34.88	26.69	0.00
203	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.14	34.97	93.99	17.20	5.58	23.19	47.66	23.26	36.62	28.09	0.00
204	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.38	45.07	98.77	16.09	1.18	3.04	12.74	24.87	34.93	26.60	0.00
205	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.06	29.89	99.70	26.54	0.00	0.49	55.35	23.02	40.21	29.98	0.00
206	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.95	25.75	99.18	51.01	0.00	28.35	73.84	22.23	41.13	30.54	0.00
207	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.11	31.88	99.73	30.37	0.00	0.08	37.17	23.25	40.53	29.50	0.00
208	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.10	31.24	99.70	17.29	0.00	0.22	44.76	23.24	39.20	29.95	0.00
209	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.99	27.15	99.70	31.98	0.00	14.45	71.27	22.50	39.77	30.58	0.00
210	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.15	33.39	99.73	19.80	0.00	0.14	22.26	23.50	39.38	29.50	0.00
211	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.19	35.41	99.95	9.75	0.00	0.03	22.17	23.88	35.83	29.22	0.00
212	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	1.06	29.97	99.73	10.40	0.00	9.91	64.77	22.99	36.52	29.96	0.00
213	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.23	37.16	100.00	11.31	0.00	0.03	12.07	24.08	36.09	28.87	0.00
214	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.25	38.02	100.00	2.87	0.00	0.14	11.80	24.26	34.42	29.00	0.00
215	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.11	32.16	99.73	4.26	0.00	2.05	51.37	23.37	34.59	29.84	0.00
216	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.28	39.71	100.00	3.09	0.00	0.03	8.57	24.45	34.50	28.71	0.00
217	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.34	43.17	96.69	54.55	7.24	9.47	24.14	23.97	43.08	26.84	0.00
218	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	1.16	36.25	92.52	70.73	11.38	27.64	46.33	22.77	45.95	27.90	0.00
219	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.35	43.68	97.38	54.73	4.62	8.23	22.04	24.07	43.12	26.74	0.00
220	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.37	44.44	96.98	51.72	6.70	8.98	22.06	24.21	42.22	26.72	0.00
221	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	1.19	37.25	93.79	66.43	9.66	25.11	44.19	22.94	44.72	27.77	0.00
222	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.38	44.93	97.43	51.87	4.25	7.62	19.58	24.29	42.24	26.63	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asy\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{R,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
223	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.49	50.06	97.27	39.54	6.79	6.48	16.24	25.04	38.83	26.00	0.00
224	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.32	42.34	94.98	48.46	7.75	18.51	35.37	23.79	40.61	27.05	0.00
225	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.50	50.47	97.84	39.90	4.12	5.45	14.52	25.12	38.87	25.93	0.00
226	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.55	52.47	97.53	31.04	6.05	5.49	13.67	25.45	37.16	25.76	0.00
227	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.37	44.41	96.07	40.40	6.89	15.37	32.03	24.14	38.53	26.78	0.00
228	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.56	52.86	98.09	31.22	3.81	5.06	12.40	25.52	37.20	25.70	0.00
229	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.26	38.89	98.91	48.74	0.00	4.64	22.28	23.71	42.61	28.59	0.00
230	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	1.14	33.71	99.02	67.34	0.00	11.17	50.93	22.87	44.64	29.28	0.00
231	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.29	40.17	99.13	50.00	0.38	3.90	15.76	23.89	42.74	28.34	0.00
232	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.29	40.45	98.74	42.03	0.00	4.29	17.80	23.93	41.58	28.51	0.00
233	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	1.17	35.05	98.69	57.21	0.00	5.57	46.70	23.08	42.98	29.23	0.00
234	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.32	41.75	99.04	42.82	0.41	3.63	13.79	24.12	41.67	28.29	0.00
235	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.39	45.02	99.07	33.72	0.00	3.74	13.98	24.68	38.23	27.86	0.00
236	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	1.26	38.90	99.07	45.69	0.00	4.92	36.59	23.79	39.46	28.60	0.00
237	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.41	46.07	99.21	34.46	0.34	3.22	11.31	24.82	38.28	27.66	0.00
238	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.44	47.60	98.91	24.66	0.00	3.50	11.88	25.06	36.71	27.65	0.00
239	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.31	41.06	98.80	34.05	0.00	3.80	25.51	24.12	37.37	28.43	0.00
240	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.46	48.65	99.04	24.69	0.40	3.47	9.78	25.20	36.78	27.49	0.00
241	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	2.37	87.05	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.45	20.92	63.14	0.00
242	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	2.41	87.99	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.58	21.29	62.63	0.00
243	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	2.37	87.07	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.45	20.89	63.13	0.00
244	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	2.37	87.31	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.44	20.36	63.06	0.00
245	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	2.41	88.26	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.56	20.70	62.55	0.00
246	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	2.37	87.33	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.44	20.34	63.05	0.00
247	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	2.47	89.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.03	18.59	61.71	0.00
248	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	2.52	90.76	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.19	18.97	61.14	0.00
249	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	2.47	89.84	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.04	18.58	61.71	0.00
250	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	2.49	90.52	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.14	17.81	61.39	0.00
251	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	2.54	91.44	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.30	18.16	60.80	0.00
252	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	2.49	90.53	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.14	17.81	61.38	0.00
253	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	2.12	79.80	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.27	17.87	69.83	0.40
254	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	2.15	80.90	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.37	18.11	69.41	0.20

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RR,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
255	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	2.13	80.02	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.30	17.76	69.73	0.10
256	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	2.12	79.80	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.24	17.18	69.75	0.10
257	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	2.15	80.90	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.34	17.45	69.33	0.30
258	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	2.12	80.02	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.27	17.07	69.66	0.10
259	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	2.20	82.80	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.72	16.12	68.60	0.00
260	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	2.24	83.95	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.84	16.37	68.12	0.00
261	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	2.21	82.93	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.74	16.06	68.54	0.00
262	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	2.21	83.31	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.78	15.21	68.30	0.00
263	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	2.25	84.46	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.89	15.49	67.83	0.00
264	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	2.22	83.42	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.79	15.16	68.26	0.00
265	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	2.30	84.75	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.22	21.15	64.76	0.00
266	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	2.30	84.75	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.22	21.15	64.75	0.00
267	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	2.30	84.77	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.23	21.14	64.74	0.00
268	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	2.30	84.97	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.21	20.39	64.67	0.00
269	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	2.30	84.97	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.21	20.39	64.67	0.00
270	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	2.30	84.99	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.21	20.40	64.66	0.00
271	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	2.37	87.04	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.71	18.45	63.73	0.00
272	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	2.37	87.04	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.71	18.45	63.73	0.00
273	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	2.37	87.06	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.71	18.45	63.72	0.00
274	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	2.38	87.62	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.78	17.40	63.48	0.00
275	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	2.38	87.62	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.78	17.40	63.48	0.00
276	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	2.38	87.63	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.79	17.40	63.48	0.00
277	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	2.14	80.08	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.40	19.25	70.02	0.80
278	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	2.14	80.10	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.40	19.25	70.00	1.00
279	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	2.15	80.30	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.43	19.15	69.93	0.50
280	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	2.14	80.08	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.36	18.59	69.93	0.60
281	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	2.14	80.10	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.37	18.59	69.92	1.10
282	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	2.14	80.30	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.39	18.52	69.85	0.20
283	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	2.20	82.46	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.81	17.25	69.08	0.00
284	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	2.20	82.48	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.81	17.25	69.07	0.00
285	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	2.21	82.62	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.83	17.22	69.02	0.00
286	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	2.21	82.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.85	16.34	68.85	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$PI_{in\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RR,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]
287	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	2.21	82.85	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.85	16.34	68.84	0.00
288	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	2.21	82.98	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.87	16.32	68.80	0.00

D.2.3. Aggregated

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	PMV_{out} [%]	PD_{asy} [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	PI_{H1} [%]	PI_{H2} [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{RFmax,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Cond _h [h]	$q_{C,RF}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	SEER [-]	Q_{annex} [%]
1	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.51	13.12	54.54	0.00	58.29	62.23	93.10	24.15	4.84	34.98	0.00	21.22	246.52	10.57	0.00
2	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.45	11.65	52.87	0.15	80.53	74.96	96.21	23.65	5.21	35.44	0.00	28.20	448.08	7.63	0.00
3	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.58	14.73	61.60	0.00	46.75	50.62	88.80	24.54	5.35	34.43	0.00	21.86	233.78	10.52	0.00
4	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.50	13.04	54.66	0.00	57.77	61.28	93.31	24.14	4.84	35.08	0.00	20.16	215.02	10.73	0.00
5	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.44	11.72	53.80	0.00	93.45	73.01	95.61	23.67	4.79	35.56	0.00	25.27	421.71	7.38	0.00
6	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.57	14.59	61.04	0.00	50.84	51.04	89.27	24.51	5.36	34.56	0.00	20.79	209.40	10.56	0.00
7	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.55	14.38	57.21	0.00	57.40	53.40	88.71	24.43	4.73	34.68	0.00	18.74	224.74	10.97	0.00
8	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.48	12.45	56.37	0.00	71.49	69.54	94.83	23.87	5.06	35.22	0.00	24.14	424.30	7.76	0.00
9	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.62	15.97	63.13	0.00	43.39	45.20	83.08	24.79	5.14	34.17	0.00	19.26	206.77	11.24	0.00
10	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.56	14.53	57.24	0.00	54.65	52.66	87.01	24.46	4.59	34.70	0.00	17.41	200.31	10.99	0.00
11	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.48	12.62	57.17	0.00	80.43	66.80	94.30	23.93	4.68	35.30	0.00	21.47	391.05	7.74	0.00
12	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.62	16.08	63.65	0.00	45.77	45.13	81.42	24.82	5.20	34.22	0.00	17.88	191.49	10.94	0.00
13	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.42	11.33	48.19	0.00	24.21	69.11	96.87	23.85	5.49	37.96	0.00	20.57	165.55	9.03	0.00
14	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.43	11.12	50.07	0.25	33.30	70.59	98.36	23.75	5.67	37.90	0.00	27.88	282.45	6.92	0.00
15	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.48	12.39	50.82	0.00	18.00	59.41	96.43	24.19	5.83	37.60	0.00	20.98	141.39	9.44	0.00
16	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.41	11.10	45.14	0.00	25.40	69.86	96.83	23.79	5.50	38.18	0.00	19.33	143.38	9.20	0.00
17	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.42	10.89	48.23	0.06	31.43	71.07	98.28	23.72	5.57	38.14	0.00	25.03	259.40	6.81	0.00
18	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.46	12.18	48.62	0.00	18.16	61.00	95.73	24.13	5.92	37.79	0.00	19.80	126.75	9.37	0.00
19	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.45	12.05	50.44	0.00	24.68	63.23	95.34	24.05	5.31	37.78	0.00	18.00	145.92	9.66	0.00
20	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.46	11.65	52.03	0.00	33.47	67.10	98.34	23.91	5.50	37.76	0.00	23.61	266.82	7.06	0.00
21	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.50	13.09	52.79	0.00	17.75	55.13	93.45	24.36	5.66	37.43	0.00	18.41	130.34	9.78	0.00
22	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.44	11.95	48.19	0.00	24.64	63.30	94.16	24.03	5.24	37.93	0.00	16.51	127.54	9.79	0.00
23	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.44	11.53	50.54	0.00	28.19	67.68	97.60	23.93	5.30	37.95	0.00	20.89	246.77	6.95	0.00
24	Ulaanbaatar	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.49	12.95	50.43	0.00	16.49	56.90	92.64	24.32	5.66	37.60	0.00	16.86	117.86	9.72	0.00
25	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.25	11.58	41.32	0.00	110.04	55.50	85.08	23.42	7.55	37.28	0.00	21.09	166.40	9.73	0.00
26	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.22	11.05	39.58	0.00	108.38	59.48	86.02	23.26	7.85	37.51	0.00	25.93	268.23	7.45	0.00
27	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.29	12.52	44.69	0.00	99.69	51.86	83.77	23.74	8.03	36.87	0.00	21.81	148.41	9.79	0.00
28	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.23	11.49	40.99	0.00	102.90	53.51	84.83	23.33	7.53	37.37	0.00	20.52	144.93	9.88	0.00
29	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.21	11.06	39.94	0.00	101.42	55.40	85.49	23.20	7.68	37.61	0.00	23.58	244.75	7.42	0.00
30	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.28	12.39	43.76	0.00	99.89	50.76	82.99	23.65	7.86	36.98	0.00	21.12	132.08	9.85	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	PMV_{out} [%]	PD_{asym} [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	PI_{H} [%]	PI_{III} [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{remax,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Condh [h]	$q_{c,RF}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	SEER [-]	$Q_{summer,3\%C}$ [%]
31	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.27	12.30	43.54	0.00	109.54	52.90	82.70	23.61	7.47	37.08	0.00	18.48	147.86	10.12	0.00
32	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.24	11.58	41.69	0.00	103.37	56.46	84.75	23.41	7.72	37.37	0.00	22.10	249.32	7.60	0.00
33	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.31	13.15	46.01	0.00	98.11	50.04	80.85	23.88	7.92	36.73	0.00	18.96	133.36	10.14	0.00
34	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.27	12.34	43.49	0.00	107.33	51.56	81.40	23.57	7.33	37.12	0.00	17.45	130.32	10.13	0.00
35	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.23	11.65	41.75	0.00	98.33	52.75	84.07	23.38	7.42	37.45	0.00	19.68	228.63	7.59	0.00
36	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.31	13.18	45.41	0.00	95.88	48.32	78.50	23.84	7.67	36.79	0.00	17.93	119.68	10.12	0.00
37	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.11	11.10	48.69	0.00	25.18	52.18	75.33	22.89	7.10	41.08	0.00	20.55	107.53	8.64	0.00
38	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.09	10.86	48.09	0.00	24.49	53.18	75.15	22.80	7.14	41.22	0.00	25.36	166.05	6.73	0.00
39	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.14	11.61	50.37	0.00	21.17	49.20	75.50	23.09	7.23	40.87	0.00	20.81	95.23	8.59	0.00
40	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.09	11.06	48.44	0.00	27.84	50.80	74.06	22.77	6.98	41.21	0.00	19.61	94.91	8.62	0.00
41	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.08	10.88	47.98	0.00	30.31	50.60	73.92	22.69	7.00	41.38	0.00	23.53	152.32	6.68	0.00
42	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.12	11.54	50.28	0.00	23.25	48.24	74.33	22.97	7.10	41.00	0.00	19.82	85.38	8.50	0.00
43	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.13	11.45	49.78	0.00	23.91	50.96	75.00	23.03	7.04	40.96	0.00	17.85	96.32	8.85	0.00
44	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.11	11.15	48.53	0.00	26.63	50.65	75.09	22.90	7.09	41.14	0.00	21.65	158.55	6.79	0.00
45	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.15	11.92	51.00	0.00	20.11	47.66	74.51	23.20	7.18	40.78	0.00	18.09	86.08	8.83	0.00
46	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.11	11.44	49.52	0.00	24.80	49.49	73.93	22.93	6.83	41.07	0.00	16.68	85.37	8.85	0.00
47	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.09	11.20	48.84	0.00	28.35	48.88	73.46	22.84	6.80	41.25	0.00	19.47	144.04	6.75	0.00
48	Ulaanbaatar	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.14	11.90	51.13	0.00	21.88	46.58	73.36	23.11	6.94	40.88	0.00	16.86	77.39	8.78	0.00
49	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.78	20.57	83.73	0.00	40.74	31.81	78.21	24.38	4.24	46.91	0.00	17.63	367.03	10.98	0.00
50	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.65	16.56	77.31	0.45	52.10	57.45	88.76	23.62	4.22	48.04	0.00	26.81	542.88	8.79	0.00
51	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.84	22.50	86.31	0.00	35.61	21.94	71.97	24.70	4.56	46.28	0.00	17.81	354.56	10.88	0.00
52	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.78	20.58	83.92	0.00	41.48	31.50	78.23	24.41	3.47	46.97	0.00	17.04	328.26	11.16	0.00
53	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.65	16.68	78.54	0.00	54.68	55.68	88.27	23.68	3.41	48.14	0.00	23.95	498.90	8.82	0.00
54	Toronto	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.84	22.49	86.35	0.00	35.82	22.79	71.87	24.73	3.94	46.36	0.00	17.12	316.43	11.11	0.00
55	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.85	22.93	85.68	0.00	38.02	24.03	68.18	24.78	4.25	46.32	0.00	15.34	345.60	11.04	0.00
56	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.70	18.12	79.56	0.00	47.28	51.18	85.32	23.94	4.08	47.61	0.00	22.97	514.65	8.91	0.00
57	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.89	24.65	87.54	0.00	34.26	17.45	61.03	25.05	4.49	45.81	0.00	15.47	327.61	11.17	0.00
58	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.85	23.29	86.33	0.00	38.33	22.79	66.17	24.87	3.42	46.31	0.00	14.39	311.73	11.19	0.00
59	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.71	18.61	81.08	0.00	47.77	47.78	84.00	24.07	3.27	47.60	0.00	20.10	471.62	9.00	0.00
60	Toronto	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.90	25.05	87.86	0.00	34.23	16.92	58.69	25.15	3.89	45.80	0.00	14.51	296.20	11.34	0.00
61	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.78	19.69	84.62	0.00	23.23	36.18	87.22	24.35	4.86	48.32	0.00	18.14	269.85	10.24	0.00
62	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.71	17.61	81.62	0.05	33.41	47.43	92.28	23.81	4.81	48.92	0.00	25.60	427.06	7.85	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	PMV_{out} [%]	PD_{asym} [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	PI_{in} [%]	PI_{in} [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Cond _h [h]	$q_{c,ref}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	SEER [-]	$Q_{summer,3\%C}$ [%]
63	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.83	21.44	85.69	0.00	20.75	24.04	80.81	24.66	4.90	47.78	0.00	18.04	257.12	10.26	0.00
64	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.78	19.89	84.03	0.00	13.52	35.71	84.55	24.40	4.39	48.54	0.00	16.85	240.93	10.40	0.00
65	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.72	18.08	82.02	0.00	24.13	42.56	90.83	23.90	4.27	49.22	0.00	23.41	393.33	7.83	0.00
66	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.83	21.63	85.18	0.00	20.32	25.90	75.64	24.71	4.60	47.99	0.00	16.61	231.16	10.41	0.00
67	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.82	21.25	85.30	0.00	22.17	29.26	76.49	24.65	4.78	48.03	0.00	15.66	247.35	10.63	0.00
68	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.75	18.83	82.85	0.00	29.34	39.86	88.68	24.06	4.72	48.67	0.00	22.41	404.83	7.99	0.00
69	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.87	23.03	86.43	0.00	20.14	20.15	68.98	24.94	4.85	47.48	0.00	15.66	236.12	10.63	0.00
70	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.83	21.71	84.87	0.00	21.91	28.92	71.04	24.75	4.22	48.14	0.00	14.18	228.42	10.52	0.00
71	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.77	19.60	83.46	0.00	19.12	38.40	83.19	24.22	4.17	48.88	0.00	20.06	377.91	7.93	0.00
72	Toronto	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.88	23.47	86.00	0.00	20.02	21.59	64.16	25.04	4.48	47.61	0.00	14.29	216.78	10.65	0.00
73	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.68	18.14	76.53	0.00	45.45	43.73	83.02	24.24	6.91	48.51	0.00	17.78	305.69	10.53	0.00
74	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.59	15.65	73.82	0.13	57.87	59.30	89.03	23.76	7.22	49.23	0.00	25.02	431.01	8.63	0.00
75	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.73	19.66	80.19	0.00	37.95	34.53	80.88	24.58	7.40	47.93	0.00	17.90	275.68	10.87	0.00
76	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.68	18.14	76.17	0.00	44.56	42.95	82.69	24.24	6.55	48.57	0.00	17.30	276.18	10.57	0.00
77	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.60	15.77	74.25	0.00	43.17	56.54	88.87	23.79	6.79	49.32	0.00	23.15	394.94	8.68	0.00
78	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.73	19.68	80.20	0.00	39.00	35.20	79.57	24.59	7.15	47.99	0.00	17.35	252.19	10.83	0.00
79	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.72	19.72	78.94	0.00	42.05	36.85	77.96	24.55	6.88	48.12	0.00	15.35	274.68	10.95	0.00
80	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.63	16.84	75.16	0.00	55.23	54.01	87.25	24.04	7.31	48.92	0.00	21.95	379.92	9.33	0.00
81	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.77	21.12	81.17	0.00	36.19	31.07	74.07	24.85	7.37	47.61	0.00	15.49	244.97	11.41	0.00
82	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.73	19.98	78.26	0.00	40.05	36.17	75.88	24.60	6.50	48.12	0.00	14.61	246.69	11.09	0.00
83	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.64	17.17	75.87	0.00	56.33	50.41	86.05	24.12	6.81	48.94	0.00	19.77	365.08	8.94	0.00
84	Toronto	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.78	21.36	81.73	0.00	36.40	30.49	71.60	24.90	7.07	47.62	0.00	14.71	229.54	11.18	0.00
85	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.64	17.29	73.52	0.00	10.10	44.79	83.37	24.17	6.74	50.30	0.00	17.52	218.79	9.88	0.00
86	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.61	16.08	71.90	0.00	16.82	50.43	87.74	23.85	6.76	50.74	0.00	24.27	325.61	7.75	0.00
87	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.68	18.50	74.71	0.00	7.00	39.60	82.04	24.46	6.84	49.87	0.00	17.65	200.05	9.87	0.00
88	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.64	17.30	72.39	0.00	11.00	44.84	82.65	24.17	6.31	50.47	0.00	16.62	196.36	10.04	0.00
89	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.60	16.20	71.55	0.00	18.65	49.45	85.76	23.88	6.36	50.92	0.00	22.20	301.68	7.74	0.00
90	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.68	18.57	74.03	0.00	7.83	40.35	79.10	24.46	6.56	50.01	0.00	17.11	180.24	10.01	0.00
91	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.67	18.35	74.35	0.00	9.03	41.26	78.91	24.41	6.72	50.07	0.00	15.56	198.11	10.19	0.00
92	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.63	16.91	73.00	0.00	14.32	47.27	85.70	24.05	6.78	50.57	0.00	21.00	305.90	7.90	0.00
93	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.71	19.44	75.28	0.00	6.48	36.48	76.27	24.65	6.80	49.71	0.00	16.00	182.75	10.19	0.00
94	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.68	18.61	73.54	0.00	9.68	41.72	76.23	24.46	6.17	50.16	0.00	14.56	178.74	10.29	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{H\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{perm\max C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Condh [h]	$q_{c,RF}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	SEER [-]	$Q_{summer,3\%C}$ [%]
95	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.63	17.18	72.74	0.00	15.36	47.08	82.09	24.13	6.22	50.71	0.00	18.84	283.60	7.92	0.00
96	Toronto	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.71	19.69	74.51	0.00	6.95	37.26	73.72	24.70	6.35	49.80	0.00	14.98	166.32	10.27	0.00
97	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.80	20.07	85.17	2.09	59.73	25.64	71.89	23.86	4.67	30.86	0.00	29.93	1547.30	7.57	0.00
98	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.57	13.55	62.26	10.17	99.22	75.28	93.65	22.55	5.19	32.35	0.00	32.87	2290.66	5.98	0.00
99	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.85	21.65	87.26	2.51	43.63	19.17	63.63	24.13	5.05	30.46	0.00	30.27	1526.88	7.49	0.00
100	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.81	20.38	85.28	1.81	61.82	25.07	68.91	23.98	4.57	30.89	0.00	28.76	1416.75	7.56	0.00
101	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.58	13.86	68.85	6.89	109.81	72.26	93.32	22.71	4.67	32.42	0.00	31.28	2135.76	5.93	0.00
102	Madrid	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.85	21.93	87.23	2.04	44.09	19.04	61.07	24.24	5.04	30.51	0.00	29.13	1369.49	7.68	0.00
103	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.89	23.28	87.24	0.56	53.53	19.13	52.73	24.44	4.60	30.34	0.00	26.39	1437.52	7.72	0.00
104	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.63	15.09	74.79	2.28	83.16	63.40	90.09	22.96	5.08	32.01	0.00	28.95	2198.80	6.00	0.00
105	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.93	24.71	88.88	0.58	40.41	15.55	44.73	24.66	4.93	30.02	0.00	26.62	1417.81	7.66	0.00
106	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.91	24.16	87.79	0.26	53.49	18.83	48.20	24.63	4.40	30.29	0.00	24.74	1391.55	7.34	0.00
107	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.65	15.72	79.26	1.20	89.90	57.07	88.44	23.18	4.48	32.02	0.00	27.11	2067.74	5.94	0.00
108	Madrid	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.95	25.60	89.66	0.27	39.80	15.36	40.95	24.86	4.89	29.98	0.00	24.98	1321.11	7.58	0.00
109	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.74	18.03	85.26	0.41	19.08	33.03	83.52	23.72	5.47	31.65	0.00	32.29	1352.91	6.85	0.00
110	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.62	14.39	79.79	4.84	53.61	58.39	95.66	22.79	5.66	32.45	0.00	33.93	1935.29	5.51	0.00
111	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.80	19.85	86.59	0.43	15.27	22.50	69.13	24.00	5.77	31.18	0.00	31.49	1324.70	6.82	0.00
112	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.75	18.33	84.94	0.06	20.68	33.63	76.00	23.84	5.33	31.77	0.00	30.71	1261.23	6.75	0.00
113	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.63	14.93	79.80	0.91	62.06	51.76	94.72	22.98	5.39	32.66	0.00	32.08	1826.63	5.41	0.00
114	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.81	20.17	86.25	0.12	16.21	24.81	64.58	24.13	5.64	31.32	0.00	29.34	1243.09	6.74	0.00
115	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.80	20.09	86.15	0.02	16.89	25.19	64.54	24.18	5.30	31.33	0.00	28.58	1264.67	6.98	0.00
116	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.66	15.66	82.90	0.29	41.41	47.66	93.51	23.18	5.42	32.22	0.00	29.94	1879.01	5.48	0.00
117	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.85	21.88	87.37	0.02	13.87	17.21	54.96	24.44	5.49	30.90	0.00	27.56	1237.47	6.95	0.00
118	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.82	20.74	85.81	0.00	17.61	25.49	59.80	24.37	5.11	31.38	0.00	27.05	1185.33	6.87	0.00
119	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.68	16.45	82.96	0.00	47.46	46.19	86.87	23.42	5.07	32.37	0.00	27.91	1791.81	5.36	0.00
120	Madrid	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.87	22.66	87.44	0.00	14.44	18.34	51.86	24.64	5.37	30.95	0.00	25.27	1159.62	6.89	0.00
121	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	0.71	18.86	77.78	4.14	63.41	31.51	65.80	23.72	7.60	31.81	0.00	30.31	1498.74	7.21	0.00
122	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.53	13.57	65.63	17.32	106.97	64.77	86.59	22.63	7.88	33.03	0.00	32.88	2212.93	5.82	0.00
123	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	0.75	20.00	79.87	4.27	49.58	25.31	61.66	23.96	7.88	31.51	0.00	30.69	1487.79	7.04	0.00
124	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	0.72	19.14	77.61	3.20	61.91	31.16	64.59	23.81	7.22	31.83	0.00	29.19	1305.01	7.58	0.00
125	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.54	13.89	67.86	12.79	119.68	59.94	85.64	22.76	7.37	33.08	0.00	31.72	2058.83	5.79	0.00
126	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	0.76	20.26	79.77	3.20	51.57	25.48	59.80	24.05	7.50	31.55	0.00	29.44	1346.09	7.16	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PpD_{avg} [%]	PMV_{out} [%]	PD_{asym} [%]	OC_{RH} [°C/h]	PI_{in} [%]	PI_{in} [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{remax,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Condh [h]	$q_{c,RF}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	SEER [-]	$Q_{summer,3\%C}$ [%]
127	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	0.79	21.49	80.47	1.32	58.75	24.63	54.93	24.23	7.62	31.41	0.00	26.50	1364.04	7.40	0.00
128	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	0.59	15.14	71.54	3.86	93.34	53.80	82.10	23.05	7.87	32.74	0.00	29.11	2085.40	5.87	0.00
129	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	0.82	22.46	81.86	1.37	47.05	21.06	51.20	24.42	7.83	31.18	0.00	26.68	1337.77	7.33	0.00
130	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	0.80	22.24	80.66	0.38	57.04	24.12	52.06	24.40	7.13	31.37	0.00	24.76	1260.88	7.33	0.00
131	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	0.60	15.78	72.47	2.12	102.49	49.55	79.70	23.23	7.24	32.72	0.00	27.33	1960.43	5.80	0.00
132	Madrid	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	0.83	23.22	82.07	0.40	47.33	20.76	48.26	24.59	7.39	31.14	0.00	24.89	1238.12	7.28	0.00
133	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.65	17.13	80.58	0.92	31.22	37.94	70.63	23.57	7.43	32.70	0.00	32.97	1346.66	6.58	0.00
134	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.53	13.93	76.46	9.12	63.93	52.23	87.32	22.75	7.66	33.39	0.00	33.98	1898.78	5.38	0.00
135	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	0.69	18.40	81.48	1.07	26.94	32.36	65.00	23.79	7.59	32.34	0.00	31.77	1293.88	6.54	0.00
136	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.65	17.42	79.50	0.37	34.81	38.39	66.38	23.65	7.08	32.79	0.00	31.00	1246.05	6.54	0.00
137	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.55	14.41	75.11	2.81	74.87	50.10	84.17	22.90	7.15	33.52	0.00	32.01	1777.80	5.32	0.00
138	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	0.69	18.71	80.64	0.37	29.24	33.55	62.42	23.89	7.25	32.44	0.00	29.91	1210.39	6.49	0.00
139	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	0.69	18.84	81.62	0.23	29.39	32.59	62.11	23.98	7.37	32.44	0.00	29.39	1232.46	6.74	0.00
140	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.57	15.10	78.40	1.54	54.33	47.61	82.73	23.13	7.52	33.21	0.00	29.94	1797.93	5.42	0.00
141	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	0.73	20.07	82.55	0.23	27.19	28.21	57.91	24.19	7.53	32.13	0.00	27.63	1184.32	6.73	0.00
142	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	0.71	19.47	80.96	0.00	29.85	32.39	59.31	24.13	6.84	32.47	0.00	26.95	1152.59	6.63	0.00
143	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.59	15.79	77.52	0.23	63.56	46.74	73.48	23.34	6.85	33.30	0.00	27.29	1713.15	5.30	0.00
144	Madrid	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	0.74	20.69	82.05	0.00	26.38	28.99	55.92	24.35	6.98	32.17	0.00	25.76	1116.57	6.61	0.00
145	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.36	44.72	95.68	0.00	14.87	17.78	41.11	25.65	2.82	58.73	0.25	19.28	831.24	11.07	0.00
146	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	1.33	43.73	94.59	0.00	25.67	24.84	43.59	25.40	2.86	58.97	0.20	25.30	968.12	10.30	0.00
147	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.39	46.00	96.26	0.00	11.34	13.40	38.12	25.84	2.92	58.30	0.10	19.35	814.35	11.04	0.00
148	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.36	44.68	95.61	0.00	15.75	17.49	40.89	25.66	2.12	58.80	0.45	18.44	746.52	11.24	0.00
149	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	1.33	43.75	94.67	0.00	27.74	23.91	43.30	25.44	2.10	59.05	0.50	22.94	874.86	10.43	0.00
150	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.39	46.01	96.11	0.00	11.61	12.92	37.55	25.86	2.30	58.37	0.05	18.48	754.94	10.88	0.00
151	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.43	47.76	96.27	0.00	12.61	14.02	36.24	26.09	2.79	57.86	0.05	16.88	776.10	11.23	0.00
152	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.40	46.53	95.15	0.00	21.95	21.75	40.44	25.81	2.76	58.16	0.05	21.76	911.28	10.42	0.00
153	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.46	48.87	96.46	0.00	10.23	10.63	32.62	26.25	2.88	57.52	0.00	16.91	757.16	11.26	0.00
154	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.44	48.30	96.41	0.00	12.82	13.26	35.00	26.19	1.99	57.77	0.15	15.79	702.12	11.36	0.00
155	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.41	47.07	95.21	0.00	23.45	20.42	39.41	25.92	1.94	58.09	0.15	19.65	830.32	10.54	0.00
156	Tokyo	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.47	49.40	96.66	0.00	10.17	10.20	31.20	26.35	2.19	57.44	0.00	15.81	683.38	11.43	0.00
157	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.25	39.36	96.69	0.00	14.20	16.72	48.71	25.28	3.73	61.12	3.10	18.12	622.21	10.83	0.00
158	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	1.24	39.15	95.96	0.00	22.93	20.27	49.16	25.13	3.87	61.10	2.65	22.09	731.08	10.03	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{H\%}$ [%]	$PI_{III\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{remax,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Cond _h [h]	$q_{c,RF}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	SEER [-]	$Q_{summer,3\%C}$ [%]
159	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.29	41.08	97.32	0.00	10.19	10.76	45.60	25.52	4.03	60.51	1.95	17.50	593.62	10.95	0.00
160	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.25	39.47	96.60	0.00	14.70	16.33	47.19	25.32	3.19	61.23	3.45	16.96	560.65	10.96	0.00
161	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	1.25	39.36	95.88	0.00	21.06	18.30	48.09	25.18	3.20	61.26	2.95	20.45	668.70	10.08	0.00
162	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.29	41.18	97.20	0.00	10.59	11.33	44.20	25.56	3.62	60.65	2.55	16.64	544.60	10.96	0.00
163	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.30	41.69	96.99	0.00	12.78	13.71	44.43	25.61	3.63	60.52	2.45	15.83	579.45	11.05	0.00
164	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	1.29	41.46	96.32	0.00	20.52	17.44	46.52	25.45	3.78	60.53	1.75	19.98	690.15	10.16	0.00
165	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.34	43.29	97.52	0.00	9.63	9.03	40.46	25.82	3.91	59.99	0.60	15.62	559.62	11.09	0.00
166	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.31	42.20	97.09	0.00	12.83	13.37	41.89	25.71	3.09	60.52	2.30	14.59	525.36	11.17	0.00
167	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.31	42.04	96.36	0.00	18.66	15.68	43.63	25.56	3.07	60.58	1.80	18.13	635.14	10.19	0.00
168	Tokyo	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.35	43.81	97.47	0.00	9.74	9.12	37.72	25.92	3.45	60.01	1.10	14.50	510.94	11.19	0.00
169	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.28	41.50	93.88	0.00	41.68	23.42	45.81	25.53	4.72	60.29	1.20	18.43	709.74	11.02	0.00
170	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	1.26	40.82	93.16	0.00	49.97	27.41	46.90	25.41	5.37	60.48	1.20	22.94	785.81	10.49	0.00
171	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.31	42.62	94.34	0.00	30.51	20.01	44.45	25.73	5.11	59.89	0.40	18.45	677.39	11.11	0.00
172	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.28	41.48	93.98	0.00	42.43	23.12	45.72	25.54	4.62	60.34	1.95	17.51	633.87	11.22	0.00
173	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	1.26	40.86	93.29	0.00	52.28	26.43	46.86	25.43	5.15	60.54	2.50	20.97	713.95	10.57	0.00
174	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.31	42.58	94.56	0.00	30.42	19.53	44.27	25.74	4.78	59.96	1.70	17.49	640.08	10.74	0.00
175	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.33	43.59	94.04	0.00	37.38	20.68	43.23	25.87	4.68	59.70	0.25	15.97	650.99	11.22	0.00
176	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.31	42.81	93.59	0.00	45.77	25.02	45.12	25.74	5.23	59.93	0.50	19.49	726.96	10.63	0.00
177	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.36	44.62	94.54	0.00	28.42	17.24	41.75	26.06	5.03	59.35	0.15	16.04	621.97	11.31	0.00
178	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.34	43.94	94.13	0.00	37.29	20.08	42.91	25.95	4.43	59.65	0.40	14.89	584.60	11.37	0.00
179	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.32	43.20	93.73	0.00	46.67	23.83	44.38	25.82	4.92	59.89	0.50	17.66	661.92	10.71	0.00
180	Tokyo	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.36	44.95	94.77	0.00	27.84	16.65	40.84	26.13	4.69	59.32	0.15	14.96	560.69	11.46	0.00
181	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.19	37.24	92.22	0.00	15.23	23.35	50.80	25.21	5.29	62.45	3.95	17.35	543.11	10.70	0.00
182	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	1.19	37.23	91.83	0.00	17.88	23.74	50.77	25.19	5.49	62.46	3.90	20.28	592.77	10.20	0.00
183	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.23	38.68	92.86	0.00	12.45	20.29	48.97	25.47	5.67	61.94	1.90	17.06	508.96	10.77	0.00
184	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.19	37.28	91.93	0.00	15.27	22.94	49.62	25.23	4.97	62.55	4.50	16.26	488.93	10.83	0.00
185	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	1.19	37.34	91.64	0.00	18.71	23.02	49.37	25.22	5.20	62.57	3.90	18.75	538.33	10.29	0.00
186	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.23	38.72	92.78	0.00	13.39	19.95	47.14	25.48	5.34	62.05	2.20	16.08	461.70	10.89	0.00
187	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.23	39.02	92.62	0.00	14.00	21.62	47.89	25.49	5.25	62.01	3.35	15.14	496.95	10.91	0.00
188	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	1.23	38.89	92.09	0.00	16.48	22.51	48.57	25.45	5.45	62.07	2.80	18.00	548.13	10.38	0.00
189	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.26	40.27	93.14	0.00	12.51	18.75	46.00	25.71	5.62	61.58	1.65	15.02	470.48	10.94	0.00
190	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.24	39.31	92.57	0.00	14.06	21.05	45.87	25.56	4.89	62.04	3.00	14.11	449.44	11.03	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	PMV_{out} [%]	PD_{asym} [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	PI_{II} [%]	PI_{III} [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{perm,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Cond _h [h]	$q_{c,RF}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	SEER [-]	$Q_{summer,3\%C}$ [%]
191	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.23	39.23	92.09	0.00	17.79	21.99	46.26	25.52	5.07	62.11	2.20	16.83	500.73	10.46	0.00
192	Tokyo	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.27	40.57	93.21	0.00	12.57	18.62	44.21	25.77	5.18	61.61	1.75	13.92	426.84	11.07	0.00
193	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.08	31.51	94.75	19.05	3.18	14.89	50.29	23.14	1.26	29.28	0.00	35.76	5257.63	5.37	0.01
194	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	0.88	24.68	85.03	23.51	38.31	53.19	72.59	21.93	2.25	30.63	0.00	36.29	6069.94	4.96	0.00
195	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.11	32.40	95.18	19.50	2.22	11.21	46.09	23.26	1.38	29.09	0.00	35.59	5205.51	5.38	0.01
196	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.09	31.99	95.06	16.78	3.28	14.52	48.42	23.32	0.69	29.28	0.00	34.68	4863.51	5.35	0.00
197	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	0.89	25.02	87.66	21.01	40.43	51.91	72.09	22.10	1.17	30.66	0.00	35.21	5731.98	4.85	0.00
198	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.12	32.87	95.65	17.33	2.27	10.96	43.68	23.44	0.87	29.11	0.00	34.68	4823.84	5.36	0.00
199	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.22	37.45	97.02	10.32	2.50	5.01	30.52	24.08	1.08	28.42	0.00	31.88	4957.89	5.41	0.00
200	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.00	29.08	91.51	10.98	17.56	38.84	62.48	22.74	2.03	29.87	0.00	32.42	5921.98	4.87	0.00
201	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.24	38.11	97.23	10.59	2.03	3.84	26.92	24.16	1.16	28.30	0.00	31.70	4913.10	5.42	0.00
202	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.26	39.07	97.61	7.96	2.49	4.43	26.89	24.42	0.50	28.27	0.00	30.27	4646.29	5.33	0.00
203	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.03	30.29	93.08	8.60	19.82	35.70	59.06	23.04	1.09	29.75	0.00	30.74	5615.91	4.77	0.00
204	Phoenix	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.27	39.70	97.85	8.05	1.98	3.41	23.48	24.50	0.64	28.16	0.00	30.15	4603.68	5.34	0.00
205	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	0.96	25.83	95.81	13.27	3.43	24.74	68.24	22.79	2.76	30.36	0.00	35.81	4802.96	5.13	0.01
206	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.83	21.93	92.53	25.53	53.73	50.58	79.23	21.98	3.22	31.07	0.00	35.79	5406.13	4.77	0.00
207	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.01	27.72	96.19	15.18	1.80	16.24	57.36	23.02	2.88	29.90	0.00	35.75	4734.09	5.15	0.01
208	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	0.97	26.34	95.92	8.64	3.73	26.12	63.08	22.97	1.93	30.43	0.00	34.40	4483.88	5.08	0.00
209	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.85	22.51	93.48	15.99	52.96	44.14	78.15	22.21	2.10	31.18	0.00	34.71	5136.17	4.65	0.00
210	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.02	28.27	96.29	9.90	1.92	17.96	50.43	23.22	2.28	29.99	0.00	34.51	4432.62	5.11	0.00
211	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.06	30.10	96.82	4.87	2.33	14.47	47.94	23.57	2.58	29.72	0.00	31.65	4558.81	5.16	0.00
212	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	0.92	25.01	94.92	5.20	26.34	37.98	73.27	22.66	3.25	30.59	0.00	31.90	5323.10	4.66	0.00
213	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.10	31.76	97.01	5.65	1.52	8.31	39.79	23.77	2.80	29.37	0.00	31.73	4484.21	5.18	0.00
214	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.09	31.50	97.04	1.43	2.41	14.12	42.27	23.88	1.97	29.64	0.00	30.23	4309.54	5.05	0.00
215	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	0.95	26.14	95.46	2.13	23.74	34.15	66.46	22.98	2.08	30.58	0.00	30.26	5102.29	4.53	0.00
216	Phoenix	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.13	33.07	97.29	1.54	1.57	8.48	37.74	24.07	2.17	29.33	0.00	30.04	4248.62	5.09	0.00
217	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	1.21	37.28	95.98	27.27	12.60	12.61	37.56	23.63	4.83	28.41	0.00	37.18	5743.08	5.28	0.01
218	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	1.04	31.00	91.68	35.37	38.94	38.68	57.71	22.52	6.03	29.50	0.00	38.34	6746.82	4.90	0.01
219	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	1.23	37.86	96.60	27.36	8.31	9.96	35.43	23.73	5.18	28.29	0.00	37.19	5686.71	5.28	0.01
220	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	1.22	37.74	96.28	25.86	12.60	12.58	37.02	23.80	4.38	28.41	0.00	36.31	5275.94	5.28	0.01
221	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	1.05	31.31	92.65	33.21	43.78	37.89	57.07	22.67	5.26	29.52	0.00	37.35	6217.54	4.90	0.01
222	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	1.24	38.32	96.75	25.94	8.31	9.93	34.70	23.90	4.90	28.30	0.00	36.21	5225.78	5.29	0.01

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PDD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{H\%}$ [%]	$PI_{II\%}$ [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Cond _h [h]	$q_{c,ref}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	SEER [-]	$Q_{summer,3\%C}$ [%]
223	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	1.33	42.69	96.86	19.77	10.73	7.52	26.60	24.55	4.78	27.71	0.00	33.37	5308.16	5.34	0.01
224	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	1.16	35.56	94.17	24.23	27.09	29.05	48.67	23.39	6.07	28.83	0.00	33.95	6332.29	4.92	0.01
225	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	1.35	43.16	97.36	19.95	8.29	5.92	24.59	24.63	5.22	27.62	0.00	33.21	5258.73	5.35	0.01
226	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	1.37	44.10	97.11	15.52	10.48	6.82	24.16	24.87	4.27	27.59	0.00	31.75	4898.19	5.32	0.01
227	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	1.18	36.67	95.09	20.20	31.11	27.19	46.91	23.68	5.26	28.73	0.00	32.26	5951.66	4.83	0.00
228	Phoenix	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	1.38	44.54	97.57	15.61	8.13	5.62	22.33	24.94	4.79	27.51	0.00	31.70	4855.23	5.32	0.01
229	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	1.08	31.68	95.95	24.37	4.71	21.22	47.88	23.32	5.67	29.36	0.00	37.12	5408.94	5.10	0.01
230	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	0.96	27.25	94.43	33.67	34.56	37.85	65.07	22.50	6.11	30.09	0.00	37.75	6185.58	4.77	0.01
231	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	1.12	32.91	96.38	25.00	5.00	15.81	43.23	23.50	5.75	29.10	0.00	36.87	5338.77	5.08	0.01
232	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	1.10	32.27	95.93	21.01	5.82	21.91	46.07	23.49	4.91	29.40	0.00	36.19	4991.04	5.09	0.01
233	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	0.97	27.77	94.38	28.60	35.60	35.81	63.21	22.68	5.08	30.15	0.00	36.49	5750.58	4.74	0.01
234	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	1.13	33.47	96.43	21.41	5.30	17.10	42.91	23.67	5.19	29.16	0.00	35.64	4937.60	5.07	0.01
235	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	1.19	36.28	96.84	16.86	3.39	13.56	38.00	24.16	5.71	28.76	0.00	33.01	5008.79	5.16	0.01
236	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	1.05	30.98	95.49	22.84	19.59	29.97	55.68	23.28	6.13	29.56	0.00	33.46	5870.58	4.75	0.01
237	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	1.22	37.29	97.11	17.23	4.69	10.01	34.91	24.31	5.78	28.56	0.00	32.75	4945.29	5.15	0.01
238	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	1.22	37.66	96.82	12.33	3.79	13.29	36.48	24.46	4.95	28.69	0.00	31.64	4659.65	5.11	0.00
239	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	1.08	32.09	95.63	17.03	22.67	29.31	50.08	23.57	5.18	29.53	0.00	31.55	5572.97	4.63	0.00
240	Phoenix	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	1.24	38.64	97.12	12.34	4.82	10.10	33.75	24.60	5.14	28.50	0.00	31.11	4606.36	5.11	0.00
241	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	WC	2.38	87.07	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.41	3.54	64.51	0.00	18.71	1400.24	10.82	0.00
242	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	PID	2.42	87.91	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.53	3.54	64.02	0.00	19.09	1441.71	10.78	0.00
243	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.02	AR	2.38	87.09	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.41	3.54	64.50	0.00	18.69	1400.26	10.82	0.00
244	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	WC	2.37	86.99	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.32	2.55	64.66	0.00	17.94	1273.80	10.97	0.00
245	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	PID	2.40	87.83	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.44	2.53	64.17	0.00	18.30	1311.72	10.93	0.00
246	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.1	0.04	AR	2.37	87.01	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.33	2.55	64.65	0.00	17.94	1273.71	10.97	0.00
247	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	WC	2.47	89.34	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.92	3.51	63.34	0.00	16.73	1310.64	10.93	0.00
248	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	PID	2.50	90.19	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.06	3.50	62.79	0.00	17.13	1352.57	10.88	0.00
249	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.02	AR	2.47	89.36	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.92	3.51	63.33	0.00	16.72	1310.46	10.93	0.00
250	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	WC	2.47	89.64	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.92	2.48	63.28	0.00	15.69	1195.53	11.08	0.00
251	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	PID	2.51	90.49	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.06	2.47	62.73	0.00	16.04	1233.96	11.04	0.00
252	Bangkok	Ins	family	0.2	0.04	AR	2.47	89.66	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.93	2.48	63.27	0.00	15.69	1195.29	11.08	0.00
253	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	2.10	78.56	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	28.29	2.89	69.86	2.10	16.36	1108.31	11.02	0.00
254	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	2.12	79.54	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.38	2.89	69.45	1.60	16.63	1138.07	11.00	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PDD_{avg} [%]	PMV_{out} [%]	PD_{asym} [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	PI_{H} [%]	PI_{III} [%]	T_{avg} [°C]	$q_{ref,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	Condh [h]	$q_{c,ref}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	SEER [-]	$Q_{summer,3\%C}$ [%]
255	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	2.10	78.77	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.31	2.89	69.76	1.95	16.29	1102.12	11.03	0.00
256	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	2.09	78.32	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	28.22	2.01	69.97	2.70	15.63	1013.01	11.15	0.00
257	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	2.11	79.30	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.31	2.01	69.56	1.85	15.91	1039.67	11.13	0.00
258	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	2.09	78.53	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.25	2.01	69.87	2.85	15.57	1008.18	11.15	0.00
259	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	2.16	81.14	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.70	2.81	68.86	0.60	14.73	1039.46	11.13	0.00
260	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	2.19	82.16	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.80	2.81	68.40	0.35	14.99	1069.67	11.11	0.00
261	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	2.17	81.27	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.71	2.81	68.79	0.55	14.71	1035.03	11.14	0.00
262	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	2.16	81.36	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.71	1.91	68.78	0.45	13.76	951.88	11.28	0.00
263	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	2.19	82.39	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.81	1.88	68.33	0.50	14.03	979.34	11.26	0.00
264	Bangkok	Ins	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	2.17	81.47	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.72	1.92	68.73	0.70	13.72	948.16	11.29	0.00
265	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	WC	2.27	83.68	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	29.04	3.86	66.68	0.00	17.54	1262.73	10.94	0.00
266	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	PID	2.27	83.68	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	29.04	3.86	66.68	0.00	17.54	1262.76	10.94	0.00
267	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.02	AR	2.27	83.72	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	29.05	3.86	66.67	0.00	17.53	1261.83	10.94	0.00
268	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	WC	2.25	83.54	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	28.97	2.80	66.81	0.00	16.76	1148.94	11.08	0.00
269	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	PID	2.25	83.54	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	28.97	2.80	66.81	0.00	16.76	1148.95	11.08	0.00
270	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.1	0.04	AR	2.26	83.57	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	28.97	2.80	66.79	0.05	16.76	1147.89	11.08	0.00
271	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	WC	2.32	85.56	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	29.45	3.85	65.87	0.00	15.43	1159.21	11.08	0.00
272	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	PID	2.32	85.56	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	29.45	3.85	65.87	0.00	15.43	1159.31	11.08	0.00
273	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.02	AR	2.33	85.58	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	29.45	3.85	65.86	0.00	15.43	1158.44	11.08	0.00
274	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	WC	2.32	85.73	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	29.44	2.76	65.86	0.00	14.30	1054.61	11.23	0.00
275	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	PID	2.32	85.73	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	29.44	2.76	65.86	0.00	14.30	1054.74	11.23	0.00
276	Bangkok	NoIns	family	0.2	0.04	AR	2.32	85.75	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	29.44	2.76	65.85	0.00	14.30	1054.10	11.23	0.00
277	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	WC	2.05	76.53	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12	28.21	3.22	70.96	4.40	16.21	1063.91	11.00	0.00
278	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	PID	2.05	76.58	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	28.21	3.23	70.93	4.45	16.22	1063.99	11.00	0.00
279	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.02	AR	2.06	76.77	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08	28.24	3.22	70.86	4.20	16.12	1056.66	10.99	0.00
280	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	WC	2.04	76.29	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	28.15	2.30	71.04	4.70	15.49	970.75	11.12	0.00
281	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	PID	2.04	76.33	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	28.15	2.34	71.02	4.95	15.50	970.82	11.13	0.00
282	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.1	0.04	AR	2.05	76.52	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	28.18	2.32	70.95	5.10	15.47	965.49	11.12	0.00
283	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	WC	2.10	78.53	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	28.56	3.19	70.23	4.10	14.51	979.59	11.13	0.00
284	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	PID	2.10	78.56	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	28.56	3.20	70.21	3.30	14.51	979.12	11.13	0.00
285	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.02	AR	2.11	78.71	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	28.58	3.19	70.16	2.75	14.50	974.06	11.13	0.00
286	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	WC	2.10	78.63	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	28.56	2.24	70.19	3.40	13.67	892.79	11.28	0.00

Case Study	Climate	Building	Occupancy	Pipe spacing	Screed depth	Control	PMV_{avg} [-]	PPD_{avg} [%]	$PMV_{out\%}$ [%]	$PD_{asym\%}$ [%]	OC_{DH} [°C/h]	$PI_{H\%}$ [%]	$PI_{IIR\%}$ [%]	$T_{f,avg}$ [°C]	$q_{RF,max,C}$ [W/m ²]	RH_{avg} [%]	$Cond_h$ [h]	$q_{C,RF}$ [kWh/m ²]	E_c [kWh]	$SEER$ [-]	$Q_{summet,\%C}$ [%]
287	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	PID	2.10	78.66	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	28.56	2.26	70.17	3.30	13.67	892.86	11.29	0.00
288	Bangkok	NoIns	elderly	0.2	0.04	AR	2.10	78.79	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	28.58	2.24	70.13	3.25	13.66	888.49	11.28	0.00